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**GEOSPATIAL DIRECT-ADDRESS VIDEOS AS ALTERNATIVE PARTICIPATORY
GOVERNANCE DEVICE FOR COMMUNITY PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION AND
DECISION-MAKING AT A SUBDIVISION IN A CITY LOCATED IN LAGUNA,
PHILIPPINES**

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23 June 2024

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GEOSPATIAL DIRECT-ADDRESS VIDEOS AS ALTERNATIVE PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE DEVICE FOR COMMUNITY PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION AND DECISION-MAKING AT A SUBDIVISION IN A CITY LOCATED IN LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **IVAN KHALIL LIJAUCO DESCARTIN** with the title: **“GEOSPATIAL DIRECT-ADDRESS VIDEOS AS ALTERNATIVE PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE DEVICE FOR COMMUNITY PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION AND DECISION-MAKING AT A SUBDIVISION IN A CITY LOCATED IN LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

IVAN KHALIL LIJAUCO DESCARTIN graduated cum laude with a bachelor's degree in Communication major in Multimedia Arts from Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna, where he has been teaching communication and social science courses under the College of Arts and Science since 2014.

In 2011, while still a multimedia arts student, he wrote and directed a short film on Jose Rizal entitled "Transisyonasyon", which eventually won the Gold Prize as well as People's Choice Award in the "Idol Ko Si Rizal" video contest organized by the National Youth Commission. The ceremony was held at the Malacañang Palace, and present was late former president Benigno Simeon Aquino III, who distributed the awards himself.

In 2021, he was a "Teaching and Learning Award" nominee at the Mapúa Malayan Colleges Laguna Faculty Awards during the Mapúa MCL Faculty Congress. Moreover, he also has writing credits as co-author in two textbooks, namely "Introspection: Understanding the Self" and "Ethics: Exploring Moral Philosophy" (published by Books Atbp. Publishing Corporation).

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Soli Deo gloria.

Dedication

This study is dedicated to those who, in their heart of hearts, dream of good governance. May it not remain but a dream.

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ABSTRACT

This study, by way of a thematic analysis, strived to determine the perspectives of barangay decision-makers and of residents of a subdivision in a city located in Laguna on a series of geospatial direct-address videos as an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making using VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power and Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes. The community problems/issues identified by the residents in the direct-address videos were embedded in a digital map of the subdivision so that they can be located geospatially. From the results, Power Over, Power With, and Power Within were observed in some of the residents' insights, plus Increased Feelings of Ownership and notions that run counter to Actual Influence on Institutions. Put together, they evoke the residents' proactive efforts, and pride, in resolving their own problems. But also, Power Over, because of instances when their powerlessness as residents was implied in community-level decision-making. As for the barangay decision-makers' insights on the videos, the most observed was Power Over, which expresses their adherence to the hierarchical ways with which they respond to community problems/issues. As for the participatory outcomes, the most observed, next to N/A, was Improvement of Competencies and Capacities, implying that the barangay decision-makers understand the benefits of using the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Slices of reality are considered to be best captured using video that even film as a medium, known otherwise as the default means of capturing footage, takes the backseat to it due to the immediacy the former brings to the table. Video, as widely deemed by many social scientists, is the best means of documentation available (Flor, 2005), as video footages can be captured quickly especially using mobile phones nowadays. In addition, video is increasingly the tool of choice for data collection among many researchers interested in the “multimodal” character of social interaction. Specifically for this study, video was used to undertake direct-address casual interviews with participants that of which yielded “naturally occurring data” in the form of the interview footages themselves (Jewitt, 2012).

The study strived to establish the perception of barangay-decision makers on geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making, done by conducting a transect walk around a subdivision located at a barangay within a city in Laguna.

Video is often used and has featured extensively in the evolution of social research, in particular within the context of sociology, anthropology, education, and psychology (Jewitt, 2012). There are many ways of using video in research, some of which are by way of participatory video, videography, the use or re-purposing of

existing videos, video elicitation, and video-based fieldwork. To specify, in producing the output, the study adopted some aspects of the participatory video (the participation and the making of the participants' experiences visible by way of the interviews), as well as video elicitation (the showing of the transect map with direct-address videos of residents to the barangay decision-makers to 'elicit' response/reaction) and video-based fieldwork (the undertaking of on-going interviews).

For the purposes of the study, the researcher captured short direct-address interview footages of residents (i.e. those who live in an identified subdivision at a barangay within a city in Laguna) talking about their grievances, all of which were reached by way of the transect walk. Said footages were then inputted as video links in a digital map of the aforementioned subdivision. The overall finished product (the geospatial direct-address videos) was then shown to select barangay decision-makers, whose perceptions on it as an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making were collated and interpreted.

Statement of the Problem

The study's research question is below:

- What are the perspectives of the barangay decision-makers and subdivision residents on the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

It was also the intention of this study to create an alternative platform (specifically the geospatial direct-address videos) for community problem identification on the barangay level, though limited only to a single subdivision.

Objectives of the Study

- To discuss the perspectives of the barangay decision-makers and subdivision residents on the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making using VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power and Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes

Significance of the Study

Invoking an aspect of participatory videos that is true about the purpose of the study, participatory videos demonstrate an ability to capture and nurture valuable knowledge often relegated to the background or neglected by the wayside but can be impactful when brought into the center stage (Tremblay & Jayme, 2015). It is also worth noting that it is important that alternative means for governance be thought up (in this study's case, the use of geospatial direct-address videos) other than the traditional ones in order to stimulate more the participation of the community in decision-making, specifically in the context of public service delivery.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study only covered the barangay context, specifically a subdivision located at a barangay within a city in Laguna. Public service delivery on both the city and provincial level were not included in the overall scope of the research. The focus is only limited to problems/issues on the community level. Problems on a local government or national scale are not accounted for.

Operational Definition of Terminologies

Geospatial Direct-Address Video – in the context of the study, this is a video footage captured of the subdivision residents at a specific location (street or drive) wherein he/she is looking directly at the camera, talking to it

Transect Walk – the method utilized in the study that was used to walk around the identified subdivision alongside a companion/guide, with the purpose of collecting the community problems/issues as perceived by the residents

Increased Feelings of Ownership – a participatory outcome that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks about a heightened commitment to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – a participatory outcome that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident

speaks of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Actual Influence on Institutions – a participatory outcome that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her realization that he/she can actually have an effect on his/her community after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power Over – a distinction about power that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her being in a position to exert control or express formal hierarchical authority over his/her constituents/neighbors/fellow residents, or control or constrain what they are able to do (Participatory Methods, n.d.); that is, after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power To – a distinction about power that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/.her realization that he/she can grow in the process of taking action by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities in addressing the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power With – a distinction about power that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her being able to work alongside/collaborate with their constituents/neighbors/fellow residents in addressing

the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power Within – a distinction about power that emerges in the thematic analysis every time the barangay decision-maker/residents speaks of his/her increased sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem regarding the addressing of the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Below are the details/set of information that are pertinent to the study that was conducted, including related studies.

Participatory Videos

A participatory video, as a tool for empowerment, has firmly evolved in the realm of documentary filmmaking, visual studies, and community development (Kyung-Hwa, 2016). Its potential to empower also has roots in the framework of Participatory Action Research (PAR), a type of research involving the collective action of a select group of respondents in terms of identifying problems and coming up with solutions and courses of action to take to redress it (Colom, 2010). As a visual method, it shares kinship with other creative forms of expression such as photography, drawing, film, drama, music, and creative writing. It is under the discipline of digital storytelling, which is defined as the sharing of experiences aided by technology (“Participatory Visual Methods: A Case Study”, n.d.).

Additionally, it is also a type of participatory action research that directly involves a specific community in the production of visual outputs that may be used to bring its members together, as well as tackle issues head-on and encourage the voicing out of concerns. From “objects of study”, the participants effectively become “protagonist subject” capable of enacting on matters and even possibly inciting

changes, fostering strong bond among a community in the process (Argenti and Signa, 2014).

The creation of participatory videos are interactive by nature, with a practitioner (in this case, the researcher) serving as facilitator in order to encourage participants to muster the capacity to communicate through capturing the world around them visually and in a creative manner (“The Process of Participatory Video”, n.d.). There are numerous stages in the creation of Participatory Videos, namely:

1. Engaging participants in a “safe” environment while also opening up discursive spaces for them; this is typically followed by group-building video exercises to consolidate a sense of collaborative purpose.
2. The participants, typically grouped, would produce video materials to help stimulate dialogue among them.
3. The editing process; paper edits may be used to distance the participants away from the complexity of digital editing, though an editing workshop is also encouraged so that participants may be present in the actual rendering of the final versions of the videos.
4. Group-sharing of the films to generate discourse; it is also note in this stage that the development of a communication strategy is important to

determine the audience to whom the videos would be shown, the time of screening, and the calibration of the content itself.

As mentioned by Anna Colom (2010), the empowering capabilities of Participatory Videos lie not so much in the final product but in the very process itself, as it allows the participants to have a degree of influence in a given political space where decisions that affect them on various levels are commonly made.

Through the steps in making a participatory video, the participants are allowed to undertake a dialogic process that would inevitably lead to an awareness stage, similar to the process postulated by Paulo Freire (1989). In addition to political spaces, participatory videos also enable participants to engage in discourse on pressing issues all while learning about, and reflecting on, the factors that make it so (“Participatory Visual Methods: A Case Study”, n.d.).

Furthermore, its function in involving participants in tackling shared issues is considered important because it drives an evolving process of exploration, commonly resulting in a much deeper understanding of communal concerns (“The Process of Participatory Video”, n.d.). According to Jayalaxshmi Mistry and Andrea Berardi (2011), Participatory Video research can result to better enabling outcomes for participants, while also producing more nuanced and grounded data for academic research.

Conversely speaking, although much has been said about participatory videos’ ability to ‘empower’ and ‘emancipate’ participants, there is only a limited

number of research within the realm of academic inquiry outside the conceptual bounds of the two aforementioned terms (Cornish and Dunn, 2009). Still, participatory videos are seen as engaging participants in a dialogical and self-reflexive process (Ugolotti, 2016).

Ethnovideography

For purposes of clarification, this study would also define an almost similar method to participatory video, which is ethnovideography. Although both are types of digital storytelling commonly used in research, ethnovideography is different from participatory video in that it actually adopts the perspective of the researcher. After all, it would be him/her that would be made to capture fragments of community life on video using his/her set of standards.

In making a participatory video, participants are allowed to shoot their own video outputs, which empowers them in the process by letting them create something that could lead to the addressing of problems concerning their community, either through the screening of said output to community decision-makers or the creation of a discourse space made possible by it (“Participatory Visual Methods: A Case Study”, n.d.).

Ethnovideography, on the other hand, as defined by Flor (2005), is the usage of techniques in small-format video documentation to study and analyze people groups. It concerns itself with five types of subject: people, places, events, processes, and social problems. Though many question the integrity of data (known

as audio-visual records) in ethnovideography, such as the subjectivity and researcher bias that go into the process of documentation, it is argued that footage captured in ethnovideography are 'recordings of reality' and not symbolic ones prone to abstractions, thus making it more reliable.

Cellphilms

Due to recent participatory research practices that make use of mobile devices to create and share images and experiences for purposes of agency-building and empowerment, Jonathan Dockney and Keyan Tomaselli were inspired to come up with the term "*cellphilm*", (a portmanteau of "cellphone" and "film"). As mobile phones are virtually everywhere nowadays, Katie MacEntee, Casey Burkholder, and Joshua Schwab-Cartas (2016) see in them a 'new way forward' for participatory visual research, as its adoption and integration into the fabric of rural-communal life will be rather easy, if not totally seamless.

Discourse Communities and Community Conversations

One of the most important aspects of this study is its roots in community discourse. A term coined by sociolinguist Martin Nystrand (1982), a discourse community centers mainly on a group of people who share discursive commonalities, understood as basic values and assumptions, and also ways in communicating about certain goals (Borg, 2003). The concept of discourse community belongs in the much wider field of genre analysis, or the study of how language is used differently depending on a particular context (Hopkins & Dudley-Evans, 1988).

Each discourse community has its own set of unspoken rules that govern each and every member's actions and decisions. According to James Porter (1992), it is defined as a constraining textual system rooted in languages, practices, and beliefs, consolidated by a common focus. For John Swales (1990), on the other hand, discourse communities are "groups that have goals or purposes, and use communication to achieve these goals." In addition, he has posited six defining characteristics of discourse communities:

1. Has a broadly agreed set of common goals.
2. Has mechanism of intercommunication among its members.
3. Uses its participatory mechanisms primarily to provide information and feedback
4. Utilizes and hence possesses one or more genres in the communicative furtherance of its aims.
5. In addition to owning genres, it has acquired some specific lexis
6. Has a threshold level of members with a suitable degree of relevant content and discursual expertise.

In terms of language, commonly used in discourse communities is what Patricia Bizzell (1992) refers to as register (or diatype): a sociolinguistic concept that centers on the interrelationship between the use and production of text and a given community's interpretive conventions. This is further defined by Michael Halliday (1989) as the choices and decisions made by speakers in terms of grammar and lexicon depending on context and situation. This renders the concept of discourse communities different from related fields, specifically speech community (or 'native discourse community'), or the exploration of the use of inherited language or dialect (Bizzell, 1992), and rhetorical community, or the study of communication in a given context but divorced from its link with the idea of community (Miller, 1994).

While discourse communities focus mainly on situational contexts and specific beliefs and assumptions that guide socio-specific dialogues, community conversations, on the other hand, are action-oriented in that they encourage dialogue to come up with solutions to a vast array of problems, often involving diverse stakeholders.

According to Public Agenda (n.d.), community conversations give government officials and community leaders the chance to actively engage members of a community in "productive, action-oriented deliberation." They are specifically designed to explore ideas, previously untapped resources, and problem-solving strategies of varying nature that could be extracted from the coming together of minds and personalities around a shared challenge, issue, or concern (Swedeen, Cooney, Moss, and Carter, 2012).

A barangay located within a city in Laguna, specifically at a subdivision, will serve as both the locus and the context from which a discourse community, and eventually a nuanced community conversation, would be extracted and created, respectively, with primary emphasis on what role its various conventions, power mechanisms, institutional hierarchies, and numerous vested interests (Porter, 1992) play in the dynamics of the relationship between the people and the decision-makers as it relates to public service delivery. The participatory video variable is also integrated, but specifically in the form of geospatial direct-address videos, so as to gauge its potential as a conduit to successful community conversation, which, in terms of impact, is able to “inform district practices and government policies, to catalyzing collaborations across existing community organizations and programs, and creating new citizen-led initiatives (Public Agenda, n.d.).

Public Service Delivery and ICT

According to Anwar Shah (2005), the public’s trust in public sector performances in delivering services in line with the preferences of citizens has been considered weak in developing countries, with the reason being most politicians and bureaucrats concern themselves more with rent-seeking activities than with delivering services to their citizens, which often lead to citizen disenchantment.

Running counter to the aforementioned expression of power, though, is the consistent flourishing of what is commonly termed as the “Information Revolution” (or “Globalization of Information”), which empowers citizens by way of a more liberal access to information. But citizen empowerment alone is not really considered

enough to ensure quality public service, for it must go hand in hand with improved governance.

In addition, citizen and community empowerment can only do so much, and would prove to be instrumental only if it is complemented with governance reforms, that which includes the bureaucracy itself, political processes, the judiciary, and the frontline providers (Asian Development Bank, 2013). Improving local service delivery is a function made possible by the triangulation of policies, institutions, and finance within a value-based and principle-oriented framework of governance (PIDS and UNICEF, 2009). With these in mind, several countries turn to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). The use of ICT has the potential to improve citizens' otherwise asymmetrical access to information and better handle the principal-agent problem (Gurbaxani and Whang, 1991).

In an article published in the Philippine Daily Inquirer, results from a survey conducted by the United Nations (UN) show that the Philippines is slowly improving in terms of the maximization of ICT use in public service delivery. In the said E-Government survey, the Philippines improved by 24 places to rank 71st (out of 193 countries) in e-government development (Enano, 2016). According to a joint project of the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) and UNICEF (2009) that tackles the relationship between local service delivery and the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), policy effectiveness may be achieved through the following:

- The need for an adaptive and responsive approach rather than prescriptive approach to policy-making and implementation
- The adoption of an inclusive human development approach that guarantees targeting the real beneficiaries
- The need for aggressive promotion and effective implementation of performance-based and results-oriented incentive system
- The imperative to link local development plans with those of the regional and national for greater development impacts

The first three factors are essential to this study, as they all highlight a more proactive and multidirectional approach to addressing flaws in local service delivery. The unique aspect of the study, though, is its primary focus on the enhancement of the access to knowledge through electronic publishing (Bhatnagar, 2014), in this case the creation of a participatory video to, in a way, enable public interest groups to “pressure their government for improvements in government services” (Shah, 2005). Finally, the “enhancement of the access to knowledge” part would not be limited to the citizens only but would also extend to local decision-makers as well.

Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) and Rapid Rural Appraisal (RRA)

According to Robert Chambers (1992), the Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) refers to a family of approaches/methods that equip or enable people to

“share, enhance and analyse their knowledge of life and conditions, to plan and to act.” Among many other frameworks and/or approaches (such as activist participatory research and applied anthropology), the PRA is rooted in Rapid Rural Appraisal (RRA), which is an approach to development research where information elicited and extracted by outsiders. With the PRA, on the other hand, information is shared and owned by local people.

Although a myriad of differences between PRA and RRA have long since been established, they also share great similarities. As streamlined from Somluckrat Grandstaff, Terry Grandstaff, and George Lovelace (1987), Jennifer McCracken, Jules Pretty, and Gordon Conway (1988), and Bara Gueye and Karen Freudemberger (1990), the following are just but some of the “**A Principles**” shared between these two appraisal methods:

- **A Reversal of Learning** – to directly learn from rural people on site, face-to-face, allowing one to gain from local physical, technical and social knowledge.
- **Learning Rapidly and Progressively** – and with heightened consciousness towards exploring, with flexible use of methods, and an emphasis on opportunism, improvisation, iteration, and cross-checking, without following a blueprint and instead being adaptable while learning along the way

- **Offsetting Biases** – directly quoting Chambers (1992): “Being relaxed and not rushing, listening not lecturing, probing instead of passing on to the next topic, being unimposing instead of important, and seeking out the poorer people and women, and learning their concerns and priorities.”
- **Optimizing Trade-Offs** – this is in keeping with the idea that trade-offs are necessary; that is, trade-offs between quantity, relevance, accuracy and timeliness, which includes the principles relating to “optimal ignorance”: knowing what it is not worth knowing, and of appropriate imprecision; not measuring more than needed. Quoting John Maynard Keynes: “It is better to be approximately right than precisely wrong.”
- **Triangulating** – refers to the use of a wide range (usually three) of methods, types of information, investigators, as well as disciplines to cross-check data (Grandstaff, Grandstaff and Lovelace, 1987; Gueye and Freudenberger, 1991)
- **Seeking Diversity** – this alludes to the idea of “maximizing the diversity and richness of information” (Dunn and McMillan, 1991), which involves, but is not limited to, non-statistical sampling; “seeking diversity” goes beyond the mere cross-checking of data (as represented by the “Triangulating” principle), for it “deliberately looks for, notices and investigates contradictions, anomalies, and differentness.”

As for the “**B Principles**”, they are the following:

- **Facilitating** – investigation, analysis, presentation, and learning by rural people are merely facilitated, so that they get to present and own the outcomes, as well as learn; the expression/phrase that best captures this principle is “handing over the stick” (or pen/chalk), which refers to the outsider researcher starting a process and then sitting back or walking away, and not anymore interrupting or interviewing
- **Self-Critical Awareness and Responsibility** – here, the facilitator consistently examines his/her behavior and tries to improve on, and even embrace, errors; welcoming error as an opportunity to learn as well as accepting personal responsibility
- **Sharing** – this pertains to the sharing of ideas or information between rural people, as well as between rural people and facilitators and different organizations

Transect Walk

One of the PRA and RRA methods on the list developed by Chambers (1992) includes transect walks, which, as defined, are the systematic walking with informants through an area, observing, asking, listening, identifying, discussing.

They also get to identify different zones, local technologies, introduced technologies, all the while seeking problems, solutions and opportunities, plus mapping and diagramming resources and findings.

As defined by Laura Puttkamer (2017) in her “parCitypatory” website/blog, a transect walk is a participatory exercise wherein members of a community, planners, and even municipality representatives walk through and around various areas of the neighborhood, in the process interviewing passersby and then afterwards drawing a map with observations of characteristics, risks, and existing solutions after the walk.

Such transect walks are typically conducted in villages for health and sanitation planning, but are used increasingly in urban settings too. Richie Thomas (2021), in an article on “Transect Walks”, wrote of the three standard types of transect walks as enumerated by N. Narayanasamy (2009): Village, Resource, and Cultural.

Village Transects are defined as those concerned with infrastructure, detailing the dwelling space of the community of interest. A new name for said transect type has been posited (to eliminate the colonial weight of the term “village”) by Thomas (2021), “residential transects”, but available literature still use the term “village transect”.

The next one is **Resource Transect**, which is considered to be the most common type of transect walk. Resource transects are those which seek to

document the resources any given society has available to them and that could be exploited for development purposes (Debnath & Bardhan, 2018; Mahiri, 1998).

Finally, **Cultural Transects**, which are most focused on human activity, not to mention that they are longitudinal (as such walks follow individuals over several days or weeks) (Mukherjee, 1998; Narayanasamy, 2009). Such transects can accumulate large quantities of narrative-heavy data that introduce human connection into research projects/initiatives.

Transect Map

Transect maps, or transect diagrams, are accomplished once transect walks are concluded, and are tools used by a group undertaking observation-based community improvement (Catalytic Communities, nd). The endgoal of transect mapping is for informed community members and people with the requisite technical skills to be able to identify, establish, and propose solutions to the issues that were diagrammed along the map/s.

Figure 1.

Example of a Transect Map/Transect Diagram.

Transect maps help, by spatially locating identified issues, in a community's overall pursuit of solutions. Essentially, once the transect walks were conducted and the transect maps were created, the data/results can be left with community leader/community decision-makers for them to utilize for both short-term and long-term development initiatives.

Direct-Address Video

In an article written by Alex Gerbaz (2008) published in the journal *Film-Philosophy*, a two-pronged question is posed: "Has the ubiquitous intervention of screens in our lives thus made it harder to understand and communicate directly with one another? Or, have screens extended our capacity to emphasize and socialize, bringing us face-to-face with people and points of view that we otherwise would never have encountered?" Another point advanced by said article is that the technique of the direct address is an example of the camera's capacity to bring a

social dimension into its perception, in order that it “not only faces a social world but is also literally faced by it.”

In simple terms, direct-address videos are those that contain footage of people generally looking in the direction of the audience or speaking or talking directly to the camera (Gerbaz, 2008). Among the most renowned proponents of the direct-address approach in filmmaking, specifically documentary filmmaking, is Errol Morris, who even devised a contraption, called the “interrotron”, to perfect said approach. As pictured below (Figure 2), the “interrotron” is essentially several modified teleprompters used to complement each other, which “bounces a live image of Morris onto a glass plate in front of the interviewee”; in turn, the “interviewee responds to an image of Morris that floats directly in line with the camera.” (Rosenheim, 1996)

Figure 2.

The Interrotron.

Some of the effects of the “interrotron” on a footage (be it film or video), among others, is a heightened sense of intimacy. It also amplifies its confrontational edge, which is only appropriate as topics discussed in direct-address interviews/videos are at times very much confrontational. One notable documentary that made use of the “interrotron” (with direct-address implications) was the 1988 film “The Thin Blue Line” directed by Errol Morris, which is about a man named Randall Dale Adams who was wrongfully imprisoned for murder. Throughout the documentary, his interviews were that of him seemingly looking directly at the camera and, by extension, the audience, creating an “interrogating effect”.

Figure 3.

Randall Dale Adams in the documentary film “The Thin Blue Line” (1988).

Tom Brown (2012), in his book “Breaking the Fourth Wall: Direct Address in the Cinema”, it has been forwarded that direct-address moments in film (of when

characters or subjects look and talk directly at the camera) produce a sense of intimacy between the character/subject and the audience/viewer, as addressing the spectator is “a very particular gesture towards intimacy”. Also, it gives the character/subject a claim to agency; that is, he or she seemingly has the freedom and capacity to act upon something.

Direct-address is also said to convey “present-ness” and a sense of immediacy. Finally, that it allows the character/subject to occupy a “superior epistemic position” in that he/she who directly addresses the audience/viewers “know” more than others; that he/she generally holds a privileged position in the overall narrative and that he/she may have access to truths unavailable to others.

Barangay Grievance Redress Mechanism

In 2016, the Grievance Redress Mechanism (GRM) was established under the Social and Environmental Safeguards (SES) Unit of the Philippine Rural Development Project (PRDP), with the purpose of seeking “feedback on the beneficiaries as well as resolve complaints on project activities and performance.” An article (2016) put out on the official PRDP website establishes the overall goal behind the GRM: that the resolution of grievances not reach regional or central offices anymore, instead being addressed and solved already on the barangay level.

The article in question was specifically about the two-day training workshop as conducted by the Regional Project Coordination (RPCO) in Kalinga, which is part of the overall effort to establish a GRM there. During said workshop, then-Tanudan

Vice-Mayor David Calsiyao was quoted: “Let us apply what we have learned from this week’s activities and resolve arising issues within our own barangays.”

Said GRM refers to the filing of complaints or queries or feedbacks in the form of call, text message, email, drop box, or personal appearance. In an infographic (see figure below) published on the official website of the Department of Agrarian Reform (see figure below) published on the official website of the Department of Agrarian Form, said channels were illustrated, as well as the general GRM process as agreed-upon and implemented.

Figure 4.

The Department of Agrarian Reform’s (DAR) Grievance Redress Mechanism (GRM) Infographic.

Related Studies

A study conducted by Gerby Muya, Eugene Lopez, Marvin Malacaman, Jayson Suba, & Nelson Tenorio (2016) used a participatory video as a means to determine a group of eight farmers' themes of experience and change after adopting the Gibberellic Acid Technology, an advance method used in aster flower production in Los Banos, Laguna (in Bayog). The main similarity it has with this study is that it also focuses on the use of participatory video as a tool for documenting a facet of the respondents' perception in relation to how said technology might potentially alter their lives. The difference, on the other hand, is its emphasis on technology acceptance and knowledge transfer in the context of agriculture, not on expressions of power in relation to community dialogue and the various outcomes in the participatory framework.

Furthermore, Valerainne Lopez, Edgie Francis Uyanguren, and Celeste Vallejos (2019) describe the use of a module-based participatory video workshop in empowering minority groups, specifically the Lumads, to assert their voices and, by extension, effect communal, political, and cultural changes. The training generated three video outputs about the following: 1.) the experiences of a teacher in a Lumad school; 2.) the life of a Lumad farmer; 3.) the history of the Lumad community.

Another participatory video-based study was done by Katharine Haynes and Thomas Tanner (2013), which was conducted in three communities in Eastern Samar. Although it centers on climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction,

it has commonalities with this study in that it also has substantial concern for both informing decision-making processes and inspiring direct action on issues through empowerment as well. In its results, it was suggested that the participatory video process itself was indeed effective in raising important issues with decision-makers and effecting significant change on the community level.

In addition, Rikin Gandhi, Rajesh Veeraraghavan, Kentaro Toyama, and Vanaja Ramprasad (2007) also made use of the participatory process in trying to cascade essential agricultural information to small farmers in India; an initiative they have called “Digital Green”. The researchers have made use of a participatory process for content creation/production, established a locally-generated digital video database, and human-mediated instruction for training in the adoption of the participatory video process, all of which this study would also do. Although the results of the study were still very much preliminary and inconclusive, they were considered promising, as they were seen to have increased agricultural practices adoption six to seven times compared to person-only agricultural extension.

Although its priority was to explore people’s communal relationship with the environment, an inquiry conducted by Claudia Magallanes-Blanco (2014) that focuses on five (5) participatory videos from Peru, Kenya, the Philippines, Mexico, and France/Argentina bears significant similarities with this study in terms of how the relationship of its two main variables (indigenous peoples and Mother Earth) may be established in much the same way the dialogic one between the community members and barangay decision-makers is. Both also repurpose the functions of participatory video into serving political activism (i.e. the airing of grievances).

A similar-minded project was spearheaded by the Darwin Initiative, a grant scheme funded by the UK government that strives to preserve biodiversity and protect the environment via region-specific, locally-based projects. In a project article (2018) published in their newsletter, details about trainings on participatory video skills conducted in indigenous communities in and around the Iwokrama Rainforest Reserve and the Kanuku Mountains in Guyana were presented. Said trainings were facilitated to share with young people some basic knowledge on making storyboards, using video equipment, and conducting proper interviews. The goal was to establish dialogic rapport between the youth and the elders of said communities. All this is premised on the idea that sharing traditional knowledge through ICT is integral in overall conservation efforts and the management of protected areas.

Related to the abovementioned project, an earlier study conducted by Marites Balbas, Arnold Macadangdang, Jan van der Ploeg, and Nicolien Pul (2012) also outlines the importance of communication in the context of environmental conservation, but with specific focus on safeguarding the endangered Philippine crocodile. By way of participatory videos and photos, proper communal dialogue on the survival of said specie among those who live in close proximity to its habitat was facilitated.

In a paper by Namita Singh, Chris High, Andy Lane, and Sue Oreszczy (2017), however, a more critical stand was taken on the use of participatory videos in interrogating gender and development issues. With young women from Hyderabad (a community in India) as participants, the study tackled the possible implications of

long-term participatory video projects as used by Nongovernment Organizations (NGOs) on agency-building among women, outlining that although they do help to an extent, sustaining the effects in the presence of power relations will prove to be rather challenging.

Regarding the use of cellphones in participatory video projects (referred to as “*cellphfilms*”), scholar-activist researchers Joshua Schwab-Cartas and Claudia Mitchell (2014) worked with two rural communities in both South Africa and Southern Mexico. The aim was to determine the extent to which the use of local technologies can be sustained in the rural-communal setting. Exploratory in nature, the study concluded that with or without research initiatives, rural communities are still generally fast in adapting local technologies in relation to self-determination and collective goal-setting.

In terms of transect walk as tool used in qualitative research, and more specifically for social change, a study conducted by Deidre Geduld, Heloise Sathorar, and Nokhanyo N. Mdzanga (2021) postulates the incorporation of transect walk as critical community-mapping tool to develop the intercultural awareness of student teachers in South Africa. As part of the student teachers’ preparation to embracing a more critical approach to pedagogy, it has been suggested that transect walks be part of the curriculum.

Another transect walk-centric study was that conducted by Theresa Lorenzo and Jane Motau (2014), which focuses on transect walks being a means to establish opportunities and challenges for youth with disabilities in Winterveldt, South Africa.

An equally interesting paper published by Ishmail Mahiri (2001) compares the transect walks conducted by both experts and local people. The study found out, among other things, is that it is difficult to mobilize professionals and get them out to do fieldwork. Also, that the rural people express great enthusiasm when it comes to sharing their knowledge about their immediate environment, though there is competition among each other in terms of who knows most and best about the topic.

But as a whole, said study has concluded that the transect walks fostered an open atmosphere for the people to express freely their knowledge and views, without necessarily being intimidated by, or under the influence of, professionals. This led to the paper appealing that the inappropriate mandate and dominance of opinion and views accorded to experts and/or professionals be re-examined (Chambers, 1997), because local knowledge should have a share of the platform, and have a sure place in policy formulation.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, the study made use of VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power, under which were incorporated Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes, as lifted from their Working Paper on Participatory Communication. Both were used in the thematic analysis of the barangay decision-makers' perception on the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making in a subdivision at a barangay located within a city in Laguna. It is also

significant to note that both the power distinctions and the participatory outcomes are framed under community conversations.

The geospatial direct-address videos were captured by adhering to one of the basic tenets that fall under the larger umbrella of the Cinema Direct theory of documentary filmmaking: that is, for the subject to look straight in the direction of the camera and, by extension, the audience. In this study's case, as mentioned, while communicating their perceived problems/issues within the subdivision.

The Participatory Model of Development Communication

According to Guy Bessette (2004), Participatory Development Communication, or PDC, is rooted in both development communication and participatory research, and is defined as a meticulously-planned activity based on the participatory process and also on media and interpersonal communication, which then facilitates a dialogue among various stakeholders concerning a common development problem or goal, with a primary objective of developing and implementing a set of activities and interventions to contribute to its solution (or its realization), and which complements the initiative. This definition was ratified by the Communication for Development Roundtable in 2005.

Figure 5.

The Participatory Communication Research Action.

Indeed, theoretically speaking, Participatory Development Communication does inspire dialogue and empowerment, with the fundamental aim of encouraging people to handle challenges and give them power to influence the direction of their respective lives (Muniz, 2010). Empowerment, according to Deepa Narayan (2005), is the bolstering of the poor's various assets and capabilities to participate in, negotiate with, and hold accountable several institutions that directly affect their lives. Participation for empowerment, indeed, is about the augmentation of people's capacities, especially those of the marginalized ones, in the context of their own communities and also the demand in governance.

In a World Bank Working Paper written by Thomas Tufte and Paolo Mefalopulos (2009), it was said that there are two main approaches to participation: the social movement perspective and the project-based or institutional perspective. The social movement perspective is mainly about the concept of participation itself

being the goal, with the result being direct empowerment. The project-based or institutional perspective, on the other hand, centers on participation being used as a tool to offer solutions to pre-established goals usually defined by someone external to the very community.

PDC, as a methodology according to Muniz (2010), postulates an approach to the sharing of knowledge that is horizontal in orientation mainly through media and interpersonal group communication. It then combines the “mirroring” features of either video (Participatory Video) or photography (Participatory Photography) to focus on what is worth looking at or for and valuing grassroots people’s knowledge of their respective communities.

Furthermore, essential to this study’s framework is the continuum of outcomes identified when participatory methods or strategies are employed in a particular intervention. The outcomes, as enumerated in the aforementioned Working Paper on Participatory Communication (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009) are as follows:

- Psycho-social outcomes of increased **feelings of ownership** of a problem and a commitment to do something about it
- **Improvement of competencies and capacities** required to engage with the defined development problem
- Actual **influence on institutions** that can affect an individual or community

Dialogue

According to Paulo Freire (1973), dialogue is the encounter between people with the primary goal of naming the world. In addition, he also stated that “naming the world”, which is also called ‘problem definition’, concerns itself with dialogues about problems that are usually of social or economic nature. A free and open conversation about issues is a ‘primordial right’, and is one of participatory communication’s core principles.

Voice

This is primarily focused on lending voice to marginalized groups and also a space on which they could talk about issues and other concerns. The role of media was also highlighted here, especially the continued augmentation and sustenance of community media to provide platform for public discourse about a wide range of problems.

Liberating Pedagogy

The role of a catalyst, which may come in the form of either a radio or television program or even a person, is given emphasis here. The latter may either be a part of the community itself or a complete outsider ‘looking in’. In both cases, he/she would play the role of dialogic facilitator. This principle is not about informing the misinformed in a manner that is non-participatory, therefore defeating its very purpose. Instead, it is concerned most with catalyzing a dialogue wherein collective problem identification and solution would happen (Freire, 1974).

Action-Reflection-Action

Another crux of participatory communication, apart from dialogue, is action. Authentic empowerment happens based on the courses of action taken by a certain community after the dialogue. The key results of participatory communication are the people's articulation of their awareness and also a certain commitment to action. In order to fix a problem, the community must first claim ownership to it, all while also showing commitment to solving it. This is the essence of what Luiz Ramiro Beltran (1979) called "horizontal communication", defined as a way of pointing out the things that participatory communication would be able to bring to the table. This stands in stark contrast to diffusion-and-effects models of communication.

Power and Empowerment

To some people, power is very difficult to tackle or explore, as it is often perceived as a dangerously stern, immutably top-down concept. But for Lisa VeneKlasen and Valerie Miller (2002), the proponents of various distinctions about power, it is actually both dynamic and multidimensional, with its application varying according to situation or context. From the assumption that power is merely all about domination and resistance, the distinctions postulated by the two went to prove that it could also be used in terms of collaboration or even transformation. Although the researchers themselves have admitted that power is relatively difficult to analyze due to it being invisible at times, they have nonetheless enumerated four distinctions of

power through which certain practices and manifestations of it could be filtered, namely:

- **Power over:** This is the most recognizable form of power. This has many negative associations, such as wealth, force, repression, coercion, discrimination, abuse, and corruption. Having power, according to conventional belief, involves taking it from someone else and then using it to subjugate or dominate others. With this in mind, academics have recommended to think of alternative forms of leadership and decision-making in order to promote more democratic forms of power. As a result, three alternatives were created to offer positive ways of expressing the concept and to encourage equity in structured relationships.
- **Power with:** This has a lot to do with equalizing otherwise very different interests in order to establish collective strength. Rooted in collaboration, solidarity, and mutual support, this form of power can help inch gaps and build bridges to reduce social conflict, eliminate hierarchies, and promote equity in relationships.
- **Power to:** Centers on people's unique ability to shape his or her life and world. If based on mutual support, it could open up possibilities for *power with*.

- **Power within:** Concerns itself with a person's self-knowledge and sense of worth. This also emphasizes an individual's ability to recognize differences across the interest of various groups of people while also respecting them. This is the form of power that banks on a person's capacity to imagine and create hope, for it affirms the human search for dignity and a sense of fulfillment.

Figure 6 (below) shows the different dimensions of 'Power over', from implicit or invisible ones to the most visible expressions of it, that irrevocably shape political participation and advocacy. Conversely, the table also presents various strategies (lowermost row) to counter feelings of helplessness and powerlessness brought about by 'Power over'.

In this study's context, it was explored as to whether or not the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making in a subdivision at a barangay located within a city in Laguna, could upset the dominant 'power over' and create a more dialogic space where shared issues on the community level could be tackled and talked about in a more dynamic and multidirectional way.

Figure 6.

Power, Political Participation, and Social Change.

Mechanisms and strategies	Invisible power: shaping meaning	Hidden power: setting the political agenda	Visible power: observable decision making
	Problems and issues are not only kept from the decision-making table, but also from the minds and consciousness of the different players involved.	Influence by controlling who gets to the decision-making table and what gets on the agenda.	The visible and definable aspects of political power – the formal rules, structures, authorities, institutions, and procedures of decision making.
<p>Mechanisms: different expressions and forms of power</p> <p>Participation in public decision making seems relatively straightforward on the surface. It appears to be determined by the political context, clout, resources, and expertise of different political actors. Yet invisible and hidden mechanisms of power shape the effectiveness of citizen participation. These mechanisms can lead to powerlessness, conflict, marginalisation, and resistance.</p> <p>Different strategies are required to counter these mechanisms so that political participation can be more inclusive and so people can exercise their rights and responsibilities as citizens. (See below.)</p>	<p><i>Socialisation and control of information:</i> Processes, practices, cultural norms, and customs shape people's understanding of their needs, roles, possibilities, and actions in ways that deter effective action for change.</p> <p>Among marginal groups, socialisation internalises feelings of subordination, apathy, self-blame, powerlessness, unworthiness, hostility, anger, etc.</p> <p>Crucial information is concealed or inaccessible.</p>	<p><i>Exclusion and delegitimisation:</i> Certain groups (and their issues) are excluded from decision making by society's and political's unwritten rules, practices, and institutions. The media does not often consider these groups' issues to be mainstream or newsworthy.</p> <p>They and their grievances are made invisible by intimidation, misinformation, and cooption. Leaders are labelled trouble-makers or unrepresentative; issues such as domestic violence are relegated to the private realm of the family and therefore not subject to public action.</p>	<p><i>Formal institutions, officials and instruments:</i> Visible mechanisms of power shape the formal ground rules of society.</p> <p>Formal institutions and officials: President, Prime Minister, legislature, courts, ministries, police, military, etc. United Nations, IMF, World Bank; Private sector: industry, multinational corporations, chamber of commerce.</p> <p>Instruments: Policies, laws, constitutions, budgets, regulations, conventions, implementing mechanisms, etc.</p> <p>Forms of discrimination: biased laws/policies (for example health care policies that do not address women's reproductive needs); closed and unrepresentative decision making structures (parliaments, courts, etc.)</p>
<p>Strategies: principal advocacy strategies to counter powerlessness and exclusion</p> <p>Social justice advocacy requires comprehensive action strategies that address the different forms of visible, hidden, and invisible power by tapping alternative sources of power (power with, within and to).</p> <p>(The arrows reflect the interactive relationships between the different forms of power and the different types of strategies.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education for confidence, citizenship, collaboration, political awareness, political analysis, and using alternative media • Sharing stories, speaking out and connecting with others, affirming resistance, linking concrete daily problems with rights • Investigation, action research and dissemination of concealed information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building active constituencies around common concerns • Strengthening organisations, coalitions, movements, and accountable leaders • Mobilising around shared agendas: demonstrating clout through direct action • Participatory research and dissemination of information that legitimise the issues of the excluded groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lobbying and monitoring • Negotiation and litigation • Public education and media • Policy research, proposals • Shadow reports • Marches and demonstrations • Voting and running for office • Modelling innovations • Collaboration • Etc.

Cinema Direct

Also called direct cinema, this is the approach commonly used by observer-documentarists that originated in North America between 1958 and 1962 and was developed by Jean Rouch in France. In simple terms, in cinema direct, nothing is dictated and the output is as much the creation of the filmmaker as it is of the subject. There are no blockings, and the subject's actions are not determined by camera angles, movements, or the positioning of said equipment. And due to

equipment considerations and subject participation, it is the most appropriate documentary medium for developing countries (Flor, 2005).

The direct cinema approach to documentary filmmaking is taking the camera to a situation and waiting for things to unfold, even for a crisis to happen, with an aspiration towards non-involvement or even complete invisibility. In this approach, the filmmaker is never a catalyst, an instigator, or a provocateur. Instead, he/she just captures footage in the most unobtrusive way possible (Barnouw, 1993).

This theoretical sensibility was applied to the participants (i.e. the subdivision residents) talking in front of, and directly to, the camera, specifically on the lack of coaching or “directing” on the part of the researcher so that the participants get to communicate their complaints/grievances as freely as they can by way of the direct-address videos.

With that said, there are two other major types of approach to documentary filmmaking: cinema verite and observational cinema (see figure below).

Figure 7.

Direct Cinema, Cinema Verite, and Observational Cinema.

Community Conversation

To reiterate, community conversations give government officials and community leaders the chance to actively engage members of a community in “productive, action-oriented deliberation”, which is the aim of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device in this study.

Specifically, community conversations, which can be made possible by way of the geospatial direct-address videos, are designed to reckon with ideas, as well as untapped resources and various problem-solving strategies, that would result from the coming together of minds and different personalities around a shared set of issues (Swedeen, Cooney, Moss, and Carter, 2012).

Just as significant as “community conversations” are to the study’s theoretical framework are “discourse communities”. As established in the literature review, a discourse community centers mainly on a group who share discursive commonalities, understood as basic values and assumptions, and also ways in

communicating about certain goals, at times with community problem identification and the subsequent decisions to be made in mind. In the context of the study, the “discourse communities” identified are both the subdivision residents (who took part in the geospatial direct-address videos) and the select members of the Barangay Council/the Sangguniang Barangay (who participated in the Focus Group Discussion).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 8.

Conceptual Framework.

The study's conceptual framework is framed under "community conversation", seeing as the output that was produced (the geospatial direct-address videos) is action-oriented in that they encourage dialogue to come up with solutions to, or make decisions on, the community problems identified, involving both the subdivision residents and the Barangay Council/Sangguniang Barangay decision-makers. As for the very core of the framework, it is VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power, within which figure Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes.

The geospatial direct-address videos (with the contents of the "videos" being the participating residents talking about problems/issues that they know of in and around the subdivision) were captured by way of a transect walk that the researcher conducted, as predicated on the Cinema Direct theory of documentary filmmaking. Broadly speaking, said theory champions observational and non-interventional filmmaking, though, for the purposes of this study, it tapped into the "direct-address" approach that falls under it, which is defined as "when a character looks in the direction of the audience". As a result, it was made a basic requirement that the direct-address videos contain the participants speaking directly to the camera while detailing the problems/issues.

Some of the residents' insights as communicated through the geospatial direct-address videos were thematically analyzed in terms of the aforementioned distinctions about power, as well as the insights from the Focus Group Discussion conducted with the barangay decision-makers (for the latter, they were also analyzed

based on Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes) as far as the videos being an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making is concerned.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

To kickstart the process, the researcher first identified a companion/guide for the transect walk that was conducted. Said companion/guide was originally set to be different, a carpenter and maintenance man who has been chosen on the basis of his being a resident in the subdivision all his life, as well as his not being affiliated with the Barangay Council or any systems of leadership within the subdivision, but who is nonetheless knowledgeable about the community. But because he did not respond anymore to the researcher's repeated follow-ups despite an initial conversation with him, the plan for him to be the companion/guide was dropped.

As replacement, a former Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) councilor and former Barangay secretary was instead chosen, as she also satisfied the abovementioned qualifiers. For full disclosure, the companion/guide is the researcher's relative (his aunt). In a study conducted by Christina Chavez (2008), there are varying levels of "insiderness" or "outsiderness" when it comes to one's positionality in a research study, so having a relative as companion/guide for the specific purposes of the paper was not decided on out of convenience because she is "family" (Chavez, in her study, wrote that her family being the subject of her research does not make the process any easier; that there are both insider advantages as well as disadvantages/complications) but instead on the "insider" access she has to members of the community/residents of the subdivision (with her being a former SK councilor/kagawad and Barangay secretary but is not currently affiliated with the

incumbent Barangay Council/Sanggunian) that the researcher did not have despite his being a resident of the subdivision.

Research Design

Before the actual data collection, the researcher first went to the homeowners association outpost located in the subdivision to attempt to establish linkage, but the researcher was informed that the association's office is physically located within the Barangay Hall premises (i.e. the officers go to work there). With this in mind, to eliminate partiality and potentially vested interests during the series of transect walks, the researcher opted to identify instead a resident highly familiar with the subdivision but is not affiliated with any organization related to the Barangay Council or the homeowners association. But that being said, the researcher nonetheless still prepared a letter addressed to the president of the homeowners association to ask for permission to do the transect walk with the identified companion/guide.

Afterwards, the researcher negotiated a schedule with his identified companion/guide. Based on her availability, the transect walk was conducted over the course of 2 hours, 21 minutes, and 49 seconds, covering all the streets/drives in the subdivision.

The participants that were made part of the study were recruited based on the criteria that **1.)** they are willing to talk about their complaints/grievances on camera and communicate them directly looking at it (to adhere to the "direct-address" style

as postulated early on in the paper), and that 2.) they are those encountered readily on the streets/drives, provided that they live in said streets/drives. These criteria (bar the “direct-address” aspect) are nearly identical with those established in the study conducted by Lorenzo and Motau (2014) on a transect walk as a means to establish opportunities and challenges for youth with disabilities in Winterveldt, South Africa. The second one, to add, also relate to the point made in the article written by Stefanie Keller (2019) published in the Sustainable Sanitation and Water Management website, which states that transect walks involve the informal interviewing of people met during the walks to get their views.

The default question to be asked to the residents is: *“As subdivision resident living in _____ Drive/Circle, what community problems/issues do you have that you want barangay decision-makers to address/solve?”*

The researcher only used the video-recording capabilities of a mobile phone to record the direct-address videos, with a landscape orientation for the clips in the event that the background is significant to the complaint/grievance being communicated by the resident. A mobile phone was decided upon, as it is, according to MacEntee, Burkholder, and Schwab-Cartas (2016), it is virtually everywhere, and is a “new way forward” for participatory visual research. Also, because its adoption and integration into the fabric of rural-communal life is easy, if not completely seamless.

The identified subdivision is comprised of ten streets/drives. Originally, in order to successfully “transect” all of them, the walks were divided into three (3)

batches, with each covering three drives that are adjacent or in close proximity to one another (refer to the Live Earth map of the subdivision below). But because of time constraints and the companion/guide's availability, the walk was conducted over the course of nearly three hours.

Figure 9.

Live Earth Map of the Subdivision.

As mentioned earlier, because of the companion/guide's availability as well as her willingness to do the transect walk within just one afternoon instead of breaking it up into several days, as mentioned, it was conducted and concluded within 2 hours, 21 minutes, and 49 seconds.

The total number of residents who willingly participated during the transect walks and appeared in the direct-address videos total to 19. In a proposition made by Mira Crouch and Heather McKenzie (2006), less than 20 participants is important in order for the researcher to reinforce the openness in the exchange of information. This is also said to lessen bias threats to validity. Additionally, from the same proposition, it has been said that the issue pertaining to sample size given a qualitative framework has little to no bearing or consequence to the study's basic logic.

After the transect walk, the researcher then collaborated with a multimedia artist to develop a digital map (based on the Live Earth Map image/map of the subdivision) containing the geospatial direct-address videos of the residents who willingly participated in the study (that is, to verbalize community problems/issues in front of the camera). Said video interviews were inputted in the digital map of the subdivision as links that one can click on in order to access them. The map also clustered, per drive, the complaints/grievances identified during the transect walks by the participants, in hopes of geographically/spatially locating them on it as well as identifying trends (if any). Transect maps/transect diagrams are traditionally drawn manually (according to Catalytic Communities, using large sheets of construction papers and markers), but because this study has a video component and given the current technological age and how different the original purpose of transect maps are, the researcher opted to produce the map digitally (with clickable links), again in collaboration with a multimedia artist.

The next step was the analysis of some of the residents' video-recorded insights in terms of VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power as well as Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes. It is worthy of note that only some of the insights were analyzed because not all of them elaborated further on the community problems/issues that they have communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos.

Afterwards, the developed digital map with the geospatial direct-address videos of the residents were then shown to seven (7) barangay decision-makers (one representative from each one of the Barangay Council's seven (7) departments, namely: Administration, Lupon, Barangay Health Workers (BHW), Barangay Peace and Security Officers (BPSOs), Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), Culture, Arts and Tourism (CAT), and Environment). This was then followed by a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) conducted with them about their perception on the research output as an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making. Due to scheduling issues, a representative from the Culture, Arts, and Tourism (CAT) was not able to attend the discussion, so in his/her stead, another BHW participated.

The decision-makers' opinions/insights were then thematically analyzed (deductively) by the researcher based on VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power (Power over, Power with, Power to, Power within) and the participatory outcomes as established by Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009). Thematic analysis is conducted on qualitative data (i.e. those that relate to opinions, feelings, thoughts; in

this study's case, perception-based insights from the FGD) in an attempt to identify broader themes or patterns or trends in the data set (Crosley, 2021).

More specifically, deductive thematic analysis, according to the website Dovetail, is done with a set of expected themes in mind (i.e. informed by prior knowledge and existing research or study) (Damyanov, 2023). In this study's case, the themes are, as mentioned, the distinctions about power (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002) and Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes.

Additionally, an inductive thematic analysis was also conducted, specifically with the aim of identifying themes in the barangay decision-makers' insights pertaining to the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making.

The Barangay

The Barangay is located at the southeastern part of a city in Laguna. One of the 18 barangays in said city, its name was derived from the fact that it is situated at the outskirts. According to the tax mapping conducted by the City Assessor's Office, the barangay has a total land area of 93.735 hectares, 80% of which is residential, 10% agricultural, and the remaining 10% commercial. It has a total population of 19,841, 9,742 of which are men and 9,739 women, respectively. Number of families are 9,500, registered voters 9,072 (with 42 voting precincts). Furthermore, it is comprised of 13 subdivisions.

For this study, a specific subdivision was selected, based in part on the concept of the “anthropology of the hometown”, seeing as the researcher lived at said subdivision for most of his life and is genuinely curious about the issues currently present in it. Raymond Madden (2010), in his paper on “Home-town Anthropology” is quoted in the first person: “As I undertake fieldwork in my home-town area, I experience the familiar and the unfamiliar colliding, overlapping and interrelating in a critically productive, yet tense, dialectic.”

This also relates to what Puttkamer (2019) wrote of transect walks in a separate article, that they, as a participatory method, can be a very interesting tool to get to know one’s own neighborhood. The researcher, in this study, also took on the role of a catalyst/dialogic facilitator (Freire, 1974), who is in a unique position in that he is both a member of the community itself (as a resident of the subdivision himself) and an outsider ‘looking in’ (a resident who is not necessarily attuned to the values and assumptions and mechanisms of intercommunication in the identified discourse community, which is the subdivision in question) (Borg, 2003).

Research Instruments

Apart from the actual digital map with the geospatial direct-address videos shown to the barangay decision-makers, a set of questions was also formulated for the FGD that was conducted with them afterwards; that is, pertaining to their perception on the produced output.

The aforementioned questions are as follows:

1. What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?
2. What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?
3. What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?
4. What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?
5. How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing community problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Originally, a video release form was also prepared by the researcher to be signed by the residents who “participated” in the study; more specifically, those who willingly allowed themselves to be captured on video verbalizing an array of community problems/issues while looking directly at the camera (i.e. “direct-address” style). But because the residents responded better to the casual and more conversational approach as utilized by the researcher and his companion/guide (in large part due to the latter’s rapport with them), the otherwise very formal video

release form that they will be required to sign was waived/not used anymore, with reflexivity in research as basis. Instead, the researcher, by way of the companion/guide, opted to settle with their verbal agreement that, indeed, their videos can be used for the study, specifically to be embedded in the digital map and, to move a step further, also be shown to the barangay decision-makers.

To reference Steve Mann (2016), “reflexivity” in research can be described as being “focused on the self and ongoing intersubjectivities” and that which “recognizes mutual shaping, reciprocity and bi-directionality, and that interaction is context-dependent and context renewing”.

Furthermore, in a paper by Mariam Attia and Julian Edge (2017), they mentioned a doctoral research on the exploration of teacher cognition as it relates to technology in teaching Arabic language to non-Arabic speakers/speakers of other languages. Because the researchers shared a “history of lived experiences” with their colleagues, which is embodied in the term “ishra” (meaning “a kind of expected solidarity and mutual assistance stemming from belonging to a “asheera”, that is, a tribal community, clan, or kinsfolk” (Badawi & Hinds, 1986; Samy, 2010), they were able to gain access to them for a series of interviews, even resulting in the teachers embracing and being fully supportive of the research.

This “embracing”, in turn, evokes the concept of “asham”, a staple in Egyptian culture that points to an “expectation or hope – founded on an existing relationship – that one will receive a desired response”. Because of these considerations, the researchers decided to not anymore distribute the informed consent protocols, as, in

their estimation, “asking the teachers to sign such forms would have risked the inference that the trust upon which our relationship was built was being brought into question” (Attia & Edge, 2017).

Additionally, a coding sheet was developed for the thematic analysis of the decision-makers’ perception (based on their answers to the aforementioned FGD questions) on the output as an alternative participatory governance device based on VeneKlasen and Miller’s (2002) distinctions about power (Power over, Power with, Power to, Power within) and the participatory outcomes as established by Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009). To further elaborate, the “perception” here in question points to whether or not the barangay decision-makers’ answers to the questions display or show insights that align with the participatory outcomes, and also whether they align with the conventional “Power over” distinction or with the alternative (and significantly more participatory) ones: the “Power with”, “Power to”, and “Power within”.

In said coding sheet, it can be noted that there is a row under “Participatory Outcomes” for “NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S”. This is for the themes in the answers that do not fall under any of the participatory outcomes. But nonetheless, the insights that fell under N/A were discussed in the paper.

“Power over” as distinction about power is also part of the coding sheet despite its being generally-recognized as negative (it is defined as the the taking of someone else’s power and then using it to dominate others). This is for themes in

the answers that reject the three other alternative distinctions about power (Power with, Power to, Power within).

The analysis of the insights from the barangay decision-makers were divided per question. Specifically, the seven (7) FGD participants's individual answers to each question were isolated, and then analyzed per sentence, again, in terms of the distinctions about power and the participatory outcomes. As for the insights from some of the residents who took part in the capturing of the geospatial direct-address videos, analysis was also done, though, to reiterate, not all of the things that the residents shared on video were analyzed, since only a handful elaborated further on the community problems/issues that they mentioned. So as implication, no tables were anymore drawn up for the analysis, with the research instead settling with a continuous, prose-style approach.

For purposes of analysis, the researcher formulated operational definitions for each of the distinctions about power as based on those developed for the study conducted by Helen Schneider, Fidele Mukinda, Hanani Tabana, and Asha George (2022) on the expressions of actor power in the implementation of a health service intervention in South Africa. As for the participatory outcomes, they were patterned after Tufte and Mefalopulos' definitions:

Participatory Outcomes (Operational Definitions)

Increased Feelings of Ownership - If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks about a heightened commitment to do something about the community

problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos.

Improvement of Competencies and Capacities - If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Actual Influence on Institutions - If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her realization that he/she can actually have an effect on his/her community after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Distinctions About Power (Operational Definitions)

Power Over – If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her being in a position to exert control or express formal hierarchical authority over his/her constituents/neighbors/fellow residents, or control or constrain what they are able to do (Participatory Methods, n.d.); that is, after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power To – If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her realization that he/she can grow in the process of taking action by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities in addressing the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power With – If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her being able to work alongside/collaborate with their constituents/neighbors/fellow residents in addressing the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Power Within - If the barangay decision-maker/residents speaks of his/her increased sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem regarding the addressing of the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos

Figure 10.

Thematic Analysis Coding Sheet.

Question:			
Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker):			
Participatory Outcomes Tuftte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As outlined in the previous chapter, firstly, the researcher went to the OHA outpost to inquire about the walk that he was to conduct. Specifically, he asked about whether an OHA representative can accompany him in doing the transect walk. The representative that the researcher talked to was hesitant about being the one to serve as companion/guide himself, so he instead told the researcher to prepare a letter of request, address it to the OHA President, and then submit to the OHA's office located inside the Barangay Hall. That way, according to him, the OHA President herself will be the one to assign a companion/guide for the researcher's walk. But because the OHA operates directly under the auspices of the incumbent Barangay Council, the researcher made a judgment call to not anymore push through with asking the OHA for a companion/guide, as this may limit the kinds of complaints/grievances that the research will be able to collate because of potential partisanship issues.

It has also been mentioned in the previous chapter that, originally, an altogether different companion/guide was to be tapped for the walk. But because he did not respond, the researcher instead reached out to his aunt, who also satisfies the basic qualifications established beforehand: that he/she is a resident of the subdivision all his/her life; also, that he/she is not affiliated with the incumbent Barangay Council or any systems of leadership within the subdivision, but who is nonetheless knowledgeable about the community. The "knowledgeable" part in the case of the chosen companion/guide for the transect walk is rooted in her being a

former SK Councilor/Kagawad and Barangay Secretary six (6) years ago, which is two terms removed from the incumbent Brangay Council. This also allowed the researcher access to subdivision residents that he previously did not have; residents who eventually became participants in the study.

In the companion/guide's capacity as a recognizable member of the community (despite her not being part of the Barangay Council) due to her being a resident in the subdivision her entire life as well as her stint as a barangay decision-maker in the past, the tapping of the residents to participate in the study became much easier. This relates to what Borg (2003) wrote of a discourse community, which is a group of people who share discursive commonalities as well as basic values and assumptions, plus ways of communicating about certain goals. It was also noted that a discourse community has a mechanism of intercommunication among its members. By extension, because the companion/guide shared a "history of lived experiences" with the residents, which was termed in the study by Attia & Edge (2017) as "a kind of expected solidarity and mutual assistance stemming from belonging to a "asheera", or a community, clan, or kinsfolk", access to them became more authentic, resulting, on their part, in a heightened willingness to participate.

To continue, a letter of permission to do the transect walk in the subdivision with my chosen companion/guide was prepared by the researcher addressed to the OHA president, Mrs. Francisca Concepcion, which she received and signed at a later date (February 22, 2024).

Afterwards, the researcher and his companion/guide scheduled the date of when they will be conducting the transect walk. The agreed-upon schedule was February 06, at 2:00 pm. As for the map of the subdivision, the researcher examined it by way of Google Maps as well as the Live Earth Map application, while, in the process, identifying and re-familiarizing himself with the names of the streets/drives, plus some key landmarks. The researcher made use of both because some details are in the former that are not necessarily in the latter (or vice-versa). The researcher also downloaded an app called “MapMyWalk”, so that the transect walk can be mapped out in real-time while it was being conducted. Recorded also was the total duration of said walk (2:21:49), plus the overall distance traveled on foot (3.03 km).

For the start of the transect walk, the researcher met with his companion/guide in a convenience store located at the entrance of the subdivision. Both talked briefly about what to do as well as the question to be asked to the residents, and then immediately afterwards, they commenced with the walk. The residents who eventually took part in the study/agreed to appear on the direct-address videos were determined by the companion/guide herself. This relates to what Keller (2019) said that that transect walks involve the informal interviewing of people met during the walks to get their views. From this point forward, the paper will be discussing the community problems/issues that the residents have identified and talked about in the geospatial direct-address videos.

THE RESIDENTS AND THEIR PROBLEMS/ISSUES

SUBDIVISION ENTRANCE

Figure 11.

Resident at Entrance of the Subdivision.

Near the subdivision's entrance, where vendors normally set up shop but, for several years now, are repeatedly asked to relocate by the incumbent Barangay Council, the first resident to whom the researcher talked, and who agreed to take part in the study (i.e. agreed to be captured on video), was a stall owner who spoke of the following community problems/issues:

- **Pagbabawal magtinda**
- **Laging traffic**
- **Mga asong pagala-gala**

This was what the resident said verbatim:

“Bawal ho kasi dito magtinda. Tsaka, ano, yung laging trapik. Saka, ano, wala na akong maisip na ano dito eh. Bawal pati dapat mga asong pagala-gala.”

FIRST STREET/DRIVE

Figure 12.

Resident (First Street/Drive).

From the entrance of the subdivision, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked to their right to enter the first street/drive, where the latter was able to secure the permission of one of its residents near the outskirts to be captured on video as she communicated only one community problem/issue. Said community problem/issue was:

- **Bhirang dumadaan ang truck ng basura**

The resident's articulation of her identified community problem/issue, as transcribed:

“Sa akin, ang gusto ko lang sana maging ano, yung pumapasok dito yung basura. Kasi mahirap magtapon...mag-abang ng basura diyan sa labas. Hindi katulad kapag napasok dito, regular kaming makakapagtapon ng basura. At saka...okay naman na yung ano dito...yun na lang yung ano ko...concern ko yung sa basura.”

SECOND STREET/DRIVE

Figure 13.

Resident 1 (Second Street/Drive).

From the first street/drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then took a left turn towards the second one, where they were able to talk to two residents who

likewise agreed to appear in separate direct-address videos to detail their complaints/grievances. The first resident was, at first, hesitant to share about community problems/issues on video, but, ultimately, she relented. The community problem/issue she identified was:

- **Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo**

This was what the resident said (in her own words):

“Hi, camera, kamusta ka? Hindi, ano lang, yung mga nag-iinuman sa labas. After mag-inuman nagkakagulo, halos magpatayan. Ayun lang yung gusto naming masolusyonan dito.”

Figure 14.

Resident 2 (Second Street/Drive).

On the other hand, the second resident on the second street/drive also had a community problem/issue to share, which he talked about in two separate direct-address videos (the first one is the resident talking about the community problem/issue; the second one is him showing to the camera the scenery which relates to the aforementioned community problem/issue in question). It is worth noting that the house in which the resident lives is just right across a private school. Below is said problem/issue:

- **Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharang sa kalye)**

In the resident's own words:

“Nagkaka...lalo kapag labasan ng Colegio (a school located right across the resident's house), nagsabay ang elementary, yung pagpaparada, andami diyan. Dapat may mga garahe naman sila dapat igarahe nila doon. Dapat yung mga jeep diyan, may mga may-ari naman ‘yan eh. Bakit iginagarahe sa harap ng hindi naman kanya. Diyan, sa apartment, dalawa-dalawa ang nakaparada diyan na jeep.”

Figure 15.

Resident 2 (Second Street/Drive - Showing the Community Problem/Issue He Identified).

This was what the resident said in the second video clip:

“Halimbawa emergency, sunog. Hindi makakadaan ang bumbero. ‘Di ba? Hindi naman tabing-tabi (talking about the parking).”

THIRD STREET/DRIVE

Figure 16.

Resident (Third Street/Drive).

And then from the second street/drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked past the homeowners association outpost and straight to the third one. Specifically, the companion/guide took the researcher to a compound, where they got to engage a resident in a conversation about the nature of the study, and then eventually, about community problems/issues. She agreed to be captured on camera while sharing her insights, resulting in five separate direct-address videos, through which she talked about the following:

- **Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada**
- **Late na pagdating ng ni-request na wheelchair (para sa PWD)**

The resident said the following verbatim (in five separate clips):

“Eh kasi po ang problema namin dito yung kalsada namin, kapag naulan, baha. Kaya kawawa po yung mga napasok pati yung mga senior, hindi makalabas. Kasi po, kagaya niyang asawa ko, ano ‘yan eh, nai-stroke.

‘Yang lubak-lubak pong ‘yan, ano siya, nanginginig ang katawan. Kaya ayan ang malaking problema namin dito. Matubig.’

“Kasi po ‘yan ay naireklamo na namin sa Kapitan, sabi gagawin daw, gagawin, hindi naman po nagagawa. Kaya hindi po namin alam kung kanino kami lalapit. Kasi para magawa yung aming kalsada, ang hiling lang naman naming ito hanggang doon eh. Hanggang doon kay (name redacted). Kahit sino po dito na nakita nila na parang hinalo ng pison. Kasi tinambakan ng putik nung kapitbahay ko, hindi naman po naayos. Kaya sobra po ang putik. Kaya hindi po makakalabas. Yun po ang aming problema.”

“(Yung asawa ko po), nai-stroke. Ngayon po, nag-apply ako ng wheelchair, sabi nila...antagal na, October pa po yun, nag-apply po ako diyan sa (name of a politician’s program). Ngayon po, sabi niya, kasi marami daw, marami. Eh ang sabi ko, “pero antagal na.” Ngayon lumapit naman po kami diyan sa Barangay, ang nakausap namin eh si (name redacted). Ngayon pinapicture-an po yung mister ko, at saka yung manugang ko kasi, nasa ospital din. Kailangan din ng wheelchair. Kaya dalawang wheelchair ang inano ko. Eh ngayon...”

Figure 17.

Resident (Third Street/Drive: Showing the Road – The Subject of One of Her Identified Community Problems/Issues).

“Pasensiya na po kayo, bagong gising eh (while standing in front of the jagged road in question).”

“(Pointing at the road) Ayan po ang aming problema. Kapag baha ‘yan, hindi ako makapunta doon sa anak ko. Nasa dulo yung anak ko eh. Ayan, diyan.”

FOURTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 18.

Resident (Fourth Street/Drive).

Coming from the compound on the third street/drive, the companion/guide then accompanied the researcher to the fourth one, where he was able to talk to a resident who also has her fair share of perceived community problems/issues. Like the previous residents, she also agreed to be captured on camera (resulting in two separate direct-address videos) while articulating the problems, which, namely, are:

- **Rugby Boys**
- **Mga jeep na nakaparada sa kalsada (nakakagawa ng “blindspots” para sa biglang tumatawid na mga bata)**

Word-for-word, here were the community problems/issues that she verbalized:

“...is yung ano, yung mga nagru-rugby boys. Sa may riles. Minsan naanuhan ko minsan, sa riles andaming rugby boys. Magkakasama sila. Kasi one time na dumaan ako doon, anung-ano talaga sila sa rugby. Kinakausap

nila ako nang hindi ko alam kung anong lenggwahe. Ang ginawa ko, hinayaan ko lang sila. Kasi baka mamaya saktan ako eh. Ganoon na lang ang ginawa ko. Yun ang minsang ano ko eh, nadami ang mga rugby boys.”

“Saka yung ano, yung mga jeep na, ano, minsan, naliit na yung kalsada, minsan mga bata, hindi makikita, biglang may sasakyan na dadaan, biglaang magco-cross over naman yung mga bata. Ayon.”

FIFTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 19.

Resident 1 (Fifth Street/Drive).

To continue, from the fourth street/drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked straight towards the adjacent fifth one, at which he

was able to talk to two residents about their perceived community problems/issues. The first one, who the researcher and his companion/guide was able to encounter on the street sitting beside her daughter and grandson, respectively, talked of just one complaint/grievance:

- **Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards)**

Here were the resident's exact words:

“Kapag sila nag-iingay, walang problema, pero kapag kapitbahay ang nag-iingay, sila namomroblema, nagrereklamo. Yun lang naman eh, ang aming ano. Saka, hindi, dito naman sa kalye namin, bigayan naman, hindi naman katulad ng iba na kung anu-ano. Diyan lang naman sa kabila, kila (name redacted), ‘yon, ayaw niya ng maingay. Kila (name redacted). Pero kapag sila nag-iingay, pwede. Yun lang. Dito naman, wala namang problema. Nagkakaisa naman eh kapag sinabing kailangang alisin, inaalis. Kailangang ibalik, ibalik ulit. Bigayan lang, kasi yun lang naman eh. Kasi kung paabutin mo lagi sa Barangay, paano mo aanuhin, lagi na lang Barangay. Pinag-uusapan naman namin. Ganoon lang naman dito eh. Hindi naman katulad ng sa ibang kalye na mag-aaway. Oo, dito...tulad diyan laging may inuman, walang problema. Pero ‘pag sila, namomroblema, ‘pag ang kapitbahay, nag-iinom. Kaya walang ano. Okay lang naman kami dito. Kasi ang hanapbuhay din namin, sa kalsada naggagawa minsan, minsan sa bahay ng nagpapagawa. Kaya walang problema. Kasi, oo, sisilipin din naman, kaya

bigayan lang talaga. 'Pag maingay, bahala kayo, basta hindi kayo nakakaperwisyo sa amin, hindi naman kayo nanghihingi eh, 'no?'

Figure 20.

Resident 1 (Fifth Street/Drive).

Afterwards, another resident who was on his bike in front of his house also agreed to talk about a community problem/issue. The researcher asked the resident to further expound on it, which resulted in the recording of two direct-address videos (the first one was the resident merely mentioning community problem/issue, while the second one is him talking about it in more detail). Said community problem/issues were:

- **Baradong Bang-Bang**

Talking about the aforementioned community problem/issue, the resident said (again, in two separate direct-address videos):

“Yung bang-bang. Yun ang ano dito. So kailangan, yun ang maresolbahan ng Barangay.”

“Minsan kasi hindi tuluy-tuloy yung kanyang daloy eh. So baka mamaya, may nakaharang doon sa dinadaan kaya hindi minsan nagtutuluy-tuloy yung...so matagal siyang dumaloy kapag napuno yung...yun lang.”

SIXTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 21.

Resident 1 (Sixth Street/Drive).

After walking through previous one, the researcher and his companion/guide then reached the sixth street/drive, where they were able to secure the participation of numerous residents (the most number of participants of all the streets/drives), totaling to five (5). The first resident who agreed to participate in the study and be

captured on camera in a direct-address video identified the following community problems/issues:

- **Malubak na kalsada**
- **Mga nakatambak na basura**
- **Mga kabataang magugulo**

From this exact statement were the aforementioned community problems/issues deduced:

“Kalsada. Mga tambak ditong mga basura. Tapos yung mga kabataan.”

Figure 22.

Resident 2 (Sixth Street/Drive).

Crossing over to the other side of the street (from where the previous resident lives), the researcher and his companion/guide then was able to talk to yet another resident, who agreed just the same to be a participant in the study. It is important to mention that the resident here in question once ran for a post in the Barangay Council, but lost (hence his detailed elaboration on, and seeming stake in, the community problems/issues that he has identified). The community problems/issues that he has identified all of which are the following:

- **Mga kabataan (mga basag na bote sa kalsada)**
- **Mga kabataan (maiingay na motor)**
- **Mga kabataan (nagkalat sa labas kahit dis-oras nang gabi)**
- **Kalsada (dapat i-aspalto)**
- **Basura sa kanto**
- **Bang-bang (tinatapunan ng basura)**
- **Illegal parking**
- **Kalsadang ginawa nang talyer**
- **Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod**

In a comprehensive statement communicated to the camera, the resident said (verbatim):

“Una, yung kabataan na mga nagmo-motor diyan, na ang motor ay sobrang ingay. Bukod diyan, ang pwedeng solusyonan ng ating Barangay, itong kalsada, na kung maaari...sabagay, ito yata parang aanuhan na ito eh, aaspaltuhin eh. Tapos yung basura nga natin diyan sa kanto, ginagawang

basurahan. Tapos kahit naman dito, bang-bang ditto, tinatapunan din ng mga ating...mismong may-ari ng bahay. Kaya kung maaari sana, dapat 'yan ang masolusyonan. Tapos 'yang mga kabataan na dis-oras na nang gabi, nasa kalsada pa. Mga nakahubad pa. Tapos 'yang mga...minsan makikita mo iisprayan...yung inyo nga inisprayan yung inyong ano diyan eh. Buti sa akin siguro may takot sila, kapag nahuli ko sila eh. 'Yan, saka 'yang...ewan ko lang, ha? 'Yang mga naka-parking na illegal parking natin dito, 'yan ang...imbes na...dapat masolusyonan kasi tulad halimbawa ng illegal parking dito na mga jeep. Dapat 'yan ay anuhan, pakialaman ng Barangay. Kasi, una, 'yang kalsada natin, kapag dis-oras nang gabi, eh siyempre may labas-masok na sasakyan, eh wala nang madaanan. Etong likod na 'yan (points at Hera Drive), ginawang talyer na, ewan ko lang kung bakit hindi nila masolusyonan 'yan. Kakampi ba o kalaban? Kasi yun ang iniisip ko rito, bigyan tayo ng magandang kalinisan. Tapos gusto ko sana, may nagro-roving na Barangay Tanod ditto sa gabi. Kahit sabihin mong may ilaw na, kailangan pa rin natin ng Barangay Tanod dito. Yun ang "the best" dito sa atin. Yung nagro-roving. Proteksiyon sa residential. Kasi hindi mo alam ang tao dito eh, labas-masok sa kalsadang 'to eh. Lusutan 'to hanggang malayo eh. Yun lang. Saka, kung maaari, 'yang...talagang malinis 'tong ating daanan. Wala 'yang mga dumi-dumi diyan. Kasi, ito, city na 'to eh. 'Di ba? Dapat dito malinis. Ayun lang ang aking masu-suggest sa inyo."

Figure 23.

Resident 3 (Sixth Street/Drive).

From the previous resident's house, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked several steps and stopped at a small Korean grocery store, where the employee/resident accommodated our questions. He eventually agreed to participate, with him citing the following community problems/issues:

- **Hindi maayos na parking ng mga jeep**
- **Mga basurang nagkalat**
- **Mga asong pagala-gala**

The resident said these exact words:

“Ah, yun po, yung...napapansin ko dito yung mga naka-parking na ‘yan, mga ‘yang...sa kalsadang ‘yan. Wala silang mag-parking, ‘yang mga jeep. At saka yung mga basurang nagkakalat. Yun po. Mga pagala-galang

aso na ‘yan na, ano, dapat hindi...sinasabog kasi yung mga basura natin. Eh nagagalit yung president ng Homeowners dito sa (name of subdivision). Yun lang po.”

Figure 24.

Resident 4 (Sixth Street/Drive).

After having talked to, and recorded, the previous resident, the researcher and his companion/guide, as decided upon by the latter, walked back from where they came to go to where the tricycle drivers/operators queue; also, so that they can afterwards “transect” the seventh street/drive from there. The researcher and his companion/guide were able to talk to two tricycle driver residents, who agreed to take part in the study and appear in their respective direct-address videos. The first one enumerated the following community problems/issues:

- **Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street**
(nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders)
- **Walang number ang mga bahay (address)**

Preceisely, the resident had these to say:

“Yung ano, yung problemang nakita ko dito eh yung street-street. Dapat meron siyang ano, yung mga nakalagay na pangalan. Kasi andami laging nagtatanong dito, mga rider, padaan-daan dito, nagtatanong kung anong street. Saka yung mga number ng bahay, nakakalito kasi minsan eh. Nakakalito. Eh turo kami nang turo, minsan yung iba, naliligaw na kakaano. Dapat nakalagay diyan yung street-street, dapat may street-street diyan na nakalagay. Tapos mga number sa bahay. ‘Yan, kita talaga, para madaling makita ng mga rider.”

Figure 25.

Resident 5 (Sixth Street/Drive).

The second resident, on the other hand, talked about only one community problem/issue:

- **Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente**

These were what the resident communicated in the direct-address video:

“Magandang hapon po para dito po sa (name of barangay), ‘no? Concern ko lang po, yung mga puno na malapit po sa kuryente, humahaba na ho nang husto. Baka pwede po nating gawan ng paraan. Para po sa ikabubuti ng ating kapaligiran. Para din sa ating mga sakuna na pwedeng mangyari, kagaya ng pagkasunog, pagkabagsak sa mga taong naglalakad. Yun lang po. Maraming salamat po.”

SEVENTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 26.

Resident 1 (Seventh Street/Drive).

From the queuing area of the tricycle drivers/operators, the researcher and his companion/guide then crossed over the other side of the road, in the process ending the previous segment of the walk and beginning that on the seventh street/drive. There, two residents identified by the researcher's companion/guide, both of whom agreed to be captured on camera to communicate their community problems/issues. The first resident owns a coffee stall, so before he was recorded on video, the researcher first bought coffee from him, with this juncture also serving as the unofficial break in preparation for the second half of the transect walk. Specifically, the resident identified the following community problems/issues:

- **Lubak-lubak na kalsada**
- **Baradong Bang-Bang**

- **Malalagong puno na malapit sa kuryente**
- **Mga asong pagala-gala**
- **Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan**
- **Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada**

The resident was significantly thorough in his enumeration of, and elaboration on, his identified community problems/issues. Here was what he said:

“Yung mga problems na nakikita ko dito sa street namin, first is yung road. Yung matagal nang problema dito sa street namin dito sa (inaudible), dito sa may kanto namin, kasi nagcau-cause siya ng accident. Actually, weekly may nangyayaring accident. Then second yung mga bang-bang. Barado na siya. Tapos parang nalilinis pero barado pa rin siya. Hindi nagru-run yung water. Then third, 'yon, yung mga puno na dapat putulin na, medyo nagiging sagabal na sa kuryente. Tapos fourth, yung mga asong pagala-gala, na nagcau-cause din ng...actually nagiging effect siya sa business ko, kasi marami nang hindi dumadaan dito dahil sa aso na nangangagat talaga siya tapos nanghahabol. Then yung iba naman, ingay lang, yung mga taong dayo, kasi yung katapat na tindahan namin is 24 hours siyang open, so hindi naman siya problema sa amin, ang nagiging problema lang is yung ingay nung mga customer. Tapos 'yon, yung sa ilaw din dito sa street namin. Parang ang alam ko naglagay dito sa street namin, pero hindi na siya working, parang for months...months lang siya nag-run, tapos ngayon hindi na siya working. Then nasolusyonan naman din agad, eto, dito sa kanto, meron na. Pero yung dito

sa pinakaloob, wala. Yun lang naman yung mga problems dito sa street namin.”

Figure 27.

Resident 2 (Seventh Street/Drive).

To continue, from the previous resident's house, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked further into the eighth street/drive, with the latter eventually talking to yet another resident, who likewise agreed to appear in the direct-address while talking about an array of community problems/issues. They are as follows:

- **Mga basurang nagkalat**
- **Mga asong pagala-gala**
- **Dumi ng mga aso**
- **Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente**

Reproduced here is the resident's entire direct-address statement:

“Magandang hapon po, ako po ay si Dexter Paglinawan. Ang mga problema lang pong hinaharap lang naman po namin dito is, basically, pagtatapon ng basura ng mga kapitbahay. Hindi proper yung pagtatapon nila, dahil may mga asong gala dito na nakakalkal, nadadala dito. At saka yung mga diaper, mga pinagpalitan ng diaper ng mga bata, ng mga babies nila, hindi naitatapon nang mahusay or nasa lugar. So yun lang po at saka dumi ng aso, actually meron din po dito na ano...and yung mga puno, masyado na pong malago yung dahon. Minsan pa may mga...makikita niyo po, meron nang sumasayad sa cable ng kuryente. So yun lamang po. Maraming salamat.”

EIGHTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 28.

Resident 1 (Eighth Street/Drive).

From seventh street/drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then moved on and continued walking until they both reached the next one, where two (2) residents agreed to take part in the study by appearing in direct-address videos talking about their community problems/issues. The first one, who was on his way out of the street/drive on his motorcycle by the time the companion/guide was able to exchange niceties with him as well as ask him about whether or not he can participate in the study, identified the following community problems/issues:

- **Wala sa oras na paglalabas ng basura ng mga residente (kahit hindi pa araw ng pagdaan ng truck)**
- **Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharang sa kalye)**

The resident's exact recorded statement:

“Ang problema po dito ay yung basura, hindi pa nadaan yung basura, kahit hindi araw ng Lunes or Huwebes, may naglalabas. Yun ang nagiging

problema dito, dito sa Nepo. At isa pa yung parking nila ng sasakyan, nasa labas lamang. Kaya kapag may dumaan, nahihirapan sila. Yun lang. Yun lamang naman dito sa Nepo.”

Figure 29.

Resident 2 (Eighth Street/Drive).

The researcher and his companion/guide then moved further along the street/drive, until they arrive at the very end of it, where they met the second resident, who was also equally willing to participate in the study (again, by being captured on camera directly communicating to it some community problems/issues).

The community problems/issues were:

- **Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura**
- **Baradong bang-bang**

The resident, in her own words, had this to say:

“Dito sa Nepomuceno, ang basura ay bihirang kunin. Tapos yung aming bang-bang, hindi dire-diretso ang tubig. Tigil ang tubig doon sa gitna. Eh nilalamok at puro basura din. Hindi naman nalilinis.”

NINTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 30.

Resident (Ninth Street/Drive).

After being done with Nepomuceno Drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then walked on towards the penultimate drive, where a resident who owns a vegetable stall near its entrance agreed to the latter to participate in the study. In her direct-address video, she talked about the following community problems/issues:

- **Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura**
- **Mga basurang nagkalat**
- **Mga batang pinapabayaang ng mga magulang sa kalye**

Presented here were the resident's words, taken verbatim:

“Basura ang magandang masolusyonan dito sa aming lugar, kasi kadalasan, matagal bago hakutin, inilalabas ng mga residente, pagkatapos ikinakalat lang ng mga aso. Kaya dapat yun talaga ang pinaka-first. Pangalawa, mga batang pinapabayaang din ng mga magulang diyan sa kalye. Siyempre, hindi natin maiiwasan ang disgrasya, minsan, driver na ang umiiwas sa mga bata. Baka pwede ring yun, isa ‘yon sa dapat maresolbahan sa atin.”

TENTH STREET/DRIVE

Figure 31.

Resident (Tenth Street/Drive).

And then lastly, the researcher and the companion/guide, coming from the previous one, then went to the tenth and final street/drive, walking up until its halfway point, finally chancing upon a resident who owns a motorcycle repair shop. Immediately, said resident agreed to take part in the study, with him identifying the following community problems/issues:

- **Tokhang (Mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit)**
- **Mga basurang nagkalat**
- **Mga tsimosang kapitbahay**

The following is the transcript of the resident's direct-address statement about the community problems/issues:

“Ang ano ko lang naman kasi, napapansin ko lang na problema, yung, number one, katulad nung sa Tokhang na ‘yan. Yung Tokhang. Magpapahuli

sila ng tao eh mali-mali ang pangalan, tapos walang kasiguraduhan na ano eh, na ebidensiya. Kahit nagbago na, ipapadampot ulit. Yung mga ganoon ba? Tapos number two ay yung basurahan, basura. Usually, basura ang problema. Tapos yung number three, mga tsismosang kapitbahay ko. Ayun lang.”

THE DIGITAL MAP OF THE SUBDIVISION

The transect walk was conducted based on the subdivision's map generated from Google Maps and the Live Earth Map application, to serve as guide in terms of the specific streets/drives to "transect" as well as establish limitations, since said subdivision overlaps with numerous other ones. Furthermore, to determine the total duration as well as distance reached in said transect walk, the researcher elected to download a mobile phone application called "MapMyWalk". It also traces, in real-time, where the user is on the map (also based on Google Maps), which made for a usable visualization of the transect walk that was conducted, as well as proof.

Figure 32.

Live Earth Map, Google Maps, and MapMyWalk (The Subdivision).

Once the researcher concluded the transect walk, he contacted a multimedia professional for the creation of the digital transect map. Said map was reconstructed digitally based on the subdivision's map as lifted from both Google Maps and Live Earth Map. For the multimedia professional to be able to identify the locations where the residents were captured on video communicating their complaints/grievances, the researcher sent to him screenshots of the subdivision's map (taken from Google Maps), complete with yellow dots to mark them. The researcher then also sent to him the direct-address videos of the residents as uploaded on Google Drive.

Figure 33.

Google Map Image of the Subdivision (With Yellow Marks by Researcher to Guide Multimedia Professional).

When the multimedia professional finished creating an initial draft of the digital map of the subdivision (in PDF form), he sent it to the researcher for checking. In turn, what the researcher did was mark the draft of the map using Adobe Acrobat Reader's commenting feature, specifically as to 1.) which of the dots on the map shall contain the links to the corresponding direct-address videos of the residents and 2.) what their complaints/features were in summarized form. These information were then used as basis by the multimedia professional to locate, contextualize, and make "clickable" on the map the direct-address videos of the residents as sent by the researcher through Google Drive.

In the first version of the finished digital transect map (in PDF form) as sent by the multimedia professional to the researcher, the links to the direct-address videos (which takes the user to a bulleted summary of each resident's identified community problems/issues, plus the link/s to the video clips) scattered throughout are not

working when opened using a smart phone, although it does when using either a personal computer or laptop.

Figure 34.

Draft of the Digital Map of the Subdivision (As PDF).

Figure 35.

Draft of the Digital Map of the Subdivision (As PDF) With Researcher's Comments.

This was perceived by the researcher as a major issue, since he needed to show/present the digital map to the barangay decision-makers using his mobile device. To address the problem, the multimedia professional decided to instead create the digital map using PowerPoint and not anymore by way of Adobe, making its final version a Powerpoint file and not a PDF document, which it was supposed to be originally.

In the finished map, the multimedia professional also included screenshots (from Google Maps, as sent separately by the researcher) of the specific parts of the streets/drives where the geospatial direct-address videos of the residents talking about community problems/issues were shot/recorded. Other features in the map include, as mentioned, the bulleted summary of community problems/issues per resident, plus a play button that, when clicked, leads directly to the geospatial direct-address videos, and a home button that takes the user back to the digital map.

Figure 36.

When Clicked, the Red Dots on the Digital Map Take Users to This (With Screenshot of Location + Summary of the Community Problems/Issues + Link to the Geospatial Direct-Address Video/s).

As for the location on the map of each of the resident's direct-address videos, see below the finished digital transect map, with the red dots serving as the marker/locator for said videos containing the community problems/issues:

Figure 37.

The Finished Digital Map of the Subdivision (As PowerPoint File).

THE LOCATION OF THE GEOSPATIAL DIRECT-ADDRESS VIDEOS

The first resident, who was recorded talking about **how vendors are prohibited from selling in the area**, as well as **traffic congestion** and **stray dogs**, is located near the **entrance of the subdivision**.

Figure 38.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Near Entrance of the Subdivision).

The second one, on the other hand, who complained about the **infrequency of garbage collection by the officially deployed trucks**, was captured on video on the first street/drive.

Figure 39.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (First Street/Drive).

Afterwards, the researcher and the companion/guide walked across from the first street/drive to get to the second one, where the two residents who talked about the **unruly behavior of drunkards** and the **inappropriate parking of vehicles that makes the street near-impassable**, respectively, can be located.

Figure 40.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Second Street/Drive).

And then from the second street/drive, the next resident, who complained in her direct-address video about the **impassably jagged road in their area**, plus the **delay in the wheelchair that she has requested for her PWD husband**, can be located at the next one, the third street/drive.

Figure 41.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Third Street/Drive).

From the third street/drive, the transect walk then moved on to the next one, the fourth street/drive, where the next resident complained on video about the increasing number of **rugby boys**, plus the **illegally-parked jeepneys along the street, which, in the process creates blindspots for children crossing.**

Figure 42.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Fourth Street/Drive).

After the fourth street/drive, the first resident on the next one complained on video about **double standards when it comes to neighborhood noise; she shared that when they are the ones creating noise, the neighbor is quick to chastise them. But when said neighbor is the one causing it, it is fine.**

Figure 43.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Fifth Street/Drive, First Resident).

The second resident on the same street/drive, on the other hand, expressed his dismay about **clogged drainage**.

Figure 44.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Fifth Street/Drive, Second Resident).

Moving on from the fifth street/drive, the researcher and his companion/guide then proceeded to walk towards the next one (the sixth), where they were able to secure the participation of five (5) residents. The first one communicated his frustration regarding **improper garbage disposal** and the **rowdiness of some juvenile delinquents**.

Figure 45.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Sixth Street/Drive, First Resident).

Still at Sparta Drive, the second resident enumerated an array of community problems/issues, namely the **broken shards of glass littering the streets as caused by juvenile delinquents** and their general **loitering at night**, plus the **noise caused by their muffler-free motorcycles**. Also, he mentioned the **jaggedness of the street** (although he rescinded saying it, stating that he already heard of plans to put asphalt on it), the **improper disposal of garbage** around him, the **clogged drainage**, the **inappropriate parking of vehicles**, the **street being turned into a makeshift vehicle repair shop**, and, finally, the **lack of patrolling/roving at night** on the part of the Barangay.

Figure 46.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Sixth Street/Drive, Second Resident).

From the previous resident, the researcher and his companion/guide then moved on to the next one, still on the same street/drive, who, in turn, mentioned of the **inappropriate parking of vehicles**, the **improper disposal of garbage**, and **stray dogs** that he consistently observes around him.

Figure 47.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Sixth Street Drive, Third Resident).

Walking back towards from where they came, the researcher and his companion/guide then approached the tricycle drivers seated at the nearby bench (located near the TODA queue). Two of them willingly participated, with the first one

talking about the **lack of signages to mark each street, as well as the address number for each house in the subdivision**. The second one, on the other hand, mentioned the **lush trees whose leaves tangle and entwine with electrical lines**.

Figure 48.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Sixth Street/Drive, Fourth and Fifth Residents).

Moving on from sixth street/drive, the researcher and the companion/guide then crossed over to the other side, which is the seventh one. The first resident, who owns a coffee stall, spoke on video about the **jaggedness of the street, their clogged drainage, and the trees whose leaves reach into, and tangle, with electric lines**. In addition, he also mentioned the **stray dogs in their immediate vicinity, the rowdy behavior of the customers of the store right across their house, and finally, their street lamp that is not anymore working**.

Figure 49.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Seventh

Street/Drive, First Resident).

The second resident, to continue, who also live on the seventh street/drive, willingly participated and was captured on video communicating his issues, specifically pertaining to his **neighbors' improper disposal of their garbage**, as well as to **stray dogs**, their **manure** and, finally, the **trees whose leaves reach up and hang on to electrical lines**.

Figure 50.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Seventh Street/Drive, Second Resident).

Next up was eighth street/drive, where the researcher and his companion/guide was able to talk to two residents, who, just like the previous ones, willingly participated and allowed themselves be recorded on video while talking about several community problems/issues. The first one talked about how his **neighbors take out their garbage earlier than they should, even when it's not yet the schedule for garbage collection.** Also, the **inappropriate parking of vehicles in their area.**

Figure 51.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Eighth Street/Drive, First Resident).

The second resident, on the other hand, talked about the **irregular schedule of garbage collection,** as well as the **clogged drainage** in their area.

Figure 52.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Eighth Street/Drive, Second Resident).

As for the penultimate street drive, the researcher then exited the eighth street/drive and headed towards the ninth one, where one resident willingly participated in the study. On video, she talked about the **irregular schedule of garbage collection** as well as **improper garbage disposal**. Also, **children who recklessly play on the streets amidst passing vehicles, all of whom are largely unmonitored and unchecked by their parents.**

Figure 53.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Ninth Street/Drive).

And finally, at Proserpina Drive, the researcher and his companion/guide has convinced one resident to participate, with him talking about the **many flaws and faults in the “tokhang” system (e.g. incorrect names on the list, little to no proof or evidence, even the reformed ones are apprehended again), the improper garbage disposal in the area, and the general gossiping of his neighbors.**

Figure 54.

Geospatial Direct-Address Videos of Community Problems/Issues (Tenth Street/Drive).

The tables on the next several pages show the summarized community problems/issues as communicated by the residents in the direct-address videos, located and classified per street/drive (some complaints/grievances that repeat per drive count only as one) and ordered chronologically based on the transect walk that was conducted. Eliminating the redundancies per street/drive, the total number of community problems/issues as communicated by the nineteen (19) residents are **fourty five (45)**. But eliminating the redundancies in the aforementioned community

problems/issues as recorded for the entire subdivision, they total to **twenty five (25)**.

The twenty five (25) unique community problems/issues are as follows:

- Bawal magtinda
- Laging traffic
- Mga asong pagala-gala
- Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura
- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Maling pagpaparada ng sasakyan
- Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada
- Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD)
- Rugby Boys
- Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards)
- Baradong Bang-Bang
- Mga nakatambak na basura
- Mga basag na bote sa kalsada (kabataan)
- Maiingay na motor (kabataan)
- Nagkalat na mga kabataan kahit dis-oras nang gabi
- Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod
- Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders)
- Walang number ang mga bahay (address)
- Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan

- Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada
- Dumi ng mga aso
- Mga batang pinapabayaang ng mga magulang sa kalye
- Tokhang (mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit)
- Mga tsismosang kapitbahay

Table 1.

Summary of Community Problems/Issues Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – First Table.

NEAR ENTRANCE	FIRST STREET/DRIVE	SECOND STREET/DRIVE	THIRD STREET/DRIVE	FOURTH STREET/DRIVE	FIFTH STREET/DRIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bawal magtinda • Laging traffic • Mga asong pagala-gala 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan) • Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharag sa kalye) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada • Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rugby Boys • Mga jeep na nakaparada sa kalsada (nakakagawang “blindspots” para sa biglang tumatawid na mga bata) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards) • Baradong Bang-Bang

Of the twenty five (25) unique community problems/issues, **eight (8)** of them have been communicated repeatedly by multiple residents in the geospatial direct-address videos, with varying number of times per complaint/grievances. Specifically, the frequency of the eight (8) community problems/issues being mentioned by the residents are (in descending order):

- Maling pagpaparada ng sasakyan (**5 times**)

- Baradong Bang-Bang **(4 times)**
- Mga asong pagala-gala **(4 times)**
- Mga nakatambak/nagkalat na basura **(4 times)**
- Ingay **(3 times)**
- Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura **(3 times)**
- Malubak na kalsada **(3 times)**
- Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente **(2 times)**

Table 2.

Summary of Community Problems/Isuses Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – Second Table.

SIXTH STREET/DRIVE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malubak na kalsada • Mga nakatambak na basura • Mga kabataan (mga basag na bote sa kalsada, maiingay na motor, nagkalat sa labas kahit disoras nang gabi) • Kalsada (dapat i-aspalto) • Bang-Bang (tinatapunan ng basura) • Illegal parking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kalsadang ginawa nang talyer • Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod • Mga asong pagala-gala • Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders) • Walang number ang mga bahay (address) • Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente

Table 3.

Summary of Community Problems/Isuses Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – Third Table.

SEVENTH STREET/DRIVE	EIGHTH STREET/DRIVE	NINTH STREET/DRIVE	TENTH STREET/DRIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lubak-lubak na kalsada • Baradong Bang-Bang • Malalagong puno na malapit sa kuryente • Mga asong pagala-gala • Malingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan • Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga asong pagala-gala • Dumi ng mga aso 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wala sa oras na paglalabas ng basura ng mga residente (kahit hindi pa araw ng pagdaan ng truck) • Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharang sa kalye) • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura • Baradong Bang-Bang 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga batang pinapabayaan ng mga magulang sa kalye 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tokhang (Mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit) • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga tsimosang kapitbahay

In a survey conducted by GMA News on their Facebook Page (2018) during the lead-up to the Barangay Elections, entitled “Top 10 Barangay Problems”, the most-frequently mentioned are the following (the survey question: “Ano ang mga problema sa inyong barangay na nais ninyong masolusyonan ng mga mananalo nung sa Eleksiyon 2018?”):

1. **Basura** (55 Answers)
2. **Tambay** (45 Answers)
3. **Droga** (33 Answers)
4. **Nakaparadang Sasakyan** (27 Answers)
5. **Ingay** (21 Answers)
6. **Aso** (19 Answers)
7. **Sirang Kalsada** (14 Answers)
8. **Presensiya ng mga Tanod** (13 Answers)
9. **Kuryente at Ilaw** (12 Answers)
10. **Tubig** (9 Answers)

Using GMA News' Facebook survey as basis, **nineteen (19)** of the twenty five (25) unique community problems/issues fall under all ten of the issues accounted for in the list. Categorized, here were said community problems/issues by the residents that can be tagged in terms of the results of said GMA News survey from 2018:

Figure 55.

The GMA News Survey on Barangay Problems/Issues (2018).

1. **Basura** (55 Answers)

- Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura
- Mga nakatambak na basura

- Mga basag na bote sa kalsada (kabataan)
- Dumi ng mga aso

2. **Tambay** (45 Answers)

- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Nagkalat na mga kabataan kahit dis-oras nang gabi
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan

3. **Droga** (33 Answers)

- Rugby Boys
- Tokhang (mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit)

4. **Nakaparadang Sasakyan** (27 Answers)

- Laging traffic
- Maling pagpaparada ng sasakyan

5. **Ingay** (21 Answers)

- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards)
- Maiingay na motor (kabataan)
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan

6. **Aso** (19 Answers)

- Mga asong pagala-gala
- Dumi ng mga aso

7. **Sirang Kalsada** (14 Answers)

- Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada

8. **Presensiya ng mga Tanod** (13 Answers)

- Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod

9. **Kuryente at Ilaw** (12 Answers)

- Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente
- Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada

10. **Tubig** (9 Answers)

- Baradong Bang-Bang

Ultimately, of the twenty five (25) unique community problems/issues, only six (6) do not fall under any of the top 10 issues as arrived at by GMA News in 2018.

Namely, they are:

- Bawal magtinda
- Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD)
- Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders)
- Walang number ang mga bahay (address)
- Mga batang pinapabayaang mga magulang sa kalye
- Mga tsismosang kapitbahay

The reason for the inclusion of this GMA News survey conducted on Facebook is so that it can be illustrated further that the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device is accurate and replicable in that the findings of said survey, for the most part (barring the six community problems/issues that are unaccounted for in the established categories) were easily and convincingly reproduced here in this study, which are some of the key features of this geospatial direct-address device: that it is **accurate**, **replicable**, and even **scalable** (considering that the almost the exact same results in the otherwise

national-level survey were also generated/yielded by this much smaller study, at least in terms of scope).

Furthermore, because the videos were of the residents communicating, unfiltered, their identified problems/issues in the community, it is **visceral** and **convincing**, because it came right from them verbally, and delivered spontaneously. Also, it is worth noting that the geospatial direct-address videos as device is **actionable** (because the barangay decision-makers can easily understand what the problems/issues are, as well as where they are located by way of the digital map) and **efficient**, because one can be done with the transect walk in just an hour or so (depending on the size of the subdivision or barangay), and **precise**, due to its replicability.

THEMATIC ANALYSIS (SOME OF THE RESIDENTS' INSIGHTS)

For VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power and Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes present in some of the residents' insights as communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos, most of them are, by default, expressions of both **Increased Feelings of Ownership** and **Power Within**, since these manifest clearly in their willingness to communicate their identified community problems/issues on video (and in a direct-address manner at that) and actually doing so/pushing through with it. Emphasis here is placed, in the operational definition of **Increased Feelings of Ownership**, on the "heightened commitment to do something about the problems/issues" part, since their actually

agreeing to communicate them in front of the camera is, in itself, an act of taking ownership over said issues.

Also, **Power Within** in that there is naturally confidence and dignity on their part as subdivision residents in their decision alone to air their identified problems in the form of a direct-address video, knowing that it will eventually reach, and be seen by, select barangay decision-makers.

But that being said, some of the participating residents provided insights that are much more context-specific and in-depth. In other words, they shared more than what was asked of them (that is, to just identify problems/issues in and around the subdivision).

Chronologically, the first one was the resident who lives on the third street/drive, who shared about the uneven and flood-prone road located near their house, as well as wheelchairs (one for her husband, who is a stroke victim, and one for her son-in-law, who was hospitalized at the time) she has requested for that she is yet to receive. In terms of participatory outcomes, her saying that she has already acted upon her identified problems/issues is an expression of **Increased Feelings of Ownership**, since it is clear that she was proactive in dealing with them.

But also, in terms of power, this is **Power Within**, for essentially the same reason; despite the futility of her efforts, she took it upon herself as a dignified member of the community/resident of the subdivision to do something in search for a solution. For the first issue (the road), she said: ***“Kasi po ‘yan ay naireklamo na***

namin sa Kapitan, sabi gagawin daw, gagawin, hindi naman po nagagawa. Kaya hindi po namin alam kung kanino kami lalapit.” As for the second issue (the wheelchairs), she was clear that, just like for the first one, she has already done her part in her capacity as resident; that the ball is now in the local government’s court: **“Ngayon po, nag-apply ako ng wheelchair, sabi nila...antagal na, October pa po yun, nag-apply po ako diyan sa (name of a politician’s program).”** *Ngayon po, sabi niya, kasi marami daw, marami. Eh ang sabi ko, “pero antagal na.”*

Curiously enough, another one of the participatory outcomes that was apparent in the third street/drive resident’s insights was **Actual Influence on Institutions**, but in a manner that runs counter to what it means (i.e. having an actual effect on his/her community). In other words, her claim that the actions she took to address the problems/issues she has identified were met with inaction and much delay on the part of the local government both on the barangay and provincial level. To reiterate, she said: **“...sabi gagawin daw, gagawin, hindi naman po nagagawa. Kaya hindi po namin alam kung kanino kami lalapit.”** Also: **“...antagal na, October pa po yun, nag-apply po ako diyan sa (name of a politician’s program).”** *Ngayon po, sabi niya, kasi marami daw, marami. Eh ang sabi ko, “pero antagal na.”*

In terms of distinctions about power, this is **Power Over** at least in terms of the local government’s lack of response to both of the resident’s problems/issues. This is so specifically because this is the former controlling or constraining what their constituents are able to do, or at least withholding (intentionally or otherwise) public service from them. Unfortunately, citizen and community empowerment (as

embodied in this case by the presence of both **Increased Feelings of Ownership** and **Power Within** in the resident's insights) can only do so much, and would prove to be instrumental only if it is complemented with governance reforms (Asian Development Bank, 2013).

Next up was one of the two residents from the fifth street/drive, who participated in the geospatial direct-address videos. Initially, she was frustrated about a particular neighbor, who is very sensitive about the noise they sometimes create but is noisy himself/herself (which implies double standards). But after expressing her dismay, she then took a step back by saying that collaboration among homeowners is fostered on their street/drive. She also mentioned that they resolve their own problems, adding that problems/issues can already be addressed from their end without escalating it on the level of the Barangay Council. Specifically, she said: "***Saka, hindi, dito naman sa kalye namin, bigayan naman, hindi naman katulad ng iba na kung anu-ano.***" The resident then added: "***Dito naman, wala namang problema. Nagkakaisa naman eh kapag sinabing kailangang alisin, inaalis. Kailangang ibalik, ibalik ulit. Bigayan lang, kasi yun lang naman eh. Kasi kung paabutin mo lagi sa Barangay, paano mo aanuhin, lagi na lang Barangay. Pinag-uusapan naman namin. Ganoon lang naman dito eh. Hindi naman katulad ng sa ibang kalye na mag-aaway.***"

The aforementioned quotes by the fifth street/drive resident are clearly an expression of the **Increased Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, considering that she essentially "owned up" to the problems/issues on their street/drive by saying that they resolve them on their own without reporting them to

the “Barangay”. Also, of **Actual Influence on Institutions**, because the resident’s insights point to her (and her fellow residents/homeowners) having an effect on the immediate community, specifically on their street/drive. Her emphasis on collaboration between fellow residents is an embodiment of “community conversations”, in particular how they engage members in “productive, action-oriented deliberation” (Public Agenda, n.d.), as well as how such bring together minds and personalities around a shared issue, challenge, or concern (Swedeen, Cooney, Moss, and Carter, 2012).

As for the distinctions about power, the fifth street/resident’s key insights touch upon both **Power With** and **Power Within**. **Power With** because, as stated in its operational definition, it refers to the resident’s talking about his/her being able to work alongside/collaborate with neighbors/fellow residents in tackling or addressing the community problems/issues (that is, while participating in the production of the geospatial direct-address videos). On the other hand, it is an expression of **Power Within** because she talked about a sense (though not necessarily increased) of confidence and dignity with which they, as a street/drive, resolve problems/issues on their own. Under the “strategies” pertaining to principal advocacy strategies to counter powerlessness and exclusion as indicated by VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), these insights from the Hera Drive resident relate to the notion of “building active constituencies around common concerns”. This is because those who live on said drive have common concerns, which they may address proactively and collaboratively.

Moving on, insights from a couple of residents from the sixth street/drive were also analyzed and are highlighted for the ideas they have communicated on top of their enumeration of their identified problems/issues. The first one, who, at one point, ran for the position of Barangay Councilor, was rather comprehensive with the insights he has verbalized. But most notable were his quotes that pertain to various participatory outcomes and distinctions about power. Specifically, they were **Increased Feelings of Ownership** and **Actual Influence on Institutions** (though running counter to its definition), and **Power With** and **Power Within**.

One quote from the resident connects to **Increased Feelings of Ownership** (as well as **Power Within** at the same time), which goes: “*Tapos ‘yang mga...minsan makikita mo iisprayan...yung inyo nga inisprayan yung inyong ano diyen eh. **Buti sa akin siguro may takot sila, kapag nahuli ko sila eh.***” This manifests the aforementioned participatory outcome and distinction about power because the resident is clear in his “owning up” to the tackling of one of the problems/issues that he has identified, specifically the juvenile youth and their unruly behavior. The resident even mentioned the researcher’s house, whose wall was spray-painted/vandalized by said youth, who are also assumed to be members of a local gang. It is him “owning up” to it because he knows in himself that the youth would not dare cross him, because he will, for sure, take serious action if ever he catches one of them on the act/red-handed vandalizing his store.

As for the **Actual Influence on Institutions** participatory outcome, the resident’s statement actually runs opposite to it, because it implies powerlessness/lack of influence on his part as homeowner who is not necessarily

affiliated/allied with the incumbent Barangay Council. This was communicated most clearly in one quote wherein he was talking about the issue of illegal parking nearby: “*Kasi, una, ‘yang kalsada natin, kapag dis-oras nang gabi, eh siyempre may labas-masok na sasakyan, eh wala nang madaanan. Etong likod na ‘yan (points at Hera Drive), ginawang talyer na, ewan ko lang kung bakit hindi nila masolusyonan ‘yan. **Kakampi ba o kalaban?**”*

The resident, with this quote, suggests that the possible reason that those who “illegal-park” nearby are yet to be reprimanded/penalized by the Barangay Council is because they were supporters of the incumbent Sanggunian. By implication, this is also **Power Over**, but in the sense that the resident is on the receiving end of formal hierarchical authority, because he is witness to the Council being selective in its implementation of barangay policies/ordinances, in this case on the subject of illegal parking. This, therefore, aligns with the concept of “hidden power” as indicated by VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), or the influence of a select few on what gets to the decision-making table and what gets to the agenda.

And then briefly, one last quote from the sixth street/drive resident relates to **Power Within** as distinction about power, specifically his saying that the subdivision should always be clean because (name of city), for the longest time, is already a city. The quote is: ***Kasi, ito, city na ‘to eh. ‘Di ba? Dapat dito malinis.*** This is **Power Within** because the resident expresses his personal need for his immediate surroundings be clean/dignified at all times because that is what the city, as a whole, deserves.

Another insight from one of the residents on the sixth street/drive was also included in the analysis, for the reason that it connects to at least one of the distinctions about power, specifically **Power Over**. Right after sharing his identified community problems/issues, the Sparta Drive resident then said: “***Eh nagagalit yung president ng Homeowners dito sa (name of subdivision).***” This is **Power Over** not because the resident is in a position to exert formal hierarchical control, but because he mentioned someone, as response to the problems/issue he has identified, who may be angered by them, specifically the president of the homeowners association. Again, invoking VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), this adheres to the concept of visible mechanisms of power being the ones that shape the formal ground rules of society.

And then lastly, the tenth street/drive resident, whose one key insight, like that of the previous one, align with the **Power Over** distinction. This was apparent in his talking about the barangay-level implementation of Tokhang (or the arrest of drug suspects for purposes, at least on paper, of rehabilitation). He said: “***Ang ano ko lang naman kasi, napapansin ko lang na problema, yung, number one, katulad nung sa Tokhang na ‘yan. Yung Tokhang. Magpapahuli sila ng tao eh mali-mali ang pangalan, tapos walang kasiguraduhan na ano eh, na ebidensiya. Kahit nagbago na, ipapadampot ulit. Yung mga ganoon ba?***”

The resident’s criticism of the barangay-level Tokhang indicates **Power Over** not because he has power over the community, or over decision-making on the subdivision-level let alone Barangay, but because he talked about a policy that is, without question, very much hierarchical/top-down to the point of fault, with improper

collection of evidence and building up of cases against alleged drug suspects, even going so far as the Barangay enacting in the repeated arrests of individuals even if they have already supposedly been rehabilitated. In other words, the Barangay, on the subject of Tokhang, at least according to the resident from the tenth street/drive, take action unilaterally, with little to no input or feedback from the residents. This, again, is “hidden power” (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002), because it is an example of the influence of the few on decision-making as well as on what gets on the agenda and what does not.

THEMATIC ANALYSIS (BARANGAY DECISION-MAKERS FGD)

After the transect walk and the development of the digital map of the subdivision, the researcher then prepared a letter (addressed to the Barangay Chairman) to ask for the Barangay Council’s permission for me to be able to conduct a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) within the Barangay Hall premises with one representative from each of the seven (7) departments, specifically the Administration, Lupon, Barangay Health Workers (BHW), Barangay Peace and Security Officers (BPSOs), Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), Culture, Arts and Tourism (CAT), and Environment. Said discussion was conducted on February 27, and began approximately at 2:30 pm and ended at around 3:10 pm. No representative from CAT came and participated in the FGD, so another BHW came to take part in the discussion instead.

The FGD in question was conducted with the geospatial direct-address videos (as embedded in the digital map of the subdivision), specifically as to how it is

perceived by the participants in terms of its being an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making. At this juncture of the paper, the (deductive) thematic analysis of their answers to the researcher's questions is presented in terms of VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power (Power over, Power with, Power to, Power within) and the participatory outcomes as established by Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009): Increased Feelings of Ownership, Improvement of Competencies and Capacities, and Actual Influence on Institutions.

Also, themes surfaced inductively from the barangay decision-makers' insights. Before the FGD began, the researcher first explained and then showed the produced digital transect map with direct-address videos using his personal mobile device.

Figure 56.

The Researcher with the Barangay Decision-Makers (Post-FGD).

.Figure 57.

The Researcher Showing the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (as Embedded in the Digital Map of the Subdivision) to the Barangay Decision-Makers (Pre-FGD).

To reiterate, the questions asked by the researcher to the barangay decision-makers were as follows:

1. What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?
2. What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?
3. What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

4. What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?
5. How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing community problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

As mentioned in the Methodology, the researcher has prepared a coding sheet as well as operationalized the definitions of the distinctions about power and the participatory outcomes, respectively. The barangay decision-makers' insights were analyzed per answer to each question.

Because the discussion was free-flowing, not everyone was able to answer per question, with some of them sharing more insights than the others. Here, again, was the coding sheet used:

Figure 58.

FGD Coding Sheet.

Question:			
Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker):			
Participatory Outcomes Tuftte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

The entire FGD was transcribed by the researcher himself, with the start and end of sentences determined by him as he has seen fit while listening to the recording of the discussion. This is significant to note, since the thematic analysis was done per sentence.

The coding was also done per insight, meaning a coding sheet was used to thematically analyze each of the barangay decision-makers' verbalized insights pertaining to each question. So if, for example, the barangay decision-maker shared his/her insights regarding the question two times, then two separate coding sheets

were used for the analysis, to better isolate his/her insights every time he/she has shared something.

Furthermore, there were instances when more than one participatory outcome and distinctions about power were observed in the barangay decision-makers' answers/insights, which were reflected in the coding sheets as well as in the discussion proper. Themes were also analyzed inductively from the insights, all of which were also identified and discussed in this chapter.

FIRST QUESTION (THEMATIC ANALYSIS)

1. *What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?*

VAWC Participant (Themes)

The first participant in the FGD to have answered the question was the VAWC representative. She shared her insights regarding the question two times. Based on the thematic analysis, most of what she shared did not align with any of Tufte and Mefalopulos' participatory outcomes, though one adhered to **Feelings of Ownership**. As for the distinctions about power (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002), both **Power With** and **Power Over** were observed. Fundamentally, the VAWC participant did not really answer the question directly, instead reacting to community problems/issues that were communicated by the residents by way of the geospatial direct-address videos.

Theme: Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

One of her insights align with both **Feelings of Ownership** and **Power With** at the same time. The quote analyzed thematically was this:

“Tapos yung sa nagrurugby, wala akong alam doon. Pero dapat, kung may reklamo sila, inform lang nila na sa amin, dadamputin naman, bakit naman hindi? Kasi talagang ayaw na ayaw namin talaga ng rugby kapag regarding diyan.”

As established in the operational definitions, an insight may be considered as adhering to **Feelings of Ownership** if the barangay decision-maker speaks about a heightened commitment to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos. In the abovementioned insight, it can be noted that she expressed a sense of urgency in terms of resolving the identified issues (in this case, the “rugby boys”), as embodied by “...*dadamputin naman, bakit naman hindi?*” and “*Kasi talagang ayaw na ayaw namin talaga ng rugby kapag regarding diyan.*”

As for the **Power With** distinction observed, her saying that “...*kung may reklamo sila, inform nila na sa amin...*”, which highlights their willingness to work alongside/collaborate with the residents in addressing the community problems/issues (the operationalized definition of said distinction about power).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

As for her other insights, they do not anymore align with any participatory outcomes, with her expressing traditional perspectives on power with her statements, thus aligning with **Power Over**, which is operationalized as speaking of the participant's being in a position to exert control or express formal hierarchical authority over his/her constituents, or control or constrain what they are able to do (Participatory Methods, n.d.). Specifically, the quotes from her insights that capture definitively this **Power Over** distinction are as follows:

“Okay, ang masasabi ko dito, kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina, although iniimplement naman ng barangay ‘yan.’”

In said quote, it can be gleaned, specifically in the “...*although iniimplement naman ng barangay ‘yan’*” part, that she was insistent that the barangay, regardless of the community problems/issues, is implementing ordinances accordingly, thus exerting control and formal authority over them in the community. Her saying that the people have no discipline (“...*talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina*”) also hints at a punitive authoritarian tone.

“Tapos yung talagang...sa aso, ‘yan naman talaga’y napag-usapan na eh, ibababa na yung ordinansa niyan eh, na bawal na talagang mag-alpas ng aso. May mga multa-multa na ‘yan eh, hindi ko lang alam kailan naiimplement.”

“At doon naman sa mga kabataan na kagaya ng sa hawak ko sa VAWC, mag-iimplement na rin kasi kami ng curfew, inaantay na lang din namin ibaba ‘yan eh. Kumbaga isang tarpaulin kasi yung batas na ilalagay sa bawat lugar para maintindihan nila.”

“At diyan din sa parking, halos pinapatanggal na ‘yan eh, kaya lang matitibay din ang mukha kung bakit pagkatapos ipatanggal, ibabalik na naman. O ‘di ba?’”

Continuing with the **Power Over** insights (with no participatory outcomes observed), as can be gleaned from the two abovementioned quotes, the participant

made mention of the Barangay Council-level implementation already to be carried out when it comes to some of the community problems/issues (stray dogs, curfew violations) as communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos.

Indicative of this were the lines “...*’yan naman talaga’y napag-usapan na eh, ibababa na yung ordinansa niyan eh, na bawal na talagang mag-alpas ng aso. May mga multa-multa na ’yan eh, hindi ko lang alam kailan naiimplement*”, as well as “...*mag-iimplement na rin kasi kami ng curfew, inaantay na lang din namin ibaba ’yan eh. Kumbaga isang tarpaulin kasi yung batas na ilalagay sa bawat lugar para maintindihan nila*”, and “...*diyan din sa parking, halos pinapatanggal na ’yan eh*”.

For the participatory outcomes, none were observed in the analysis, because most, if not all, of the VAWC participant’s insights (as outlined in the quotes above) mostly refer to the more traditionally top-down way of policy implementation, with no “heightened commitment” to tackle the identified community problems/issues in the geospatial direct-address videos after having seen them.

Theme: Residents’ Perceived Lack of Discipline

For this next theme, an earlier quote is referred to again, specifically:

“Okay, ang masasabi ko dito, kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina, although iniimplement naman ng barangay ’yan.”

The emphasis is placed this time around on the residents’ perceived lack of discipline, with the line “...*kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina*” as best representing this. The power distinction here, to reiterate

from early on in the analysis, is **Power Over**, because of the participant’s top-down frustration with the residents, with no desire, at least based on the insight, to help them be more so; that is, in the collaborative/participatory sense. Here, no participatory outcome was observed (or N/A), since the quote is focused far too much on a hierarchical view of barangay policy/ordinance implementation, with no expression pointing to a desire or a notion, from her end, that there ought to be participation on the part of the resident.

“Yon siguro, ang tulong lang doon is yung tao na lang, disiplina lang.”

Curiously, although there were no participatory outcomes observed in the quote above (because it can be interpreted from said insight that a heightened degree of participation between barangay decision-makers and residents was not given emphasis, instead just focusing on the need for residents to be more disciplined), it nonetheless adheres to the **Power With** distinction, specifically when she mentioned that the residents can “help” with barangay implementation by being more disciplined (*“...ang tulong lang doon is yung tao na lang, disiplina lang”*).

Table 4.

VAWC Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 1).

VAWC Participant – Question 1 (Answered Two Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1)

Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline (2)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power With (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

Administration Participant (Theme)

The second participant to have shared her insights was the Administration representative. Again, based on the thematic analysis that was conducted, her overall answer to the question adhere to the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome and the **Power To** distinction about power, respectively. For this question, the Administration participant shared two times.

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

After the VAWC representative answered the question rather indirectly, the Administration participant decided to answer what was actually being asked, which was what she thought/what her feeling were about the produced digital map of the subdivision embedded with the geospatial direct-address videos. Her insights, as mentioned, align with both the **Improvement of Competencies** participatory outcome and the **Power To** distinction about power, with her commending the map, especially in terms of its potential use as barangay-level mobile application for grievance redress.

“Sa akin effective talaga, mas maganda siya, kasi kahit ako, minsan nag-Google Map ako eh.”

“Parang mas okay siya lalo na kung iimplement sa mga barangay.”

The thematic analysis arrived at the aforementioned outcome because, as defined operationally, it pertains to when the barangay decision-maker spoke of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues, which is embodied in the quotes above, specifically *“...effective talaga, mas maganda siya...”* and *“...mas okay siya lalo na kung iimplement sa mga barangay.”*

“Parang mas okay siya kung magiging apps natin siya”.

“Oo, dapat meron, para mas madali, para mas mabilis. Kita agad eh. Sa akin talagang accessible, mas maganda.”

As for the **Power To** distinction about power, it is defined, in the context of this study, as that which can be observed when the barangay decision-maker speaks of his/her realization that he/she can grow in the process of taking action by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities. In one of the quotes above, it is captured in *“Sa akin effective talaga, mas maganda siya, kasi kahit ako, minsan nag-Google Map ako eh”* in that it communicates her familiarity with a digital map as tool but also her intention to use it in a new context, specifically grievance redress on the barangay level, even to the point that she expressed her measured desire to adopt it as community problem identification “app”, as stated in the *“Parang mas okay siya kung magiging apps natin siya”* sentence.

In a nutshell, she has captured this **Power To** expression best by way of the second quote: *“Oo, dapat meron, para mas madali, para mas mabilis. Kita agad eh. Sa akin talagang accessible, mas maganda.”*

Table 5.

Administration Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 1).

Administration Participant – Question 1 (Answered Two Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues (2)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (2)	Power To (2)

Environment Participant (Theme)

Compared to the insights shared by both the VAWC and Administration participants in the FGD, the Environment representative was rather terse with her answer:

“Alam niyo kaagad.”

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

By the above quote, she meant that the geospatial direct-address videos allows a barangay decision-maker like herself to instantly know as to where the community problems/issues are situated/located. This was her agreeing with the Administration participant and her assertion that, indeed, the videos (and the digital map into which they are embedded) can be useful as an alternative participatory governance device (as mentioned in the previous section).

Just like the participatory outcome and distinction about power to which the Administration participant's insights adhered previously, the Environment participant's insight also articulates both the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** outcome and **Power To** distinction, respectively. Both were embodied because, although short, the statement forwarded by the Environment participant was assertive that there is growth in the process of taking action about the community problems/issues by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities. In this case, it is the quick realization that the geospatial direct-address videos indeed allows a barangay decision-maker like herself to immediately know as to the location of the community problems/issues.

Table 6.

Environment Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 1).

Environment Participant – Question 1 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power To (1)

Peace and Security Participant (Themes)

To continue, the Peace and Security participant was the last to share his insights, all of which appropriately run opposite to the findings in both of the Administration and Environment representatives' answers. In particular, here are the most notable quotes from his overall answer to the question:

“Pagdating nang mga bandang 10:00, roving na ‘yan. Taliwas sa sinabi nito na hindi raw nagro-roving. Araw-araw ‘yan.”

“Ang order sa amin ni Kapitan, kada-kanto, kada-phase, kinukunan ng litrato ‘yan. Yung kinukunan ng litrato, para may ebidensiya kami na nagro-roving.”

“Kumbaga, kayo’y may aso, gusto niyo ipahuli, pupunta ka sa barangay, iaano mo. Para mabigyan ng certification na ipahuhuli mo yung aso. Madadala sa City Vet.”

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

Based on his overall answer to the question, the Peace and Security participant was insistent that the Barangay Council is rather proactive with its implementation, specifically in their “patrolling” around the subdivision. This runs counter to one of the residents’ identified community problem/issue in the geospatial direct-address videos, which states that *Tanods* (the local term for security personnel on the barangay-level) do not do their patrolling regularly.

The lines *“Taliwas sa sinabi nito (pertaining to one of the residents in the geospatial direct-address videos) na hindi raw nagro-roving. Araw-araw ‘yan”* and *“Ang order sa amin ni Kapitan, kada-kanto, kada-phase, kinukunan ng litrato ‘yan. Yung kinukunan ng litrato, para may ebidensiya kami na nagro-roving”* best represent this assertion on the part of the Peace and Security participant. This was analyzed as an articulation of **Power Over**, or the decision-maker expressing his being in a position to exert control or express formal hierarchical authority, although more specifically, it is Power Over in the sense that the participant immediately shut down the complaint/grievance and then quickly responding that they are doing their job properly/implementing initiatives accordingly. Meanwhile, no participatory outcome has been observed in the thematic analysis, since the quotes very much awash in a hierarchical view of community problem identification and decision-making without the geospatial direct-address videos as possible alternative participatory governance device in mind. The way the Peace and Security participant sees it, what takes precedence are the visible and definable aspects of political power; that is, the formal rules, structures, and authorities, as well as institutions and procedures of decision-making (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

Still with the Peace and Security participant, another theme identified during the analysis was his answer's adherence to hierarchy in terms of tackling community problems/issues. This is because, while talking about stray dogs, he was quick to speak of the conventional process one goes through whenever he/she wants them to be taken to the city pound. Specifically, what he said was *“...kayo’y may aso, gusto*

niyo ipahuli, pupunta ka sa barangay, iaano mo. Para mabigyan ng certification na ipahuhuli mo yung aso. Madadala sa City Vet.”

This was observed as **Power Over** again because of his articulation of the traditional and formally hierarchical way or method of tackling community problems/issues, in this case the stray dogs. Again, just like in the previous theme, no participatory outcomes were observed, since the quote above highlights a commitment on the part of the Peace and Security participant to “visible power” as elaborated on by VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), or the visible mechanisms of power in a given context (in this case, the barangay or subdivision) that shape the formal ground rules of society. Specifically, he refers to the hierarchical procedure of reporting (potentially rabid) stray dogs: first, one goes to the barangay to get certification, and then to the City Veterinary Office.

Table 7.

Peace and Security Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 1).

Peace and Security Participant – Question 1 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

SECOND QUESTION (THEMATIC ANALYSIS)

2. *What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?*

Administration Participant (Themes)

Moving on to the second question, the Administration participant was first to share. Her answer, as analyzed thematically, fall under the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, as well as **Power Over**, **Power With**, and **Power Within** distinctions, respectively.

Theme: **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**

Several of the Administration participant's insights were analyzed to have been indicative of her stand that it is the community members who are accountable when it comes to problems/issues on the level of the community, not the Barangay Council. Also, that it is through their collaborative effort that these can be resolved. Quotes that represent this are as follows:

“Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya ‘yan eh.”

“Ayun naman ang sa akin. Kasi, yun nga, sabi kong lagi, nung kami’y nag-meeting doon, wala namang ibang mag-aalaga nung aming street kundi kami rin. Kasi kami lang din yung maapektuhan.”

“So yun, yun ang ano namin, since lalo na doon sa aming street, mas marami ang apartment kesa homeowners. Ilan lang kaming homeowners talaga. Parang

lima, anim lang yata kami, pero puro apartment, napakarami. Oo, so ang malimit ko namang kinakausap doon 'pag may mga problema is yung nagpapaupa. Siyempre mga tenant nila 'yan eh, sila may responsibilidad diyan."

"So as of now, kung meron mang kaming problema sa basura, nagagawan naman namin ng solusyon. Yun 'yon, sa amin."

The insights above, analyzed in terms of the distinctions about power, express **Power Over**, **Power With**, and **Power Within**. **Power With** occurred in the analysis because of the Administration participant's adherence to the idea that community members ought to work with each other to resolve problems/issues instead of always bringing them to the attention of the Barangay Council. This is best represented by this line: *"Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya 'yan eh."*

Also, **Power Within** in terms of how she expresses a sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem regarding the tackling of the community problems/issues, but specifically as member of the community itself (even more specifically as subdivision resident) and not as barangay decision-maker. The line that embodies this most ideally: *"Ayun naman ang sa akin. Kasi, yun nga, sabi kong lagi, nung kami'y nag-meeting doon, wala namang ibang mag-aalaga nung aming street kundi kami rin. Kasi kami lang din yung maaapektuhan."* This relates to the participants' effectively becoming "protagonist subjects" capable of enacting on matters and even inciting changes, which, in the process, may foster a strong bond among a community (Argenti and Signa, 2014).

But interestingly, as mentioned earlier, **Power Over** was also observed, specifically when the Administration participant shared about her talking to the

owners of the apartment buildings on her street to sort out the problem with garbage disposal. The way she worded her insight, she seemed to have talked to them in her capacity not just as a community member but as a barangay decision-maker, specifically as Administration personnel in the Barangay Council. The line that captures this perfectly: *“Oo, so ang malimit ko namang kinakausap doon ‘pag may mga problema is yung nagpapaupa. Siyempre mga tenant nila ‘yan eh, sila may responsibilidad diyan.”*

But ultimately, this is also **Power With**, because it is a demonstration of community members working together to tackle the community problems/issues, or, as defined operationally in the paper: *“...of his/her (the barangay decision-maker) being able to work alongside/collaborate with the residents in addressing the community problems/issues.”*

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

Furthermore, **Power Over** was again observed under this theme, because the Administration participant also outlined a more traditional and top-down way of tackling the community problems/issues, in this case the improper disposal of garbage (although she still mentioned the important role of the community). In particular, she explained that, when it comes to said issue, it is the City Environment and Natural Resources Office (CENRO) that is accountable, not the Barangay Council. The line that specifically represents this best is *“Problema hindi naman ng Barangay yun eh, problema ng community at saka ng CENRO. Hindi responsibilidad ng Barangay. Sa akin.”* Specifically, this alludes to the idea that the improvement of

public service delivery is a function made possible by the triangulation of institutions (in this case, the local Sanggunian and the city government working together) within a value-based and principle-oriented framework of governance (PIDS and UNICEF, 2009).

The quote above does not align with any of the participatory outcomes, since the Administration participant explained that some of problems/issues identified are not necessarily the Sanggunian’s problem but of the community as a whole, as well as that of the CENRO. This unwillingness, at least on her part, to be accountable to the problems/issues and instead pointing fingers at someone else imply her lack of desire to collaborate with the community/residents in resolving them.

Table 8.

Administration Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 2).

Administration Participant – Question 2 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power Over (1), Power With (1), Power Within (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

VAWC Participant (Themes)

Continuing on with the second question, the next participant who answered and shared her insights was that from VAWC. Mainly, hers fall under the **Feelings of Ownership** and **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome (although some of her quotes also do not align with any of the outcomes), while for the distinctions about power, it is **Power Over** and **Power With**.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

The VAWC participant's insights that fall under this theme do not align with any of the participatory outcomes, as they are a general expression of her commitment to a top-down, hierarchical meting out of power (**Power Over**), at least in the context of tackling community problems/issues. The lines below are those that capture this best:

“Eh hindi na...ang alam ko dito sa (inaudible) wala na, ‘di ba? Napatanggal na ni Kap ‘yan eh, yung mga kabataan na nandiyan eh.”

“Yung sa puno kasi sa Meralco yun eh. Ire-request mo yun through CENRO.”

The first quote expresses the participant's conviction that, despite the identified community problems/issues in the geospatial direct-address videos, the Barangay Council, specifically the Barangay Chairman, is doing its/his best to resolve them, specifically juvenile delinquency. She was clear with her statement that the Barangay Chairman himself, as an individual, has already resolved the issue (*“Napatanggal na ni Kap ‘yan eh...”*).

As for the second quote, just like the Administration participant previously, she mentioned CENRO once more as being chiefly responsible for the tackling of the identified community problem/issue, in particular the leaves of the trees that entwine with electrical lines at the subdivision (*“Yung sa puno kasi sa Meralco yun eh. Ire-request mo yun through CENRO”*).

Both quotes do not necessarily align with any of the participatory outcomes, since both are expressions of the more traditional, hierarchical take on community problem identification and decision-making. Specifically, the Administration participant referred to notion that the Barangay Chairman (representing in his personhood the Sanggunian) has already unilaterally resolved the identified community problem/issue (pertaining to juvenile delinquents). Also, her insistence that the problem with trees identified by some of the residents in the geospatial direct-address videos should be reported to the CENRO, not to the Barangay Council..

Theme: Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

But despite the participant’s adherence to hierarchy, she also expressed her gratefulness to residents who have brought problems/issues in the subdivision to her attention, stating that their tackling is only possible so long as they are communicated properly to her/them (the barangay decision-makers). This was identified in the thematic analysis as an expression of **Power With**, as it is indicative of her preference that the residents collaborate with them when it comes to tackling,

and deciding on, community problems/issues. Colom (2010) wrote that the empowering capabilities of participatory videos, or, in this matter, the geospatial direct-address videos, lie in the process, because it allows the participants (or the Olympia Park Subdivision residents) to have a degree of influence in a given political space where decisions that affect them are made.

Specifically, these are the quotes that embody it:

“Kaya lang, ang problema, dapat sana may magreklamo. Kapag walang nagreklamo, wala kaming malalaman. Yun lang ‘yon. Yun ang problema. May magreklamo, aaksiyunan agad, bakit hindi? Mas maganda, ‘di ba?”

“Hindi ko alam yung anong yun eh, ngayon ko lang narinig na may ganoon. Kasi actually kapag may mga ganoon kasi na case, pinapaalam agad sa amin. Thank you naman at nalaman naming yung ganoong sistema.”

“Yes. Hangga’t walang nagrereklamo.”

The first quote, aside from its being aligned with the **Power With** distinction about power, captures the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, since it highlights a sense of urgency on the part of the VAWC participant to *own* the problems/issues reported to them (*“May magreklamo, aaksiyunan agad, bakit hindi? Mas maganda, ‘di ba?”*). She also reiterated in the third quote that their actions, collectively, as barangay decision-makers hinge on whether or not the residents communicate to them the problems/issues (*“Yes. Hangga’t walang nagrereklamo.”*), thus reinforcing **Power With**. This is “community conversation” in action. As what was written in a document published by Public Agenda (n.d.): community members give government officials and community leaders the chance to actively engage members of a community in “productive, action-oriented deliberation”.

As for the second quote, the participatory outcome identified in the thematic analysis was **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** (while also **Power With** again in terms of distinctions about power), since it highlights her knowing more and better about her community (specifically, at the subdivision) thanks to the residents who communicated their identified community problems/issues, and allowed themselves to be included, in the geospatial direct-address videos (*“Kasi actually kapag may mga ganoon kasi na case, pinapaalam agad sa amin. Thank you naman at nalaman naming yung ganoong sistema”*). As defined operationally, **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** is the barangay decision-maker *“speaking of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos.”*

Table 9.

VAWC Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 2).

VAWC Participant – Question 2 (Answered Four Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (2)	N/A	Power Over (2)
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (3)	Feelings of Ownership (1), Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power With (3)

THIRD QUESTION (THEMATIC ANALYSIS)

3. *What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?*

Environment Participant (Theme)

For the third question, the Environment participant was first to share her insights, noting that the residents should have communicated the community problems/issues that they have identified directly to her instead of by way of the geospatial direct-address videos. Her insights run in opposition to the idea that ICT (which is what the geospatial direct-address videos represent) has the potential to improve the citizens' asymmetrical access to information, which may also better handle the principal-agent problem (in the context of this study, the relationship between the constituents and the Barangay Council) (Gurbaxani and Whang, 1991).

In the thematic analysis, her answer to the question was classified as **Influence on Institutions** as far as the participatory outcomes are concerned, while also being an expression of **Power With** in terms of distinction about power. These are the quotes from her answer:

“Parang nagulat lang po kasi alam naman nilang dito ako nagtatrabaho dapat po yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin.”

“Yung halimbawa nga po may ganoon, kagaya niyan, mga kilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako.”

Theme: Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers

The aforementioned quotes, as stated, fall under the **Influence on Institutions** participatory outcome and **Power With** distinction about power, respectively. The former was because of the Environment participant's communicating her perspective that the community problems/issues could have been reported directly to her, because she, as barangay decision-maker, can do something to resolve it. This is best represented by *"...kasi alam naman nilang dito ako nagtatrabahao dapat yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin."* Also, by *"...mga kakilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako."*

This is **Influence on Institutions** because, as stated in the operationalized definitions, it points to when the barangay decision-maker speaks of his/her having an actual effect on his/her community and its residents, in this case in terms of tackling and deciding on the community problems/issues, stating that she can do something about them in her capacity as barangay decision-maker (*"...dapat yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin."*).

As for the **Power With** distinction, it is due to both quotes being about how the Environment participant prefers that the residents come to her directly (*"...mga kilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako."*), and to the barangay decision-makers individually, if they are to report community problems/issues (and not to some alternative governance devices like the geospatial direct-address videos).

Table 10.

*Environment Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power
(Thematic Analysis – Question 3).*

Environment Participant – Question 3 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers (1)	Influence on Institutions (1)	Power With (1)

VAWC Participant (Themes)

The next participant to share was from VAWC, whose insights individually align with all three of the participatory outcomes, as well as all four of the distinctions about power. While in terms of themes, three different ones were arrived at.

Theme: Collaboration with Residents (in Grievance Redress)

For this first theme, the **Feelings of Ownership** as participatory outcome was tagged, plus **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities**. While regarding distinctions about power, it's **Power With** and **Power To**. For **Feelings of Ownership**, the quote was:

“So kung may mga...any concerns, sana pwede namang pumunta ng Barangay para at least nagagawan ng remedy kung ano yung problema. Yun lang ‘yon.”

This is classified as **Feelings of Ownership**, because there is mention of taking immediate action (*“...para at least nagagawan ng remedy kung ano yung*

problema.”) to tackle the community problems/issues to be brought to their attention as barangay decision-makers, which, in and of itself, is an elaboration on a “heightened commitment” to do something about them.

At the same time, this is **Power With** because it hinges on collaboration between the barangay decision-makers and the community members, specifically in terms of the latter reporting directly to them the community problems/issues. This is a textbook implementation of community conversation, as this is a coming together of minds and personalities around a shared challenge, issue, or concern (Swedeen, Cooney, Moss, and Carter, 2012).

Theme: Barangay Decision-Makers Being Made Aware of Community Problems/Issues Previously Unknown to Them

Next theme that materialized during the analysis was the barangay decision-makers being made aware of community problems/issues that were previously unknown to them, which then aligns with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** as participatory outcome, as well as with **Power With** and **Power To** distinctions. The quotes from the VAWC participant’s insights are as follows:

“Eh siyempre, na-surprise ako, na may ganoon palang scenario. Wala akong alam.”

“O siyempre, na-surprise kasi hindi ko naman alam na may mga ganoong scenario palang problema, hindi naman naia-address sa amin.”

Both of the quotes above are expressions of **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** because of the new knowledge that the barangay decision-makers gained from knowing about these supposed “scenarios” (i.e. previously unreported community problems/issues). This captures the operational definition of said participatory outcome, which reads: the barangay decision-maker speaks of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos.

Furthermore, the insight can be traced to the “present-ness” of direct-address videos in that he/she who directly addresses the audience/viewers “know” more than others (i.e. a superior epistemic position), and that he/she (the resident) may have access to truths unavailable to others (Brown, 2012). This also relates to what Gerbaz (2008) wrote of the direct-address approach in that it contributes to bringing us face-to-face with people and points of view that we otherwise would have never encountered.

While in terms of distinctions about power, it is **Power With** because of how the VAWC participant talked about the indirect collaboration that happened between them and the residents after the former saw the geospatial direct-address videos. But also, **Power To** because, just like the participatory outcome that was discussed, it implies a *growth “in the process of taking action by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities in addressing the complaints/grievances”*. In particular, the developed competency or capacity here is the new knowledge gained out of being made aware of the community problems/issues previously unknown to them

as barangay decision-makers (*“Eh siyempre, na-surprise ako, na may ganoon palang scenario. Wala akong alam.”*).

Theme: Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)

As for this next theme, the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome was tagged, as well as the **Power With** and **Power Within** distinctions. The quote that yielded these observations:

“Sa amin po kasi sa (name of sitio), kapag regarding diyan sa basura at hindi na nahahakot agad, eh di aayusin nila.”

As established in the operationalized definitions of the participatory outcomes, this insight falls under **Feelings of Ownership** because it has been mentioned that those who live in a nearby “sitio” (where the VAWC participant lives, which is part of the larger barangay) takes care of the garbage disposal problem on their own as a community, thus effectively “owning” said issue.

While for **Power With** and **Power Within**, it is the former because of the sense of collaboration captured in the quote (*“...kapag regarding diyan sa basura at hindi na nahahakot agad, eh di aayusin nila.”*), while also the latter because, as defined in the study, **Power Within** refers to an increased sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem regarding the tackling of the community problems/issues.

Theme: Influence on the Tackling of Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances

And then finally, for this theme, it is **Influence on Institutions** for the participatory outcomes, while **Power Over** and **Power Within** for the distinctions.

Below is the quote that was analyzed:

“Kapag hindi pa rin, tumatawag ako...meron kasi akong friend na nagtatrabaho sa CENRO. Siya ang tatawagan ko, magpapadala siya ng truck para hakutin yung basura. Yun na lang po ang ginagawa ko.”

This quote captures the VAWC participant’s capacity to take on the issue as a barangay decision-maker, not by wielding power directly, but through acquaintances who are in positions of relative power in the community. Specifically, it is an acquaintance who work at CENRO. This is classified as **Influence on Institutions**, because this is the VAWC participant actually having a direct effect on her community and the residents, which leads directly to the **Power Over** distinction because of the reinforcement of the hierarchical, top-down approach to tackling community problems/issues (i.e. bring it to the level of CENRO). But also, to **Power Within**, because the quote points to her sense of confidence (as someone who has an acquaintance working at CENRO) regarding the addressing of the problem of garbage disposal in her immediate community.

Table 11.

VAWC Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 3).

VAWC Participant – Question 3 (Answered Two Times)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1)
Barangay Decision-Makers Being Made Aware of Community Problems/Issues Previously Unknown to Them (1)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power With (1), Power To (1)
]Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1), Power Within (1)
Influence on the Tackling of Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances (1)	Influence on Institutions (1)	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

Administration Participant (Themes)

For the next set of insights, the study once more turns to the Administration participant, who shared twice regarding question three. For the participatory outcomes, **Feelings of Ownership** was observed in her insights, while for the distinctions about Power, **Power With and Power Within** were tagged in the analysis. The quotes that represent said outcome and power distinctions are the following:

“Kung hindi na talaga nila kayang masolusyonan, saka lang dapat ipasok yung Barangay.”

“Kasi ganoon din ang problema ko, kami muna ang nag-solusyon.”

“Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay. Alam mo ‘yon? Yung nasaan na yung ating bilang magkakapitbahay na yung basura niya, bakit hindi kayo yung mga mag-usap nang mas maayos, kasi mas masosolusyonan nang kayu-kayo lang.”

“Kasi kung lagi niyong dadalihin sa Barangay, kapitbahay mo irereklamo mo dahil sa basura, nasaan na yung anuhan natin ng pagiging magkakapitbahay, ‘di ba? Alam mo ‘yon? Simpleng problema na kapag dinala niyo pa ‘yan sa Barangay, lalaki, magkakaroon pa kayo ng mga gap, eh magkakapitbahay na kayo since mga bata pa kayo. Pwedeng pag-usapan.”

Advantage saka disadvantage yung mga ganoon kasi nga, oo nagsasabi kayo, pero within sana sa inyo na lang ‘yon para mas okay. Kasi magkakapitbahay eh. Iba na kasi kapag ininvolve niyo na yung Barangay.”

Theme: Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)

The first theme that emerged based on the Administration participant’s insights was rooted in her insistence that community problems/issues ought to be resolved by the community members themselves. The participant’s insights serve as more of a reminder to, or call to action for, the residents, communicating that problems/issues ought to be addressed by those directly affected by it. Although it champions community collaboration, it situates it outside the context of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device, thus running counter to how participatory videos are said to drive an evolving process of tackling and exploring shared issues, which commonly result in a much deeper understanding of communal concerns (The Process of Participatory Video, n.d.).

So as such, it falls under **Feelings of Ownership**, because the Administration participant was adamant in stating that the residents should “own” the problems/issues around them, and take the necessary steps in addressing them themselves/on their own. She then added that the Barangay Council should only be a last resort.

In one of the quotes, the Administration participant stated: *“Kung hindi na talaga nila kayang masolusyonan, saka lang dapat ipasok yung Barangay.”* Also: *“Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay. Alam mo ‘yon? Yung nasaan na yung ating bilang magkakapitbahay na yung basura niya, bakit hindi kayo yung mga mag-usap nang mas maayos, kasi mas masolusyonan nang kayu-kayo lang.”* According to Freire (1973), the key results of participatory communication are the people’s articulation of their awareness and also a certain commitment to action. He also wrote that a problem can be fixed if a community claims ownership to, and shows commitment to solving, said problem.

The Administration participant also shared about her own experiences resolving, alongside her fellow homeowners, the issues within her immediate community (*“Kasi ganoon din ang problema ko, kami muna ang nag-solusyon.”*). She also noted the social implications of always bringing one’s complaints/grievances to the Barangay Council, because it may needlessly create gaps among residents/neighbors. As quoted, the Administration participant said: *“Simpleng problema na kapag dinala niyo pa ‘yan sa Barangay, lalaki, magkakaroon pa kayo ng mga gap, eh magkakapitbahay na kayo since mga bata pa kayo. Pwedeng pag-usapan.”*

The quotes, as presented, express both **Power With** and **Power Within**; **Power With** because the insights generally encourage collaboration among residents when it comes to tackling community problems/issues, and **Power Within** because the Administration participant dignifies in her statements the residents’

capacity to solve their own problems/issues (which she further reinforced by sharing that she also tries to solve the problems/issues in their street as resident working alongside her fellow residents, not in her capacity as a barangay decision-maker).

Theme: Appreciation of Residents' Initiative to Participate in the Study

Another theme that surfaced based on the thematic analysis is the Administration participant's rather objective appreciation of the residents having the initiative to share community problems/issues in the geospatial direct-address videos. Specifically, she said: *"Sa akin, sir, yung ganoon, okay, hinahangaan ko naman siyempre, kasi sinasabi nila 'yon."* This insight was identified as an expression of **Power With**, since it implies a willingness on her part to, at the very least, listen to the residents. One aspect of participatory videos to which the aforementioned statement connects is that they demonstrate an ability to capture and nurture valuable knowledge often relegated to the background, or are neglected, that are nevertheless impactful when brought to the fore or center stage (Tremblay & Hayme, 2015).

But that being said, still, no participatory outcomes were observed from the quote above due to the context. Despite her appreciating the residents' initiative to communicate their identified problems/issues by way of the geospatial direct-address videos, the Administration participant followed the quote up with this line: *"Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay."* This, again, indicates non-commitment from the

Administration participant's end to engage the residents in a participatory initiative such as direct-address videos as alternative governance device.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

For the last theme, the Administration participant's insight align with an adherence to the more conventional, hierarchical ways of tackling community problems/issues, with no participatory outcomes emerging. As for the distinctions about power, it is **Power Over**, or the barangay decision-makers' expression of formal hierarchical authority over the addressing of the issue (she mentioned CENRO), specifically the improper disposal of garbage. She said: "*Ganoon naman din. Kahit naman saan ganoon. Kapag hindi na ano, itinatawag sa CENRO. Ganoon yung nagiging proseso namin sa basura.*"

No participatory outcomes were observed here, since the Administration participant, on the issue of the improper disposal of garbage in the subdivision, doubled down on the formal authorities, institutions, and procedures (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002) one needs to follow or adhere to when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making.

Table 12.

Administration Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 3).

Administration Participant – Question 3 (Answered Two Times)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1), Power Within (1)
Appreciation of Residents' Initiative to Participate in the Study (1)	N/A	Power With (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

Barangay Health Worker 1 (Themes)

Furthermore, the first Barangay Health Worker participant's insights align with the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, while **Power Over**, **Power With**, and **Power Over** for the distinctions about power. However, some of her insights do not necessarily adhere to any of the participatory outcomes. The following quotes are most notable and best represents the aforementioned participatory outcome and distinctions about power:

"Tapos yung katulad nung nag-ano ng rugby boy, katabi lang po yung...dapat alam po niya 'yon."

"Tapos yung isa na driver...dapat nire-report din yun kay (name redacted) kasi magkasama sila lagi."

"Kasi po yung lahat ng reklamo po nila, lahat po 'yan, ginagawa po ni Kap. Regarding din sa aso, yung pagtatae, inano din 'yan ni Kap."

"Ano po, aware po si Kap doon sa yung naimbestiga niyo. Lahat po, si Kap hindi po nagkukulang. Mahigpit po si Kap."

"Tapos regarding din po sa...yun nasabi na naman ni hepe na ang tanod namin, sir, 7:00 pa lang po, nagro-roving na po, hanggang 11:00."

Theme: Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)

For the first theme that emerged, the first Barangay Health Worker participant insisted that the residents should be aware of the problems/issues in their immediate community. Although her tone is very much **Power Over** (i.e. the participant seem to be dictating to the residents what they ought to do), what surfaced were both **Power With** and **Power Within**. **Power With** because the insights encourage collaboration among the residents (*“Tapos yung isa na driver...dapat nire-report din yun kay (name redacted) kasi magkasama sila lagi.”*), and **Power Within** because the participant insists on the residents becoming more proactive in addressing their own complaints/grievances (*“Tapos yung katulad nung nag-ano ng rugby boy, katabi lang po yung...dapat alam po niya ‘yon.”*)

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

For the second theme, on the other hand, no participatory outcome was observed, since the first Barangay Health Worker participant was repeatedly insisting that the community problems/issues communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos have already been addressed hierarchically (i.e. top-down) by the Barangay Council (*“Kasi po yung lahat ng reklamo po nila, lahat po ‘yan, ginagawa po ni Kap. Regarding din sa aso, yung pagtatae, inano din ‘yan ni Kap.”*). Another one of her insights reiterate the proactive role that the Barangay Council plays in tackling the problems/issues mentioned, specifically pointing to the Barangay Chairman (“Kap”) as chiefly responsible for doing so. She stated: *“Ano po, aware po*

si Kap doon sa yung naimbestiga niyo. Lahat po, si Kap hindi po nagkukulang. Mahigpit po si Kap.”

Also, she emphasized that, contrary to one of the community problems/issues in the geospatial direct-address videos, the Barangay Council is properly implementing their roving/patrolling schedule. The first Barangay Health Worker participant was quoted saying: *“Tapos regarding din po sa...yun nasabi na naman ni hepe na ang tanod namin, sir, 7:00 pa lang po, nagro-roving na po, hanggang 11:00.”*

In terms of the distinctions about power, the aforementioned insights fall under both **Power Over** and **Power Within**. The former because of her stand that the Barangay Council is implementing accordingly (in a top-down manner), while the latter because all of what she shared point to her sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem as part of the barangay decision-making body, or the Barangay Council.

In terms of participatory outcomes, none were observed in the analysis, since the first Barangay Health Worker participants' insights under this theme are very much hierarchical in orientation, especially when she referred to “Kap” as strict and is never found wanting when it comes to resolving problems/issues. Also, she insisted that the Peace and Security officers are always on schedule in their patrolling, thus contradicting the information received from one of the residents through the geospatial direct-address videos, in the process pushing back against the opportunity for a more participatory relationship between the Sanggunian and the residents.

Table 13.

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 3).

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant – Question 3 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1), Power Within (1)
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

Barangay Health Worker 2 (Theme)

To continue with the second Barangay Health Worker participant’s insights, none of the participatory outcomes emerged. With that said, differing combinations of the **Power Over**, **Power With**, and **Power Within** distinctions were observed. Here are the quotes:

“Halimbawa naman po sa isang lugar, kung halimbawa pong may reklamong ganoon, lahat naman po kami dito, hindi lamang po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), marami po, (name of subdivision), (name of subdivision), lahat po may kawani ng Barangay. Kung may concern ka po sa lugar ninyo, pwede kayong lumapit po doon sa kawani para maipaabot niya po kay Kapitan. Maiparating po.”

“Eh kung sasarinin mo na lang po, tapos may nagtanong sa ‘yo, saka mo sasabihin, eh parang nakakasira naman sa amin bilang kapitbahay niyo na kawani ng Barangay.”

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)

The first quote, as reproduced here in the discussion, adhere to both **Power Over** and **Power With**. **Power Over** because the participant explained the top-down, hierarchical process of reporting a community problem/issue, while **Power With** because it still implies a preference on her part that the residents are supposed to work/collaborate with the barangay decision-makers by reporting the issues properly (*“Kung may concern ka po sa lugar ninyo, pwede kayong lumapit po doon sa kawani para maipaabot niya po kay Kapitan. Maiparating po.”*).

As for the second quote, what was observed are both **Power Over** and **Power Within** because the participant expressed her frustration that their reputation may be affected adversely because the residents opted to air the community problems/issues through an alternative participatory platform (i.e. the geospatial direct-address videos) instead of reporting them directly to her and her fellow barangay decision-makers. She stated: *“Eh kung sasarilinin mo na lang po, tapos may nagtanong sa ‘yo, saka mo sasabihin, eh parang nakakasira naman sa amin bilang kapitbahay niyo na kawani ng Barangay.”* Her conditional view of community problem identification and decision-making goes against Freire’s (1973) concept of naming the world, which concerns itself with dialogue about problems that are of social or economic nature.

The second quote is **Power Over** because her disagreeing with alternative ways by which the residents can talk about community problems/issues (again, in this case, the geospatial direct-address videos) reinforce her commitment to the

more traditionally top-down methods of community problem identification and decision-making. Also, **Power Within** because her disappointment about the residents talking about problems/issues in the community elsewhere speaks of her perceived dignity as barangay decision-maker, and how bypassing her is tantamount to undermining her role.

As for the participatory outcomes, none were observed, because the first quote by the second Barangay Health Worker participant outlines, rather crudely, the hierarchical process a resident needs to go through in case he/she has a problem/issue to report (i.e. he/she needs to report to the homeowners, and then to the Barangay Chairman). This is an expression of VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) formal rules and structures of decision-making, wherein political power manifests.

The second quote, on the other hand, refers to the participant's frustration with such an alternative participatory governance device (i.e. the geospatial direct-address videos), because the residents participating in such may possible ruin their reputation as barangay decision-makers, who may also happen to be their neighbors.

Table 14.

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 3).

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant – Question 3 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power

Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power With (1), Power Within (1)
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FOURTH QUESTION (THEMATIC ANALYSIS)

4. *What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?*

Administration Participant (Themes)

The first participant in the FGD who shared was the representative from the Administration department. Specifically, she chimed in on the question four (4) times, with **Feelings of Ownership** as the only participatory outcome that emerged in the thematic analysis. The rest of her insights did not align with any of the other outcomes. As for the distinctions about power, an instance of **Power With** and several of **Power Over** were observed.

Theme: Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)

The theme to have first surfaced in the analysis was the participant, after having been exposed to the geospatial direct-address videos, communicating about the importance of tackling problems/issues on the community level, specifically in terms of residents collaborating with fellow residents. This is **Power With**, since her

statement points to the residents' ability to work alongside each other to solve problems/issues.

On the other hand, it also taps into the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, since it places emphasis on the heightened commitment the residents ought to take on when trying to take on problems/issues in their immediate community. The insight analyzed for this is:

“Ayun po, yung sinasabi ko nga po, yung kanina, yung may advantage at disadvantage, kasi nga magkapitbahay, baka mamaya, makita ng iba, “o ako lang pala yung inaano mo, magkapitbahay lang tayo, hindi tayo nag-usap.”

Theme: Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues

To continue, the Administration participant also recommended about the types of community problems/issues that ought to be reported through the geospatial direct-address videos. In particular, she said that the problems/issues to be reported should be more serious, meaningful, and less trivial, so that the platform will not be wasted and that the residents be encouraged to resolve their own problems/issues before bringing them to the Barangay Council's attention. The Administration participant said:

“Pero ang advantage, sana, siguro yung mga concerns na mas malalim.”

No participatory outcome has been identified in the analysis here, since the recommendation given by the Administration participant was very hierarchical in tone and intention. It is also worth noting that her claiming monopoly, at least in the quote

above, over the definition of what a problem/issue or “concern” should be is very much an expression of “hidden power”, or, as VeneKlasen and Miller (2002) have written, the influence of a few in controlling as to who gets to the decision-making table and what gets on the agenda.

Meanwhile, by extension, the **Power Over** distinction was observed. This is so because, as barangay decision-maker, the Administration participant prescribes the specific types of community problems/issues that should be reported, and in a top-down manner at that (thus limiting the freedom the residents have when it comes to identifying problems). In “Participatory Visual Methods: A Case Study” (n.d.), it has been mentioned that participatory videos enable participants to engage in discourse on pressing issues while also learning about, and reflecting on, the factors and/or conditions that make them pressing in the first place.

With the above notion in mind, the Administration participant then effectively contradicts the essence of such a participatory governance device when it comes to determining what issues are “pressing” and otherwise, since she decreed that only “deeper” community problems/issues be reported without fully elaborating herself on what “deeper” means (something that the residents themselves should be the ones establishing in a participatory manner).

According to the Administration participant, these are the types of problems/issues that should be reported by way of the geospatial direct-address videos:

“Yung ano, yung sa pushers, sa drugs, ‘no? May violence ditong nangyayari, sa pamilya. Sana parang mas malalim na mga ganoon.”

Theme: Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)

As for the next theme, which also relates directly to the one that comes right after (**Adherence to Hierachy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**), the Administration Participant then communicated her position that the access to the geospatial direct-address videos should only be limited to a select few (i.e. the barangay decision-makers) because it being accessible to all may create relational problems among the residents in the long run. Broadly speaking, this goes against what Freire (1973) wrote about dialogue, or the free and open conversation about issues: that it is a ‘primordial right’, and, as such, is not to be stifled, for it is one of participatory communication’s core principles.

Her take, in addition, also stands in opposition to one of the “A Principles” shared between the Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) and Rapid Rural Appraisal (RRA) methods, specifically “A Reversal of Learning”, which refers to learning directly from rural people on site, face-to-face, allowing one to gain from local physical, technical and social knowledge (Grandstaff, Grandstaff, & Lovelace, 1987; McCracken, Pretty, & Conway, 1988; Gueye & Freudemberger, 1980).

That being said, the insight is an expression of **Power Over**, since she asserts the control that barangay decision-makers should have over such an alternative participatory governance device. She said:

Kasi 'di ba yung...kung magiging accessible sa lahat ng ano...kahit ako siguro hindi ako magsasabi na yung kapitbahay ko, may ganito. 'Di ba?"

"Although mas maganda sana...pero sana, baka siguro limited lang ang maga-access, hindi public. Kasi baka pagmulan pa ng away ng mga magkapatbahay."

Here, no participatory outcomes were observed in the analysis, since the Administration participant was essentially saying that, as alternative participatory governance device, the geospatial direct-address videos should not be "participatory" in the sense that it should not be accessible to the public. In this way, its very purpose is thus defeated. Again, returning to VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), this is "invisible power" manifest, since, as defined, it pertains to when problems and issues are not only kept from the decision-making table but also from the minds and consciousness of the players involved, in this case the subdivision residents.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

Again, relating to the previous theme that emerged, the Administration participant reiterated that the geospatial direct-address videos be accessible only to the barangay decision-makers, noting the problems that may arise if it is to be made available to all. This is **Adherence to Hierarchy** in the analysis, because of her conviction that the Barangay Council, as a whole, should be the one implementing such a governance device (*"Oo. Parang ganoon, hindi siya public talaga."*).

It should be noted that the aforementioned quote inside the parenthesis is the participant's response to when the researcher asked her if the Barangay Council should be the ones to instead have control over it (*"...parang kayo po ang may*

control dito po sa Barangay, kayo po ang parang may hawak nung map, tapos kayo na po yung maglalagay?”). **Power Over** was observed here, since she maintains her stand that the residents not be allowed access to the tool in question, with the barangay decision-makers, if possible, the only ones to be granted access to it.

In addition, the Administration participant also noted the issues with regard the Data Privacy Act, which she believes the geospatial direct-address videos may encroach on if it is to be made freely accessible to residents. Once more, this is **Power Over**, because of the emphasis on the tool’s limited accessibility (that is, limited only to the barangay decision-makers). She said:

“Ang worry ko diyan, sir, yung ating Privacy Act, na baka ma-violate natin. May Data Privacy Act tayo. Baka masagasaan natin. Yun sa akin.”

As for the participatory outcomes, again, none were observed, since, just like in the previous theme, the Administration participant is adamant that the geospatial direct-address videos (and the digital map of subdivision into which they are embedded) only be accessible to the Sanggunian.

Table 15.

Administration Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

Administration Participant – Question 4 (Answered Four Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power

Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1)
Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues (2)	N/A	Power Over (2)
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (3)	N/A	Power Over (3)

VAWC Participant (Themes)

The next participant to have shared her insights pertaining to the question was that from VAWC. In terms of participatory outcome, one of her points align with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities**, while for the distinctions about power, it is **Power To**, **Power Over**, and **Power Within**, spread out across several insights.

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

The VAWC participant first talked about her appreciation of the geospatial direct-address videos, noting that it is of benefit to the Barangay Council if it is to adopt said tool when it comes to database management (of community problems/issues). She also added that the geospatial dimension of the output

(complete with a digital map of the subdivision) will be able to help them barangay decision-makers in analyzing problems better. Her exact words were:

“Hindi, sa akin, mas good ‘yon, para naaano mo yung, naa-analyze mo yung mga problema. May database ka na. Kagaya dito sa amin, may kaso kami na-ano, may database kami na a year, yung comparison, ganoon din sana, mas maganda. Na may database kung ano yung mga nangyayari.”

As mentioned, this insight connects with the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome, because, as established in the operational definitions, this refers to when the barangay decision-maker speaks of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues (*“...Mas good ‘yon, para naaano mo yung, naa-analyze mo yung mga problema. May database ka na.”*). The “database” part of the participant’s insights relates to a study on the “Digital Green” initiative by Gandhi, Veeraraghavan, Toyama, & Ramprasad (2007), which pertains to a participatory process for content creation to cascade essential agricultural information to small farmers in India, specifically the digital video database that was generated for it.

On the other hand, it is **Power To** due to the implied realization on the part of the VAWC participant that she can grow in the process of taking action about the community problems/issues by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities (*“Kagaya dito sa amin, may kaso kami na-ano, may database kami na a year, yung comparison, ganoon din sana, mas maganda. Na may database kung ano yung mga nangyayari.”*)

Theme: Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues

Next theme, to continue, refers to the VAWC participant's recommendation in terms of the types of community problems/issues that are supposed to be reported and be included in the geospatial direct-address videos (just like what the Administration participant has done previously). No participatory outcomes are observed in her insights, though **Power Over** was expressed.

“Kaya lang, baka naman kahit Maritess eh sasabihin pa, eh wala namang kuwenta. ‘Di ba? Minsan kasi, gossip lang eh, palalakingin na, hindi naman relevant yung reklamo. ‘Di ba? Mga ganoon sana.”

Specifically, the participant talked about how some of the community problems/issues are mere hearsays or gossips. Informally, she referred to residents who engage in such as “Maritess”, or a slang for anyone who spread unfounded, baseless information that may affect the reputation of someone in the community adversely. This was classified by the researcher in the analysis as **Power Over**, since she thinks that limits must be set regarding the complaints/grievances to be reported. This implies, on her part, an intention to exert control over, or constrain, what residents can do.

Meanwhile, no participatory outcomes have been observed. This is due to the VAWC participant expressing her skepticism towards the community problems/issues that residents may report to them, even labeling them as “Maritess” who merely circulate/spread gossips instead of actual, serious issues. Given this view, opportunities to participate, at least on the part of the residents, are thus limited. In VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) view, this is “exclusion and

delegitimation”, which refers to how certain groups are excluded from decision-making by society’s and politics’ unwritten rules (in this case, the barangay’s).

Theme: Recommendation on the Types of Citizens Who Are Allowed to Communicate Community Problems/Issues

As extension of the previous theme, the VAWC participant further elaborated as well on the select few residents who may be allowed to report their identified community problems/issues. She made mention that there is a likelihood that those who harbor issues on the barangay level (and who, in the process, may also capture said issues on video) are against the incumbent Barangay Council, and whose only aim is to besmirch its reputation. So as such, she recommended that those to be asked to participate in the digital transect map with direct-address videos in the future be politically neutral residents who have no vested interest or hidden agenda.

Her exact words were:

“Ano naman ‘yon, depende kasi sa magvi-video, sa paggagamitan, kasi minsan, may mga magvi-video, ang intention lang is “i-video natin ‘to kasi yung nakaupo is kalaban natin.” Kasi minsan may political ano diyan eh. ‘Di ba?”

“Sana pwede yung hindi siya involved, nasa gitna lang. Walang bias. O ‘di ba? Kapag alam mong kalaban, bakit mo iinterviewhin siya? Natural sasabihin sa ‘yo niyan, lahat negative. Mas mabuti pang mag-interview ka doon sa wala siyang pakialam sa politics. Kumbaga yung intention niya is i-video niya dahil nakita niya is mali. Yun ‘yon, mas gusto ko ‘yon.”

Again, no participatory outcomes were analyzed from the aforementioned insights, though **Power Over** was observed, because she wants only a few residents to be able to report their complaints/grievances and not all (i.e. constraining what the

residents are able to do). Her insistence on this is an expression of the concept of “exclusion and delegitimation”, which means that certain groups are excluded from decision-making politics’ unwritten rules, practices, and institutions. Also, this is “hidden power”, or the influence some individuals have over who gets to the decision-table and who gets on the agenda (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

The VAWC participant’s last insights, although brief, is an expression of an adherence to hierarchy (no participatory outcomes just like the previous theme), with **Power Over** observed, but also **Power Within**. She was quoted saying:

“Kahit ang lupon, ilan ang kaso niyan regarding diyan sa aso? Tae, ihi, magpupunta, magreklamo.”

This was interpreted in the analysis as **Power Over**, because it is an expression of traditional, hierarchical power (i.e. the Lupon as the arbiter of barangay-level issues), while also **Power Within**, because said insight dignifies the burden of the role of the Lupon as always being on the receiving end of reported community problems/issues.

As for the participatory outcomes, none emerged in the analysis, because the VAWC participant doubled down on the formal rules, structures, and procedures when it comes to decision-making (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002) instead of welcoming openly the alternative participatory governance device (i.e. the geospatial direct-address videos) on the subdivision/barangay level, in this case, the issue with stray dogs.

Table 16.

VAWC Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

VAWC Participant – Question 4 (Answered Three Times)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues (1)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power To (1)
Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)
Recommendation on the Types of Citizens Who Are Allowed to Communicate Community Problems/Issues (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

Barangay Health Worker 2 (Theme)

After the VAWC participant was the second representative from the Barangay Health workers, who shared her insights only once. As far as the participatory outcomes are concerned, her thoughts aligned with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities**. While for the distinctions about power, it is **Power To**. The insights relate to **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** because the second

Barangay Health Worker participant spoke of how helpful the geospatial direct-address videos will be to them as barangay decision-makers. As such, it subscribes to the notion, as defined in the study, that she has an improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the complaints/grievances after having seen the aforementioned videos (complete with the digital map of the subdivision).

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

In particular, the second Barangay Health Worker participant talked about the utility of the geospatial direct-address videos in terms of being a surveillance tool that the Barangay Council can use for addressing community problems/issues more quickly. Her exact words were:

“Ay, ano lang po siguro, yun eh kung, halimbawa, kapag ganoon naman, pwede naman sigurong magsisilbing surveillance na rin po. Para po, halimbawa, mas mabilis nating makukuha kung ano ang concern nila. At makikita rin po natin.”

The quote above manifests **Power To**, because it implies a realization that she can grow as barangay decision-maker by developing new skills, or, in this case, learning about a new tool for community problem identification and decision-making. Manifested in the above insight is the aspect of community conversation that refers to the exploration of ideas, previously untapped resources, and problem-solving strategies of varying nature that could be extracted from the coming together of minds and personalities around a common challenge or issue, even concern (Swedeen, Conney, Moss, and Carter, 2012).

Table 17.

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant – Question 4 (Answered One Time)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues (1)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power To (1)

Peace and Security Participant (Themes)

Afterwards, the representative from Peace and Security chimed in with two insights, which, in the process, yielded none of the participatory outcomes but align with both the **Power Over** and **Power Within** distinctions. The first quote that was analyzed, although short, was this:

“Lahat ng hinaing diyan, nagawa na natin ‘to eh. ‘Di ba?”

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

The aforementioned quote was tagged in the analysis as both **Power Over** and **Power Within**, because it is an assertion that they, as barangay decision-makers, are doing their jobs correctly (and in a traditionally top-down manner,

removed from any collaboration with residents), and that they take pride, and have dignity, in it. This is, according to VeneKlasen and Miller (2002), “visible power”, or “observable decision-making”, which pertains to the visible mechanisms or power that shape the formal ground rules of society (which are unlike alternative platforms or devices, such as the geospatial direct-address videos).

This is also supported by the second quote:

“Katulad niyang parking. Yung parking dito sa ano. Itinaboy na namin ‘yan. Itinaboy namin, lumipat lang sa kabila. Ganoon lang naman eh. Paikut-ikot.”

Once more, this quote aligns with both **Power Over** and **Power Within**, for the same reasons mentioned above. Specifically, the former because of the insistence that they, as barangay decision-makers, have already done their part to address the complaints/grievances (the issue with parking, in particular). And the latter because of the pride he had sharing about the measures that they have already taken to resolve the problem in question (*“Yung parking dito sa ano. Itinaboy na namin ‘yan. Itinaboy namin, lumipat lang sa kabila.”*).

Moving on, in terms of participatory outcomes, there were none observed. This is due to the Peace and Security participant’s insistence that they have already unilaterally resolved the problem/issue that was identified (the issue with illegally-parked vehicles) in the geospatial direct-address videos, while at the same time shrugging off what the residents have shared, saying that the problems/issues just keep on recurring. The bottomline: they have already resolved the issue with illegal

parking; it is just that the residents keep on doing it (parking illegally), hence the persistence of the problem/issue.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

The same quotes discussed above are also the ones that fall under this theme, specifically in terms of the **Power Over** distinction that were observed in them by way of the analysis. To reiterate, it points to the Peace and Security participant’s conviction that they have already unilaterally addressed the issues in question as barangay decision-makers, and that the real problem is the recalcitrance of the residents.

For the participatory outcomes, again, none were observed, with the explanation being the same as the one for the previous theme.

Table 18.

Peace and Security Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

Peace and Security Participant – Question 4 (Answered Two Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (2)	N/A	Power Over (2), Power Within (2)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (2)	N/A	Power Over (2), Power Within (2)

Barangay Health Worker 1 (Themes)

Same as the Peace and Security participant, the insight shared by the first Barangay Health Worker also do not align with any of the participatory outcomes and express both the **Power Over** and **Power Within** distinctions. Said participant in the FGD only spoke once when asked the question. Specifically, she stated:

“Matagal na po ‘yan, sir, pero lagi po ‘yan...kinikilos po kakaagad ‘yan ni Kap.”

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

This first theme emerged because she insisted, just like the Peace and Security participant, that the Barangay Council (represented through the personhood of “Kap”) has already addressed the community problems/issues documented in the geospatial direct-address videos (*“Matagal na po ‘yan, sir, pero lagi po ‘yan...kinikilos po kakaagad ‘yan ni Kap.”*). This is both **Power Over** and **Power Within** because it points to a hierarchical, unilateral exertion of power and the sense of dignity she communicated about their role, collectively, as barangay decision-makers.

In terms of participatory outcomes, none were observed given the **Power Over**-slanted line of thinking of the first Barangay Health Worker participant. Even if **Power Within** was also observed in the analysis, it only mostly refers to her sense of pride as barangay decision-maker in unilaterally solving the problems/issues, without

any mention of the residents' active participation in tackling them. With her mention of "Kap" as the one who takes action in tackling the problems, she, in effect, expresses a commitment to the visible mechanisms of power (the structures and authorities) that shape the formal ground rules of society (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

As extension of the earlier theme, the aforementioned quote is also expressive of an adherence to hierarchy because of her emphasis on how the Barangay Council ("Kap") has already addressed the community problems/issues as collated in the digital map of the subdivision as well as communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos. As such, it is **Power Over**. But also, **Power Within**, because of her heightened confidence and self-esteem when talking about it.

Just like in the previous theme, there were no participatory outcomes observed, because of her insistence that "Kap" has already resolved the problems/issues identified, without taking into account the role the residents have in community problem identification and decision-making, even after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos.

Table 19.

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant – Question 4 (Answered One Time)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

Environment Participant (Themes)

Lastly, the Environment participant's sole insight pertaining to the fourth question is identical with those of the Peace and Security participant and First Barangay Health Worker in that she expresses her conviction that the Barangay Council is always proactive in addressing the residents' community problems/issues as included in the geospatial direct-address videos. With this said, the insight do not adhere with any of the participatory outcomes but articulate both **Power Over** and **Power Within**. Her exact insight was:

“Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po ‘yan. Hindi po ano si Kap diyan sa yung sinasabi nila.”

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

The explanation for this theme in terms of the **Power Over** and **Power Within** distinctions observed in the analysis is the same as that for the previous two FGD participants. It can also be noted that, just like the first Barangay Health Worker, the Environment participant also made use of “Kap” as shorthand for the Barangay

Council, at least in the context of how proactive it is when addressing the community problems/issues they have seen prior as communicated by the residents in the geospatial direct-address videos (*“Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po ‘yan. Hindi po ano si Kap diyan sa yung sinasabi nila.”*)

Just like with the insights of the first Barangay Health Worker participant, no participatory outcomes also emerged, due to her saying that, again, “Kap” is doing the best he can in resolving the problems/issues that were identified by the residents, even saying that the Barangay Chairman is never one to delinquent on them. In effect, this is the Environment participant saying that, when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making, it is predominantly “Kap’ who makes moves, if not the only one supposed to. This, again, is an adherence to the formal structures and authorities of decision-making, as explained by VeneKlasen and Miller (2002).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

The quote in question also falls under this theme because of the Environment participant’s emphasis on the Barangay Council’s top-down proactiveness when it comes to addressing the complaints/grievances mentioned in the digital transect map by the participating residents (*“Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po ‘yan.”*). This is **Power Within**, because of her confidence in stating that they are doing their job accordingly, but also **Power Over**, because of the adherence to a top-down-type of implementation in terms of community problem identification and decision-making.

For the participatory outcomes, they are absent in the analysis, for the same reason elaborated on in the previous theme. To add, in the Environment participant's insights, participation by the residents is not given particular emphasis in favor of championing "Kap's" proactiveness as leader of the Sanggunian. In this instance, he, as Barangay Chairman, is the embodiment of the visible mechanisms of power that shape meaning in the barangay, as well its formal ground rules (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Table 20.

Environment Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 4).

Environment Participant – Question 4 (Answered One Time)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

FIFTH QUESTION (THEMATIC ANALYSIS)

- How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing community problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?*

Lupon Participant (Themes)

For the last question, the Lupon participant was the one who shared the most number of insights, totaling to five. In terms of the participatory outcomes, some of his initial insights aligned with both **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** and **Feelings of Ownership**. As for the distinctions about power, it is a combination of **Power With, Power Within, Power To, and Power Over**.

The Lupon participant acknowledged the benefits of using the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device (at least in the context of community problem identification and decision-making), although he later on emphasized the residents' overall lack of discipline, hence the recurrence of the problems/issues. He also insisted on the holding of a public forum (which is its own governance device), so that the residents can air their problems/issues and, at the same time, they can be reminded by the Barangay Council of their errors.

Themes: Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

The first theme with which the Lupon participant's initial insight aligned was collaboration with residents when it comes to the tackling of community problems/issues, which, by extension, adhered to **Power With**. This is **Power With** because it points to the Lupon participant's articulation on the collaborative aspect of

community problem identification and decision-making (although his statement implies frustration). Specifically, he said:

“Kaya lang, meron kayong mga na-interview na ganyan, na may mga reklamo palang ganyan, na hindi naman nakakarating dito. Kaya ang nangyari, parang surprise.”

What the Lupon participant was surprised of was the residents’ articulation of their awareness of problems/issues in their community, which also implies their claiming ownership of them, and eventually of showing commitment to solve them (that is, by communicating them by way of the geospatial direct-address videos to the barangay decision-makers) (Beltran, 1979).

Now in terms of participatory outcome, it was perceived in the analysis as **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** because the Lupon participant expressed that some of the community problems/issues in the geospatial direct-address videos have not been reported to them/brought to their attention, hence the element of "surprise", and the sense that the participant was made privy to new information. To add, the complaints/grievances might have come across as surprising, because of the pressure that came with the direct-address videos of the residents. After all, similar videos that are, by nature, participatory, enable public interest groups to pressure their government for improvements in government services (Shah, 2005).

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

This next theme is but an extension of the previous one, since, aside from mentioning his surprise by the problems/issues reported by way of the geospatial direct-address videos (all of which he was previously unaware), the Lupon participant also expressed that the digital map of the subdivision into which they are embedded, in his view, is effective, noting the speed with which one can easily identify the issues within one's immediate surroundings when using it. The exact quote was:

“Pero sa tinatanong, sasagutin ko na yung tinatanong mo kanina, yung tungkol sa map na sinasabi niyo, sa akin, okay ‘yan, effective ‘yan. Kasi alam mo, identified mo kakaagad kung ano problema ng kapaligiran mo. ‘Di ba? ‘Yon, maganda para sa akin. Okay siya.”

The aforementioned quote also falls under **the Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome, since it points to a realization on the part of the Lupon participant that the geospatial direct-address videos will be useful when it comes to quickly identifying the problems/issues in the area (which qualifies in the analysis as new competency or skill on the subject of community problem identification and decision-making). It is also **Power To**, because, as operationalized in the study, it refers to increased knowledge or improved skill/s when it comes to tackling the community problems/issues, since the Lupon participant recognized the effectiveness/appropriateness of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device.

Another quote that aligned with both **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** and **Power To** from the Lupon participant (with the same explanation/s):

“Oo, magagamit talaga, kasi nga maaano mo yung problema nila eh. Tukoy mo agad. Magagawa mo. Mabibigyan mo agad ng aksiyon, kasi nga, at least, mayroon doong mga tao na yung siyang haharap agad, mga committee. Kaya ang problema, naso-solve na agad. Ayun po.”

The Lupon participant noted here the usefulness of the geospatial direct-address videos, how actionable they are (*“Tukoy mo agad. Magagawa mo. Mabibigyan mo agad ng aksiyon...”*), and how quickly the community problems/issues can be addressed/solved (*“Kaya ang problema, naso-solve na agad.”*).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

To continue, another theme observed in the analysis, at least concerning the insights of the Lupon participant, was an adherence to a more hierarchical implementation of policies to address the problems/issues. With this, none of the insights aligned with any of the participatory outcomes, specifically due to his mention of the Sanggunian’s “grievance committee” as well as the formal, hierarchical procedures that come with its tackling of community problems/issues, which connects with VeneKlasen and Miller’s (2002) concept of “observable decision-making”, or the formal ground rules and structures and authorities in making decisions, in this case on the barangay level, those of which sit well outside the context of participatory communication.

To continue, the **Power Over** distinction was also tagged. The quotes analyzed from which this theme emerged were:

“Sa amin po, may grievance committee kami na pinatutupad sa bawat lugar. Ngayon, doon po namin pinaalam kung ano yung mga dapat gawin, ano yung mga problema nila. Yun ang sinusolusyonan doon sa grievance.”

“Ngayon ang ano naman ng mga grievance diyan eh yung mga ano ng Homeowners ng bawat subdivision. ‘Yan sila ang ano para hindi na dumating dito ang problema. Doon pa lang, sosolusyonan na nila ‘yan.’”

Both quotes point to the Lupon participant's adherence to hierarchy when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making. Specifically, he mentioned the grievance committees implemented per area, through which the Barangay Council course the policies and ordinances that can be used to tackle the problems/issues (*“Sa amin po, may grievance committee kami na pinatutupad sa bawat lugar. Ngayon, doon po namin pinaalam kung ano yung mga dapat gawin, ano yung mga problema nila.”*).

Moreover, he also talked about the homeowners associations at the subdivisions, all of which serve as the first lines of defense so that the complaints/grievances will not anymore reach the level of the Barangay Council (*“Yan sila ang ano para hindi na dumating dito ang problema. Doon pa lang, sosolusyonan na nila ‘yan.’*). These are mechanisms that represent the concept of “visible power”, which are observable systems through which decision-making on the

community level is made. “Visible power” refers to visible and definable aspects of political power: the formal rules, structures, authorities, institutions, and procedures of decision-making (Veneklasen & Miller, 2002).

In addition, the Lupon participant also points to the holding of a public forum, so that the barangay-level issues (even subdivision-level) can be tackled by both the barangay decision-makers and the residents at the same time.

“Oo nga, magkaroon ng public forum, masabi lahat sa tao kung ano yung mga dapat na solusyonan na ano.”

“Kaya siguro, maaaring ulitin uli ang public forum para mabigyan ng...malaman uli nila na mali yung ginagawa nilang ‘yan.”

The holding of a public forum is largely a traditional, hierarchical way of engaging the community in dialogue, hence its falling under this theme all the same. But also, it is because the Lupon participant also talked about the public forum in terms of how it can be a platform with which the barangay decision-makers can chastise the residents for lacking discipline (“...*maaaring ulitin uli ang public forum para mabigyan ng...malaman uli nila na mali yung ginagawa nilang ‘yan.*”). This is what Freire (1973) referred to as a “problem definition”, which concerns itself with dialogues about problems that are usually of social or economic nature.

And then the last one under this theme was the Lupon participant saying that the geospatial direct-address videos should not be presented or shown during the

planned public forum, implying that it should only be for the barangay decision-makers' consumption. This is an expression of the concept of “invisible power”, which points to the idea, in the context of expressions and forms of power, wherein problems and issues are not only kept from the decision-making table, but also from the minds and consciousness of the different players involved (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

“Baka hindi. Ngayon, siya lang ang mag-ano nito, magsagawa ng schedule.”

All of the aforementioned quotes are expressions of **Power Over** in that they reinforce a traditionally hierarchical way of dispensing power. Although one of them, specifically the Lupon participant's initial insights on the holding of a public forum, also manifests **Power With** because the need for the residents to be able to communicate problems/issues, even grievances, to the proper authorities was highlighted (*“Oo nga, magkaroon ng public forum, masabi lahat sa tao kung ano yung mga dapat na solusyonan na ano.”*).

Theme: Recommendation on Tackling Community Problems/Issues

The next theme identified in the analysis from the Lupon participant's insights was a recommendation (discussed in the previous section) on his part that a public forum be held given the number of problems/issues communicated by the residents through the geospatial direct-address videos. The Lupon participant said:

“Ang sa akin naman, parang suggestion ko lang, siguro para mabigyan ng tamang solusyon itong mga problemang ‘to, tulad ng basurang ‘yan, aso, mga rugby boys na ‘yan, siguro magkaroon ng public forum.”

Based on the analysis, this quote aligns with the **Feelings of Ownership** participatory outcome, seeing as the Lupon participant demonstrates an "increased feeling of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it" ("*...siguro para mabigyan ng tamang solusyon itong mga problemang ‘to, tulad ng basurang ‘yan, aso, mga rugby boys na ‘yan, siguro magkaroon ng public forum.*"). While in terms of the distinctions about power, it is **Power With** and **Power Within**. It is **Power With** because of him expressing the need for collaboration with/to work alongside the residents to be able to address the community problems/issues. But also **Power Within** because it expresses an increased sense of confidence or pride about being a barangay decision-maker in terms of his initiative to address said problems/issues documented in the videos, but specifically by way of a public forum.

Theme: Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline

Another theme identified was the Lupon Participant's insistence that the residents really lack discipline. No participatory outcomes were tagged, which is due to his calling out the residents for not being disciplined enough and are thus the ones who are at fault, which, in itself, is an expression of invisible power, specifically how “marginal groups” in a given society (or, in this case, in a given subdivision/barangay) are made to internalize feelings of subordination and self-hate (VeneKlase & Miller, 2002). By extension, in terms of distinctions about power, **Power Over** was observed. The exact quote was:

“Katulad niyan, eto’y kung tutuusin, problema ng bawat ano ‘to eh, tao lang sa kapaligiran natin eh, yung mga rugby boys. Kanino bang anak ‘yan? O, ‘di ba dapat yung magulang ang mag-ano diyan, mag-suheto sa mga...tapos ‘yang mga basura, ‘yan naman eh, kung ikaw eh may ano sa sarili mo, may disiplina ka, kaya mo namang linisin ‘yan eh, hindi para ikalat mo ‘yan sa bang-bang eh. ‘Di ba?”

This is **Power Over** because the participant decrees in a top-down way, through his insights, that they (the residents) be more disciplined and proactive when it comes to solving their own problems, in particular the issue with children loitering on the streets/the "rugby boys" and the improper disposal of garbage ("Kanino bang anak ‘yan? O, ‘di ba dapat yung magulang ang mag-ano diyan, mag-suheto sa mga...tapos ‘yang mga basura, ‘yan naman eh, kung ikaw eh may ano sa sarili mo, may disiplina ka, kaya mo namang linisin ‘yan eh..."). In effect, this is the participant, in spoken word, indirectly exerting control over what the residents can and cannot do regarding the tackling of community problems/issues.

Theme: Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)

And then lastly, one of the Lupon participant's insights, which has already been discussed and elaborated on previously, specifically under the **Adherence to Hierarchy** theme, refers to how limited the access should be to the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device.

When asked about whether or not the geospatial direct-address videos can be shown during the public forum, he answered "*baka hindi*" ("probably not"). This connects to the insights from the other FGD participants regarding the other questions, all of which also point to how the access to the videos should only be limited to a select few, with some even stating that it should only be limited to barangay decision-makers.

This is **Power Over**, since it implies an exertion of control over, in this case, what the residents can and cannot see or know about, as well as a desire for a more hierarchical/top-down approach to public service on the barangay/subdivision level.

As for the participatory outcomes, none were observed, because the Lupon participant was clear regarding his stand that the geospatial direct-address videos are not to be shown during the public forum, thus eliminating opportunities for participation on the part of the residents. In terms of VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) ideas and concepts pertaining to power, this is an expression of invisible power, under which it is stated that problems and issues are not only kept from the decision-making table but also from the minds and consciousness of the different players involved (in this case, the residents).

Table 21.

Lupon Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 5).

Lupon Participant – Question 5 (Answered Five Times)

Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power With (1)
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues (2)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (2)	Power To (2)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (2)	N/A	Power Over (2), Power With (1)
Recommendation on Tackling Community Problems/Issues (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (1), Power Within (1)
Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power With (1)
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to the Barangay Decision-Makers) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

Administration Participant (Themes)

The next one to have shared her insights on the question was the Administration participant. Based on the thematic analysis, the **Feelings of Ownership** and **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcomes emerged across the various themes, as well as a combination of all of the distinctions about power (**Power Over, Power With, Power To, Power Within**).

Theme: Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

For the first theme, the Administration participant expressed her sense of pride in their desire as Barangay Council to always take action whenever there are problems/issues. This is **Feelings of Ownership** since, through her statement, she effectively articulated her commitment to always do something about them.

Specifically, the quote is:

“Siyempre po, nandoon pa rin yung...sabi nga, ang Barangay, kapag may nagreklamo, talagang aaksiyunan. Kahit gaano kaliit at kalaking reklamo ‘yan, basta may reklamo, aaksiyunan.”

This is expressive of **Power With**, since it places emphasis on the willingness on their part as barangay decision-makers to work alongside the residents in addressing the complaints/grievances (*"Kahit gaano kaliit at kalaking reklamo ‘yan, basta may reklamo, aaksiyunan."*). But also, it is **Power Within** because, as mentioned, there is a sense of confidence and dignity with which she communicated her insights about the action that the Barangay Council always swiftly takes whenever complaints/grievances are reported to them (*"...sabi nga, ang Barangay, kapag may nagreklamo, talagang aaksiyunan."*).

Another insight by the Administration participant still points to the collaboration necessary when it comes to solving problems/issues in the community. But this time, she spoke of how the said issues in the geospatial direct-address videos were a "community problem" and not a "Barangay problem", thus concluding that the

resident ought to work/collaborate with each other outside of the Barangay Council. This collaboration between residents is at the heart of what Swales (1990) refers to as a discourse community, which is defined as a “group that has a common goal or purpose, and use communication to achieve these goals.” Also, it points to two of the defining characteristics of a discourse community: that it has a broadly agreed set of common goals, and has a mechanism of intercommunication among its members.

Furthermore, the participant also said that this is the reason why Homeowners (Associations) exist (*“Pero yun nga po, kalimitan naman ng sinabi is parang, sa akin, in my own opinion, community problem, not Barangay problem. Parang tulung-tulong lang dapat talaga.”*). In precise terms, she said:

“Pero yun nga po, kalimitan naman ng sinabi is parang, sa akin, in my own opinion, community problem, not Barangay problem. Parang tulung-tulong lang dapat talaga yung ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners”.

One last insight that still falls under this theme refers to how the Barangay Council cannot do it on its own, especially given the limited manpower when contrasted against the barangay's large population. This relates to one of the more participatory ways that people can mutually shape meaning, specifically by sharing stories, as well as speaking out and connecting with others (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Afterwards, the Administration participant also reiterated that the problems/issues communicated through the geospatial direct-address videos were more of a community problem, not Barangay. Specifically, she said:

“Kasi hindi kaya naman talaga ng Barangay lahat na bantayan, iilan lang ang Tanod, gaanong kalaki naman ang ating populasyon. So ‘yon, yung problema is parang community problem, not Barangay.”

These two quotes are expressive of both **Power With** and **Power Within**. For the former, it is **Power With** in terms of the power of the residents to work/collaborate with their fellow residents (not necessarily with barangay decision-makers).

As for the latter, the first **Power Within** refers to the resident's sense of confidence and dignity and pride when collaborating with each other every time there are problems/issues within their immediate community/subdivision street, even invoking the role of Homeowners Associations (*"Parang tulung-tulong lang dapat talaga yung ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners"*) given such a context. While the second one, on the other hand, is more of the Administration participant expressing that, although the Barangay Council is always ready to spring into action to address community problems/issues, it is limited in terms of manpower and resources. This is her communicating the sense of dignity that comes with being barangay decision-makers/part of the Barangay Council in the face of endless number of problems being brought to their attention.

Theme: Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

To continue, the second theme was analyzed from another insight by the Administration participant, which aligns with the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome, but also with **Power To** in terms of distinction about power. Here is the quote in question:

“Pero yung ganito pong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda. Huwag lang maging public.”

This quote was tagged in the analysis as **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities**, because the Administration participant was clear in expressing that the geospatial direct-address videos as both "topic" and as "potential application" will be good for community problem identification and decision-making, pointing to a perceived growth in her capacity in tackling the residents' issues; that is, upon assessing the benefits of using the videos as alternative participatory governance device after seeing it.

In terms of distinction about power, this is **Power To**, because it implies new knowledge gained or realization that contributes to her growth in the process of taking action (on the problems/issues) (*“Pero yung ganito pong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda.”*)

Theme: Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues

But also, to continue, **Power Over** was also observed, because the Administration participant then mentioned that, ultimately, the geospatial direct-address videos should not be made public, implying either that its access be limited only to the barangay decision-makers (also based on previous insights). This refers to a preference of hierarchical control over matters of community problem identification and decision-making ("*Huwag lang maging public.*"). Said insight runs counter to the notions that the use of ICT has the potential to improve citizens' otherwise asymmetrical access to information (Gurbaxani & Whang, 1991), and that electronic publishing can enhance the public's access to knowledge (Bhatnagar, 2014).

Another set of insights by the Administration participant that aligns in the analysis with **Power Over**, and falls under the same theme, can be gleaned from the following quotes:

"Yes, para sa akin, ganoon, oo. Parang baka, yun nga, yung privacy nila, masyadong maaano, magiging talk of the town pa sila ng kanilang mga kapitbahay. Parang baka mag-away."

"So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang humahawak...Barangay."

These two are interpreted as **Power Over** because of the Administration participant's concerns regarding privacy, leading to her stand that limited accessibility, as decided upon unilaterally by a barangay decision-maker like her, can prevent conflict between neighbors/fellow residents ("*Parang baka, yun nga, yung privacy nila, masyadong maaano, magiging talk of the town pa sila ng kanilang mga kapitbahay. Parang baka mag-away.*"). Eventually, she concluded that the

Barangay should be the only one to have access to the geospatial direct-address videos (“*So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang humahawak...Barangay.*”).

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy

Another theme observed from the Administration participant’s insights was her adherence to hierarchy (a theme observed in some of the other participants’ insights throughout the analysis). As for this theme, although the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome is present, the **Power Over** distinction was what emerged. The quote in question is:

“Pero yung ganito pong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda. Huwag lang maging public.”

For this theme, the third sentence was what was interpreted as an expression of **Power Over**, since it is clear that the Administration participant is adamant that the geospatial direct-address videos not be made accessible to the public. This is Adherence to Hierarchy since the insight reasserts that, when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making, the barangay decision-makers are who should have access to the tools. To reiterate, this is a manifestation of “invisible power” as elaborated on by VeneKlasen and Miller (2002) in that problems and issues are kept from the decision-making table, and also from the minds of the players involved.

Another set of quotes that also fall under this theme are the following, still by the Administration participant:

“Yun po, katulad ng laging sinasabi ni (name redacted), lahat po yung problema naman is sinusolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay. Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo.”

“Suwerte tayo sa (name of barangay), mas marami tayong subdivision kesa sa ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Siguro yun ang dapat na pinagtutuunan ng Homeowners kasi, siyempre, sila yung leader ng kanilang subdivisions, dapat siguro, kaya nga sila kinuha na ni Kap, yung HOA, para makatulong sa bawat solusyon.”

In terms of the participatory outcomes, none were observed, but **Power Over** and **Power Within** in terms of distinctions about power. Both quotes are expressions of her adherence to hierarchy, though subtly different as to why. For the first quote, it conforms to said theme because of the Administration participant saying that the Barangay Chairman (“*Kapitan*” in the quote) and the whole of the Barangay Council are doing their best in the addressing of the problems/issues as documented in the geospatial direct-address videos (“*...lahat po yung problema naman is sinusolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay.*”); it is just that the problems are repetitive, and that, despite the fact that they are being addressed by the Barangay time and time again, they just merely recur (“*Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo.*”).

While for the second one, it is adherence to hierarchy because of the Administration participant noting that there are hierarchical pathways to community

problem identification and decision-making, as well as to grievance redress, already in place (which directly answers the fifth question), specifically by way of the HOAs, as assigned accordingly by the Barangay Chairman.

Now, in terms of distinctions about power, both quotes are **Power Over**, since they derive from the same overall point: that the Administration participant speaks of an exertion of control and formal hierarchical authority of the barangay decision-makers/the Barangay Council over their constituents (as defined in the study) (*“Siguro yun ang dapat na pinagtutuunan ng Homeowners kasi, siyempre, sila yung leader ng kanilang subdivisions, dapat siguro, kaya nga sila kinuha na ni Kap, yung HOA, para makatulong sa bawat solusyon.”*).

While on the other hand, it is **Power Within** because both quotes are communicative of the Administration participant’s increased sense of confidence, dignity, and self-esteem about her being a barangay decision-maker and about the Barangay Council in general (of which she is a part), at least in the context of community problem identification and decision-making after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos.

Furthermore, the quotes that fall under the **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)** were also classified in the analysis under **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**, since they also communicate the stand that, ultimately, it is the barangay decision-makers/the Barangay Council who are

supposed to have the final say in community problem identification and decision-making (“*So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang humahawak...Barangay.*”).

And then finally, one last insight from the Administration participant was still classified in the analysis under the **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** theme, also with none of the participatory outcomes observed, but with the **Power Over** distinction identified. Specifically, she said:

“Maraming makakakita.”

This quote was interpreted as falling under **Power Over** because, in terms of context, it points to the Administration participant’s preference that the geospatial direct-address videos be accessible only to the barangay decision-makers, because if not, then “*maraming makakakita*” (“*many will get to see*”).

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

For the last theme, one insight from the Administration participant was tagged as such, because of her insistence that the Barangay Council has been, for the longest time, doing all that it can to resolve the many issues identified. The only hurdle, according to her, is that the same problems already previously addressed keep on recurring, hence them being communicated again by way of the geospatial direct-address videos. Specifically, the quote is:

“Yun po, katulad ng laging sinasabi ni (name redacted), lahat po yung problema naman is sinosolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay. Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo.”

As mentioned already under the **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)** theme, this insight express both **Power Over** and **Power Within** (with no participatory outcomes) because, for the former, the Administration participant was adamant about the Barangay Council’s top-down implementation in terms of community problem identification and decision-making, while the latter because she refers to an increased sense of confidence and dignity on the part of the Administration participant (as part of the Barangay Council), specifically in the context of addressing the problems/issues as seen in the geospatial direct address videos.

As for the participatory outcomes under this theme, none emerged in the analysis. This is because of the Administration participant saying that “Kap” has already solved the problems/issues identified by the residents; it is just that they keep on recurring because the residents, one can assume, refuse to change their ways. The quote above, thus, effectively champions the Sanggunian while also placing the blame on the residents’ feet as to why the problems/issues keep on recurring, without regard for whether or not the solutions effected from their end as barangay decision-makers apply long-term.

Table 22.

Administration Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 5).

Administration Participant – Question 5 (Answered Three Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (1)	Feelings of Ownership (1)	Power With (3), Power Within (3)
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues (1)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power To (1)
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to the Barangay Decision-Makers) (3)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power Over (4)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (4)	Improvement of Competencies and Capacities (1)	Power Over (4), Power Within (1)
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)

Environment Participant (Themes)

The following set of insights were from the Environment participant. In terms of participatory outcomes, only one emerged, namely **Influence on Institutions**. As for the distinctions about power, it is a combination of **Power Over** and **Power Within**. The first quote from the Environment participant was analyzed to have been representing three separate themes. This is said quote:

“Saka kami naman po, sir, dito po sa mga kawani, may malasakit naman po sa bawat ano. Kaya nga po kami nilagay ni Kap bawat isang ano para po may ma-tap doon. Sa amin po, wala pong nagrereklamo, pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.”

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation & Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman’s Trust

The quote above is an expression of the following themes (as formulated by the researcher himself): **Assertion of Barangay Implementation and Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues via Chairman’s Trust.**

For the first theme, this was when the Environment participant mentioned that the Barangay Council possesses genuine concern when it comes to the problems/issues being reported to them (*“Saka kami naman po, sir, dito po sa mga kawani, may malasakit naman po sa bawat ano.”*), and that she, individually, perceives that she does her job properly. In particular, she said that she messages “Kap” (the Barangay Chairman) privately so that he is aware whenever problems are reported to her (*“Sa amin po, wala pong nagrereklamo, pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.”*).

Said quote is both **Power Over** and **Power Within** in terms of distinctions about power. **Power Over** because it is a reiteration of the Barangay Council’s being in the position to solve the community problems/issues because they were handpicked for the job/s (*“Kaya nga po kami nilagay ni Kap bawat isang ano para po may ma-tap doon.”*), and that nobody has complained about any of them so far.

While **Power Within**, on the other hand, for essentially the same reason, because, in the quote, she communicates a sense of confidence and dignity and self-esteem in her job as a barangay decision-maker. In terms of participatory outcome, this is an expression of **Influence on Institutions**, since the Environment participant stated rather clearly that she, and by extension the entire Barangay Council, has the Barangay Chairman's trust and, as explained above, that she is able to message him directly about the problems/issues, thus exerting actual influence over decision-making in the community ("*...pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-
pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.*"). This falls under the second theme, **Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues via Chairman's Trust**.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)

Next theme, to continue, is **Adherence to Hierarchy** (no alignment with any of the participatory outcomes). For the first quote, it is an expression of said theme because it refers to the Barangay Council's top-down, rather simplistic system of tackling community problems/issues: the barangay decision-makers messaging (via SMS) the issues directly to the Barangay Chairman (this is **Power Over** and **Power Within**, as explained above).

The subsequent quote is also the same thematically, as well as in terms of distinction about power (**Power Over**). It is **Power Over** because it is an expression of the idea, like those of the other participants previously, that the geospatial direct-

address videos' accessibility only be limited to the Barangay Council, thus reinforcing a very top-down, hierarchical view of community problem identification and decision-making. Specifically, the quote is:

“Sa amin, dito po, pwede po ‘yan, sir. Sa Barangay po.”

As mentioned, no participatory outcomes emerged in the analysis of this second quote because it is expressive of both invisible power and hidden power, especially in terms of problems and issues being kept from the decision-making table, and the influence that is exerted by those who control and set the decision-making agenda (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002). For the first quote, it has hints of **Influence on Institutions**, since the Environment participant, by sending SMS messages to the Barangay Chairman, has a hand in tackling and ultimately resolving some of the problems/issues.

But that said, this is, for the most part, still not necessarily participatory, because even though the residents may be the ones telling the Environment participant about the issues, she still has the final say when it comes to how to phrase or contextualize them to the Chairman. In the end, this is the formal instruments and visible mechanisms of power (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002) in action, specifically the ground rules that the Barangay Council itself has unilaterally decided upon (i.e. the SMS method of reporting problems/issues among the decision-makers with no explicit participation from the residents) when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making.

Theme: Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Only Limited to Barangay Decision-Makers)

Still on the same quote, the theme **Limited Access to the Digital Transect Map with Direct-Address Videos** also surfaced in the analysis because of the Environment participant saying that the geospatial direct-address videos should only be made accessible to the Barangay Council. In terms of distinction about power, it is also **Power Over**, since it is a clear expression of formal hierarchical authority when it comes to the handling and usage of the videos.

To continue, no participatory outcomes were observed here, since the Environment participant stated outright that the geospatial direct-address videos (and the digital map into which they are embedded) ought to be accessible only to the Sanggunian. By implication, this is her saying that the residents be kept from the decision-making table, and that crucial information be concealed or inaccessible, which is an expression of invisible power (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Table 23.

Environment Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 5).

Environment Participant – Question 5 (Answered Two Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power

Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	Influence on Institutions (1)	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)
Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman's Trust (1)	Influence on Institutions (1)	Power Over (1), Power Within (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (2)	Influence on Institutions (1), N/A	Power Over (2), Power Within (1)
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers) (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)

VAWC Participant

The last participant to have shared her insights was the representative from VAWC. Compared to the previous ones, hers were relatively brief. Also, no participatory outcomes were observed, with **Power Over** as the only distinction about power identified in the analysis. The quotes from her insights are the following:

"Nagawa na 'yan ni Kap eh."

"Yung mga kalaban, siyempre, negative lahat ng sasabihin."

Theme: Assertion of Barangay Implementation

The first quote is an **Assertion of Barangay Implementation**. This is because she was clear in her statement that the problems/issues that were identified/communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos have already been addressed/solved unilaterally (*"Nagawa na 'yan ni Kap eh."*), which also aligns

it with **Power Over**. To reiterate, and this is also the basis for the fact that no participatory outcomes were observed in its analysis, this is visible power, since it connects to its definition that it is the visible formal rules, structures, authorities, institutions, and procedures of decision-making that are observed and enacted (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002). In this case, it is the Barangay Chaiman himself who represents the formal authority of decision-making.

Theme: Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)

Furthermore, the second theme emerged because it points to an adherence to formal hierarchical exercise of authority over matters concerning the identification of, and decision-making on, community problems/issues, thus making it **Power Over** just like the previous theme.

As for the second quote, it is also **Adherence to Hierarchy**, because it assumes, without basis, that political enemies will only say negative things about the barangay/subdivision in the geospatial direct-address videos, if only to ruin the Barangay Council's reputation (*"Yung mga kalaban, siyempre, negative lahat ng sasabihin."*). This is also **Power Over**, since it is a statement that decided independently on who should be the only ones to be allowed to air problems/issues by way of the videos.

Participatory outcomes, by extension, are absent in the analysis, since the VAWC participant insights here was hostile towards residents who communicate their problems/issues because they may just be saying negative things to hurt the Sanggunian's reputation (thus dampening opportunities for participation from the

residents' end). This is a clear manifestation of exclusion and delegitimation, or the labeling of the residents as trouble-makers, with their issues being made invisible (VeneKlasen & Miller, 2002).

Table 24.

VAWC Participant Summary of Themes/Participatory Outcomes/Power (Thematic Analysis – Question 5).

VAWC Participant – Question 5 (Answered Two Times)		
Themes	Participatory Outcomes	Power
Assertion of Barangay Implementation (1)	N/A	Power Over (1)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) (2)	N/A	Power Over (2)

Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis)

With all the insights combined as shared by the FGD participants across all questions (pertaining to their perception on the geospatial direct-address videos of the residents communicating their identified community problems/issues embedded into the digital map of the subdivision after having seen them), the data yielded, in terms of themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power, can be seen on the table below, specifically the number of times each one of them occurred/were observed in the thematic analysis conducted by the researcher. For the themes:

Table 25.

Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	24
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	9
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	7
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)	6
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	5
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	4
Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues	3
Appreciation of Residents' Initiative to Participate in the Study	1
Barangay Decision-Makers Being Made	1

Aware of Community Problems/Issues Previously Unknown to Them	
Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances	1
Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman's Trust	1
Recommendation on Tackling Community Problems/Issues	1
Recommendation on the Types of Citizens Who Are Allowed to Communicate Community Problems/Issues	1
Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline	1
Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers	1

The most frequently-observed theme in the thematic analysis was **Adherence to Hierarchy** (with 24), trailed by **Assertion of Barangay Implementation** (9) at second place, both of which are aligned primarily with the **Power Over** distinction. But these two were then followed by **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (7), which is primarily an expression of **Power With**.

And then afterwards, what came next was **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)** (6), which is essentially a return to **Power Over**. And then from there, the theme **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues** placed next (with 5), which was then succeeded by **Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)** (4) and **Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues** (3). The eight other themes that followed from then on were observed only once each throughout the entire discussion and thematic analysis.

Now in terms of the participatory outcomes that were observed:

Table 26.

Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	28
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	10
	9

Feelings of Ownership	
Influence on Institutions	5

Of the three participatory outcomes, again as established by Tufte and Mefalopoulos (2009), **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** were observed most frequently from the FGD participant's insights, followed by **Feelings of Ownership** and **Influence on Institutions**. But consistent with the theme that was observed most frequently in the analysis, which is **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)**, there were 28 instances in the thematic analysis when none of the FGD participants' insights align with any of the participatory outcomes, making **N/A** the most frequently-observed overall, implying their primarily hierarchical, non-participatory view of community problem identification and decision-making after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos.

As for the distinctions about power as put together by Veneklasen and Miller (2002):

Table 27.

Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power
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Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	48
Power Within	25
Power With	18
Power To	6

Of the aforementioned distinctions about power, **Power Over** was observed most frequently in the FGD participants' insights (with 48), followed by **Power Within** (25). Both go together in that, as the participants expressed their adherence to the more traditionally hierarchical ways of community problem identification and decision-making on the barangay/subdivision level throughout the discussion, they also placed emphasis on the sense of confidence and dignity with which they perform their jobs as barangay decision-makers, sometimes at the cost of collaborating with the residents and listening to what they actually have to say. This, in turn, relates to the definition of **Power Over** as established in this study, which is,

among other things, the expression of formal hierarchical authority on the part of the barangay decision-makers over what the residents/their constituents are able to do.

But that being said, **Power With** places third (with 18) and was just seven times less frequent than **Power Within**. **Power With** placing third in the thematic analysis is identical to when **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** also secured the third place in terms of frequency in the themes observed in the discussion. **Power With** and **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** relate to each other because the former is defined as the barangay decision-makers communicating that they can work alongside or *collaborate with the residents* in tackling the issues, that is after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos.

The VAWC Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

For the FGD participant from VAWC, across all five questions (although, as mentioned previously, all of the participants did not necessarily share their insights on all questions), on the tables below are all the themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power observed from her insights during the discussion, with varying numbers depending on the frequency of their being observed in the analysis:

Table 28.

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	6
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	5
Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline	2
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	1
Barangay Decision-Makers Being Made Aware of Community Problems/Issues Previously Unknown to Them	1
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	1
Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances	1
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	1
Recommendation on the Types of Citizens Who Are Allowed to Communicate Community Problems/Issues	1
Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues	1

Just like the overall number of times each of the themes was observed in the discussion based on the analysis, **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)** (with a total of 6) takes the top spot for the VAWC participant. Although at second place is **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (5 times), which demonstrates a push and pull, at least based on the insights she has shared, between the more traditional, top-down way of dispensing power and a predisposition towards collaborating with the residents. But trailing the second most frequently-observed theme is the **Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline** (2), which further extends the VAWC participants' overall adherence to a more hierarchical view of her being a barangay decision-maker. In her view, the community problems/issues recur because the residents lack discipline, not because they are not doing their jobs properly in the Barangay Council.

Moving on, for the participatory outcomes observed from the VAWC participant's insights:

Table 29.

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)

N/A	8
Feelings of Ownership	3
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	3
Influence on Institutions	1

Of the participatory outcomes, **Feelings of Ownership** and **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** were observed most frequently in the VAWC participants' insights (both have 3), with **Influence on Institutions** being observed only once. But the most frequently-observed was **N/A** (meaning no participatory outcomes were observed in the insights; **N/A** recurred 8 times), which stays true to the themes from the previous table, specifically because the highest in terms of frequency, as far as the VAWC participant is concerned, was **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**.

As for the distinctions about power, here is the table:

Table 30.

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

VAWC Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power	
Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	11
Power With	7
Power Within	3
Power To	2

The most frequently-observed was **Power Over**, which aligns with the theme of **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** and **N/A** in terms of participatory outcomes, respectively, as most frequently-observed in the previous tables. The alignment between all three further reinforces the VAWC participant's foremost preference of a more top-down and traditional way of

implementing solutions and/or tackling community problems/issues. Although curiously, those which occupy the second spots in all three (themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power) point to the VAWC participant's rather favorable view of collaborating with the residents in the context of community problem identification and decision-making (after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos).

The Administration Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

Moving on to the Administration participant, collated here, just like for the previous participant, are the themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power, in tabular form, that emerged from her insights (again, across all five questions).

Table 31.

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	9
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to	4

Barangay Decision-Makers)	
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	3
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	2
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	2
Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues	2
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	1

The most frequently-observed theme in the Administration participant's overall set of insights was **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (the same as that of the VAWC participant as well as in the overall frequency of the themes), which relates to the second one that recurred the most, which is **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)** in the sense that both subscribe to a top-down approach to community problem identification and decision-making. The next one, on the other hand, is the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos**, under which falls the Administration's participant's acknowledgment that they can indeed be of use as an alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making. While the three subsequent ones all have two each (in terms of frequency), namely **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**, **Community-Level**

Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council), and Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues. Lastly, which was observed in the participant's insights only once, was **Assertion of Barangay Implementation.**

Now in terms of the participatory outcomes, on this table is the frequency for each one:

Table 32.

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	7
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	5
Feelings of Ownership	3

Influence on Institutions	0
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Of the participatory outcomes, **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** was observed most frequently in the Administration participant's insights (with 5), followed by **Feelings of Ownership** (3). **Influence on Institutions**, however, was not observed, while **N/A**, just like in the VAWC participant's insights and the overall summary, recurred the most number of times, with 7. The **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** theme observed in her insights connect primarily with the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues** as theme, because of her communicating numerous times in the discussion that the videos (and the map of the subdivision into which they are embedded based on location) will indeed be useful in improving the competency of the Barangay Council's approach to community problem identification and decision-making.

Finally, for the distinctions about power:

Table 33.

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Administration Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power

Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	18
Power With	7
Power Within	7
Power To	3

Just like in the overall number of themes observed in all of the participants' insights as well as those of the VAWC participant, Power Over was observed the most number of times (18). And again, just like with the previous participant, the second most frequently-observed was **Power With** (tied with **Power Within**, both with 7). While the last one was **Power To**, with only 3 (all of which align with the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues** theme and the **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome). Most interesting here was **Power Over** being followed by both **Power With** and **Power Within**, which is suggestive of the

barangay decision-makers' preferring to be authoritative in its implementation of policies and response to community problems/issues, while also wanting to collaborate with the residents in tackling them.

The Lupon Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

Moving on, the next set of tables are a summary of the Lupon participant's insights, specifically in terms of the themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power observed in his insights.

Table 34.

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	2
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	2
Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	1
Recommendation on Tackling Community	1

Problems/Issues	
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to the Barangay Decision-Makers)	1
Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline	1

The Lupon participant, unlike some of the other ones in the FGD, only seldom shared, but when he did, the theme that was observed in the analysis most frequently was **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**, as well as **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Grievance Redress** (both with 2). The participant mentioned during the discussion, just like the Administration participant previously, that the geospatial direct-address videos can be “effective” as alternative participatory governance device, at least from their end as barangay decision-makers.

But also, he talked about the **Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline** (which was one of the themes observed in his insights once, alongside **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)**, **Recommendation on Tackling Community Problems/Issues**, and **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)**, hence the recurrence of some, if not most, of the problems/issues communicated by the subdivision residents by way of videos embedded in the digital map.

As for the participatory outcomes observed in the Lupon participant's overall insights:

Table 35.

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tuftte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	3
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	3
Feelings of Ownership	1
Influence on Institutions	0

The order from most to least observed participatory outcomes analyzed off the Lupon participant's insights is the same as those of the Administration participant, with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** as the most frequently-observed (3), followed by **Feelings of Ownership** (1), with **Influence on Institutions** not having been observed at all. But tied with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** was **N/A** (again, similar with the Administration participant).

The former, as a participatory outcome, recurred in the Lupon participant's insights the most because he said repeatedly that the geospatial direct-address videos will indeed be effective as a tool to improve the Barangay Council's grievance redress capabilities, which connects to the definition of **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** in this study: "If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos"

For the distinctions about power, finally, here is the table:

Table 36.

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Lupon Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power
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Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	4
Power With	3
Power Within	2
Power To	1

Again, just like the Administration participant, the Lupon participant's insights as they relate to distinctions about power are also ordered as such in terms of frequency (as observed during the analysis): **Power Over** (4), **Power With** (3), **Power Within** (2), **Power To** (1). **Power Over** being the most observed of the power distinctions relate to **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** as the theme having the most number of recurrences. But interesting as well is that what followed **Power Over** in the distinctions about power, as far the Lupon participant's insights are concerned, was **Power With**, which points

to working/collaborating with the residents for the tackling of the community problems/issues.

The Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

The next set of tables, to continue, are for the insights shared by the first Barangay Health Worker participant, as analyzed specifically in terms of themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power.

For the themes:

Table 37.

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	2
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	1
Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	1

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The themes that recurred most frequently when analyzing the first Barangay Health Worker participant's insights was **Assertion of Barangay Implementation** (with 2), followed by both **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** and **Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)** (with 1 each). Said participant was limited with the insights she shared.

As for the participatory outcomes observed from her insights:

Table 38.

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	3
Feelings of Ownership	1

<p style="text-align: center;">Improvement of Competencies and Capacities</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">0</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Influence on Institutions</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">0</p>

None of the participatory outcomes were observed in her insights except for **Feelings of Ownership** (observed only once). Outside of the outcomes, **N/A** was the most frequently-observed, which relates to the participants' predominantly hierarchical view of community problem identification and decision-making. Furthermore, this is also in keeping with the most-frequently observed of the distinctions about power, namely **Power Within** (4) and **Power Over** (3). There was no instance when **Power To** emerged in the analysis, while **Power With** was observed only once. **Power Within**, in this context, primarily points to the sense of pride and confidence and self-esteem that the first Barangay Health Worker participant, as a barangay decision-maker, had and communicated

As the operational definition of **Power Within** states: *If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her being able to work alongside/collaborate with their constituents/neighbors/fellow residents in addressing the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos.*

Table 39.

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 1 Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power	
Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Within	4
Power Over	3
Power With	1
Power To	0

The Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

And then, to continue, for the second Barangay Health Worker participant, here is the summary (per table) in terms of the themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power observed.

Table 40.

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	1
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	1

Just like the first Barangay Health Worker, the second Barangay Health Worker participant only shared her insights several times, with the most frequently-observed theme being **Adherence to Hierachy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** and **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (both with 1). No other themes were observed.

In terms of the participatory outcomes, on the other hand:

Table 41.

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	1
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	1
Feelings of Ownership	0
Influence on Institutions	0

Improvement of Competencies and Capacities was the only participatory outcome observed in the thematic analysis (with 1). But also, **N/A** (observed once as well). This one instance of said theme being observed connects to the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** theme, in particular because the benefits in using the geospatial direct-address videos identified and acknowledged by the participant contribute to a potentially improved sense of competency or capacity to do something about the community problems/issues (as stated in the operational definition).

And then finally, the distinctions about power. All of the four distinctions about power were observed at least once in the analysis.

Table 42.

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Barangay Health Worker 2 Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power	
Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	1
Power To	1

Power With	1
Power Within	1

The Peace and Security Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

Second to the last of the summaries was that of the insights shared by the Peace and Security participant. For the themes, here is the table:

Table 43.

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	3
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	3

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Only two themes, **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** and **Assertion of Barangay Implementation**, were analyzed from all of the Peace and Security participant’s insights (with 3 each), both of which align with a top-down approach to, or view of, community problem identification and decision-making.

Table 44.

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	4
Feelings of Ownership	0

Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	0
Influence on Institutions	0

Consistent with the themes observed previously, none of the participatory outcomes emerged in the Peace and Security participant's insights after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos, but with 4 instances of **N/A** being observed. This further reinforces the participant's hierarchical view of community problem identification and decision-making.

Table 45.

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Peace and Security Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power	
Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	4
	2

Power Within	
Power To	0
Power With	0

The most frequently-observed distinctions about power in the Peace and Security participant's insights also align with the themes and the participatory outcomes (discussed previously), specifically in terms of their being indicative of his consistently hierarchical take on community problem identification and decision-making (after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos). In particular, **Power Over** was observed the most number of times (4), followed closely by **Power Within**, which allude to the participant's having the confidence and self-esteem as a barangay decision-maker.

Environment Participant (Overall Themes, Participatory Outcomes, and Distinctions About Power)

And lastly, for the Environment participant, collated here are the themes, participatory outcomes, and distinctions about power analyzed from all of her insights, ordered per table from most to least observed.

Table 46.

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes (Thematic Analysis).

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of Themes	
Themes	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	2
Assertion of Barangay Implementation	2
Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman's Trust	1
Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)	1
Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	1
Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers	1

Like in the themes analyzed from the previous participants' insights, **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** was the one observed most frequently, tied with **Assertion of Barangay Implementation**, which imply a commitment to a top-down view of community problem identification and decision-making (like the Peace and Security participant). Other themes observed, with one each, were **Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman's Trust** (a theme unique only to the Environment participant), **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)**, **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos**, and **Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues**.

Table 47.

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes (Thematic Analysis).

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of Participatory Outcomes	
Participatory Outcomes (Tufte and Mefalopulos, 2009)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
N/A	4

Influence on Institutions	4
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities	1
Feelings of Ownership	0

For the participatory outcomes, on the other hand, most curious was **Influence on Institutions** being the most frequently-recurring (the only time said outcome was first place in the ordering from most to least observed), tied with **N/A** (which but, again, reinforces the participants' predominantly top-down view of community problem identification and decision-making). The **Influence on Institutions** participatory outcome, in the context of the Environment participant's insights, is premised on her knowing of her influence as barangay decision-maker on and within her immediate community (in the case of the study, within the barangay and, more specifically, within the subdivision) and how it can directly affect the residents.

The Improvement of Competencies and Capacities participatory outcome was also observed (but only once), which connects to the observed **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community**

Problems/Issues) theme. **Feelings of Ownership**, on the other hand, was not observed at all.

Table 48.

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power (Thematic Analysis).

Environment Participant - Overall Frequency of the Distinctions About Power	
Distinctions About Power (VeneKlasen and Miller, 2002)	Frequency (in the Thematic Analysis)
Power Over	7
Power Within	5
Power To	1
Power With	1

The same with all of the other participants' insights, the analysis conducted by the researcher yielded frequent observations of **Power Over** (with 7), aligning with their mostly hierarchical views on community problem identification and decision-making as a whole, and the utilization of the geospatial direct-address videos as an alternative participatory governance device for it, as shared and communicated in the FGD. Next to **Power Over** was **Power Within** (5), combining the top-down approach to community problem identification and decision-making most, if not all, of them repeatedly articulated with the confidence and sense of pride they have in their roles as barangay decision-makers.

And then with one each are both **Power To** and **Power With**. The former relates to the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** theme and **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** participatory outcome, while the latter align with the theme of the **Residents' Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers** and the **Influence on Institutions** participatory outcome.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

To reiterate, this was the study's research question:

- What themes emerged (inductively) from the barangay decision-maker's insights (with VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power and Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes) on the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making, as well as from some of the residents' insights as communicated by way of the videos?

But before the segment dives into the addressing of the aforementioned question (from the results and discussion), first, a brief overview as to the data collated using the geospatial direct-address videos, at least in terms of community problems/issues.

As discussed in the previous chapter, the geospatial direct-address videos (i.e. addressing the camera directly while speaking) of the residents communicating their identified community problems/issues at specific areas/location around the subdivision were arrived at/collated by way of a transect walk, which the researcher has conducted along with a companion, who served as guide around the subdivision, as well as enabled access to the residents, and ultimately secured their willingness

to participate. Overall, a total of **19** subdivision residents participated, with them mentioning **45** complaints/grievances as a whole.

But, as mentioned in the Results and Discussion, eliminating the redundancies, the transect walk yielded **25** unique community problems/issues, as communicated by way of the geospatial direct-address videos of the residents. They are the following (ordered in terms of first to last to have been communicated by each resident/participant):

- Bawal magtinda
- Laging traffic
- Mga asong pagala-gala
- Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura
- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Maling pagpaparada ng sasakyan
- Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada
- Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD)
- Rugby Boys
- Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards)
- Baradong Bang-Bang
- Mga nakatambak na basura
- Mga basag na bote sa kalsada (kabataan)
- Maiingay na motor (kabataan)
- Nagkalat na mga kabataan kahit dis-oras nang gabi

- Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod
- Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders)
- Walang number ang mga bahay (address)
- Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan
- Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada
- Dumi ng mga aso
- Mga batang pinapabayaang ng mga magulang sa kalye
- Tokhang (mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit)
- Mga tsismosang kapitbahay

In the discussion, it has been mentioned that most of the community problems/issues communicated by the subdivision residents by way of the geospatial direct-address videos align with the results of a survey conducted by GMA News' Facebook page in 2018, during the lead-up to the Barangay Elections. The survey question answered by the respondents: *“Ano ang mga problema sa inyong barangay na nais ninyong masolusyonan ng mga mananalo sa Eleksyon 2018?”*

Of the **25** unique complaints/grievances communicated by the subdivision residents by way of the direct-address videos, **19** align with the GMA News survey's results. To reiterate, here were the barangay-level “issues” or “problems” that emerged in the 2018 survey:

1. **Basura** (55 Answers)
2. **Tambay** (45 Answers)
3. **Droga** (33 Answers)
4. **Nakaparadang Sasakyan** (27 Answers)
5. **Ingay** (21 Answers)
6. **Aso** (19 Answers)
7. **Sirang Kalsada** (14 Answers)
8. **Presensiya ng mga Tanod** (13 Answers)
9. **Kuryente at Ilaw** (12 Answers)
10. **Tubig** (9 Answers)

Breaking down the subdivision residents' identified community problems/issues per category identified in the GMA News survey, majority of them, as mentioned, fell under all **10** answers.

1. Basura (55 Answers)

- Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura
- Mga nakatambak na basura
- Mga basag na bote sa kalsada (kabataan)
- Dumi ng mga aso

2. Tambay (45 Answers)

- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Nagkalat na mga kabataan kahit dis-oras nang gabi
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan

3. Droga (33 Answers)

- Rugby Boys
- Tokhang (mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit)

4. Nakaparadang Sasakyan (27 Answers)

- Laging traffic
- Maling pagpaparada ng sasakyan

5. Ingay (21 Answers)

- Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan)
- Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards)
- Maiingay na motor (kabataan)
- Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan

6. Aso (19 Answers)

- Mga asong pagala-gala
- Dumi ng mga aso

7. Sirang Kalsada (14 Answers)

- Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada

8. Presensiya ng mga Tanod (13 Answers)

- Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod

9. Kuryente at Ilaw (12 Answers)

- Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente
- Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada

10. Tubig (9 Answers)

- Baradong Bang-Bang

This then leaves only **6** community problems/issues as communicated by the subdivision residents through the videos that otherwise did not align with the results of the GMA News survey from 2018. They are the following:

- Bawal magtinda
- Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD)
- Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders)
- Walang number ang mga bahay (address)
- Mga batang pinapabayaan ng mga magulang sa kalye
- Mga tsismosang kapitbahay

As for the locations of the community problems/issues communicated by the subdivision residents in terms of where they were recorded/documentated (by way of the geospatial direct-address videos) during the transect walk, a digital map of the subdivision was created, where each was situated accordingly depending on where the residents were when the direct-address videos of their problems/issues were captured.

In collaboration with a multimedia arts practitioner, the researcher developed said map with clickable links that take the user directly to a landing page where the summary of each resident's problems/issues are listed, as well as buttons that, when clicked, lead to the direct-address videos. The map was made initially as a PDF document, and then as a Microsoft PowerPoint file for easier access and navigation.

As summarized in the tables presented in the Results and Discussion, the subdivision has a total of 10 official streets/drives (but 11 overall counting the respondent near the entrance of the subdivision), which the researcher was able to “transect” during the walk with his companion/guide. To reiterate:

Table 49.

Summary of Community Problems/Issues Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – First Table.

NEAR ENTRANCE	FIRST STREET/DRIVE	SECOND STREET/DRIVE	THIRD STREET/DRIVE	FOURTH STREET/DRIVE	FIFTH STREET/DRIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bawal magtinda • Laging traffic • Mga asong pagala-gala 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mga nag-iinuman sa labas na nagkakagulo (halos magpatayan) • Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharang sa kalye) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binabaha at lubak-lubak na kalsada • Late na pagdating ng naipangakong wheelchair (para sa PWD) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rugby Boys • Mga jeep na nakaparada sa kalsada (nakakagawang “blindspots” para sa biglang tumatawid na mga bata) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inirereklamo palagi ng kapitbahay dahil sa ingay kahit maingay din ang nagrereklamo (double standards) • Baradong Bang-Bang

Table 50.

Summary of Community Problems/Issues Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – Second Table.

SIXTH STREET/DRIVE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malubak na kalsada • Mga nakatambak na basura • Mga kabataan (mga basag na bote sa kalsada, maiingay na motor, nagkalat sa labas kahit dis-oras nang gabi) • Kalsada (dapat i-aspalto) • Bang-Bang (tinatapunan ng basura) • Illegal parking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kalsadang ginawa nang talyer • Kulang sa roving ang mga Barangay Tanod • Mga asong pagala-gala • Walang pangalan/signage ang ibang mga street (nakakalito/nakakaligaw para sa mga riders) • Walang number ang mga bahay (address) • Malalagong puno na malapit sa linya ng kuryente

Table 51.

Summary of Community Problems/Issues Communicated in the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Per Street/Drive) – Third Table.

SEVENTH STREET/DRIVE	EIGHTH STREET/DRIVE	NINTH STREET/DRIVE	TENTH STREET/DRIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lubak-lubak na kalsada • Baradong Bang-Bang • Malalagong puno na malapit sa kuryente • Mga asong pagala-gala • Maiingay na mga dayo na bumibili sa tindahan • Hindi gumaganang ilaw sa kalsada • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga asong pagala-gala • Dumit ng mga aso 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wala sa oras na paglalabas ng basura ng mga residente (kahit hindi pa araw ng pagdaan ng truck) • Maling pagpaparada ng mga sasakyan (humaharang sa kalye) • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura • Baradong Bang-Bang 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Madalang dumadaan ang truck ng basura • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga batang pinapabayaang mga magulang sa kalye 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tokhang (Mali-mali ang pangalan, walang kasiguraduhan ang ebidensiya, kahit nagbago na ipapadampot ulit) • Mga basurang nagkalat • Mga tsimosang kapitbahay

During the transect walk, Sparta Drive has had the most number of residents who participated in the study (that is, by communicating their identified community problems/issues by way of the geospatial direct-address videos), with **5**, which was

then followed by Olympus Circle, Hera Drive, Rhodes Drive, and Nepomuceno Drive, each with 2. While Zeus Drive, Athena Drive, Achilles Drive, Poseidon Drive, and Proserpina Drive all had a participant each, including one near the subdivision's entrance.

Research Question: *What are the perspectives of the barangay decision-makers and subdivision residents on the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?*

Generally speaking, all of the residents who communicated their problems/issues by way of the geospatial direct-address videos demonstrate both **Increased Feelings of Ownership** as a participatory outcome and **Power Within** as distinction about power, since their willingness alone, and their eventual participation in the capturing of the direct-address videos as they communicate the problems refer to a heightened commitment to do something about them, as well as showing a sense of confidence and dignity in their deciding to air their problems/issues by way of the videos.

But more specifically, because some of the residents shared more than what the study required them to (to merely communicate their identified problems/issues as subdivision residents), their insights naturally lended themselves to analysis, which yielded, as mentioned, **Increased Feelings of Ownership**. This is because some of them mentioned that they have already reported several of the

problems/issues to the appropriate authority, which hints at their proactiveness, and, by extension, their heightened commitment to do something about the issues.

As for **Actual Influence on Institutions**, some of the residents' insights run counter to it, because their problems/issues are yet to be tackled/resolved on the level of the barangay, even provincial, thus implying powerlessness and lack of influence on their part. But that being said, there were also some insights that demonstrate said participatory outcome quite affirmatively, as the residents were clear in their confidence that they have an immediate impact on their community (especially in the context of collaborating with their fellow residents in the resolution of their problems/issues).

While in terms of distinctions about power, **Power Over**, **Power With**, and **Power Within** emerged in the analysis of the residents' insights. Firstly, **Power Over** because some of those they have shared point to hierarchy in decision-making, at least on the subdivision and barangay level. One instance of this power distinction manifesting in the insights was when some of the problems/issues identified are not immediately addressed or resolved because the culprits are allied with the incumbent Sanggunian. Another was when one resident highlights the deeply flawed unilateral decision-making on the part of the Barangay Council during the implementation of Tokhang, wherein arrests are made without proper collection of evidence and even when the identified drug users/suspects have already changed their ways. One resident also mentioned that it is best that the problems/issues that he identified be resolved, because otherwise, the homeowners president will be angry.

As for **Power With**, this is most readily apparent in one resident's insights, wherein it was mentioned that she was more than happy to collaborate with her fellow residents/her neighbors to resolve problems/issues, because there is no need to report them to the Sanggunian every time. At the same time, this is also **Power Within**, since there is confidence on her part, as well as pride and heightened self-esteem, in tackling the community problems/issue on their own as subdivision residents/as neighbors living on the same street/drive. Some other expressions of both power distinctions are apparent when, for instance, one resident talks about his confidence that the juvenile delinquents on their street/drive will not be able to vandalize his house because he is always ready to push back. Also, when he mentioned that the city deserves better, cleanliness-wise.

After the transect walk conducted by the researcher and his companion/guide, which resulted in the recording of geospatial direct-address videos of the subdivision residents communicating their problems/issues, as well as the creation of an interactive digital map that collated the direct-address videos depending on where the problems/issues were communicated by the residents, an FGD was then conducted with select barangay decision-makers, at least in relation to the geospatial direct-address videos as an alternative participatory governance device.

With the assistance of the Sangguniang Barangay (Barangay Council), the researcher was able to secure an FGD schedule with representatives from the Barangay Council departments, namely one participant each from the

Administration, VAWC, Lupon, Peace and Security, and Environment departments, plus two Barangay Health Workers.

After the FGD, the insights shared by the barangay decision-makers per question were interpreted by conducting a **deductive** thematic analysis, basing on Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes and VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power. In the process of the analysis, themes emerged/were also identified **inductively** based on the recurrence of key insights.

In the previous chapter, the barangay decision-makers' insights were discussed extensively in terms of the participatory outcomes and distinctions about power that emerged, as well as the themes, both in general and per participant. For the overall frequency of the themes that came up during the thematic analysis, **Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (24 times) as a theme was the most observed in the insights, followed by **Assertion of Barangay Implementation** (with 9). Both are very top-down in terms of view of community problem identification and decision-making, as they predominantly reinforce a preference on the part of the barangay decision-makers to adhere to convention and address problems/issues hierarchically/from a position of authority. But curiously enough, these two themes were then followed by **Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)** (7), which indicates also their acknowledgment of the necessity for the residents to work with them on the issue of, again, community problem identification and decision-making, though in a manner that is not extensively collaborative.

Furthermore, all these extend into the next most frequently-observed theme, which is **Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)** (6 times). In the FGD, numerous barangay decision-makers spoke of the potential benefits of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device, with some elaborating on its effectiveness to locate community problems/issues more efficiently, as well as how it can serve as barangay surveillance tool. This is consistent with the fact that next theme that emerged the most throughout the analysis was **Perceived Benefits of Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues** (5 times).

In addition, some of the FGD participants also elaborated on the importance of the subdivision residents working/collaborating with each other to resolve issues more than with them as barangay decision-makers. Despite their generally hierarchical view of community problem identification and decision-making, they also centered on how, in some cases, the Barangay Council is not at all needed, because some of the issues can already be addressed by just the residents themselves. As interpreted in the thematic analysis, this was the **Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)** theme, which was observed by the researcher four times.

They also recommended, if ever the geospatial direct-address videos be adopted by the Barangay Council as alternative participatory governance device, that the problems/issues to be included/documented be the more serious ones that actually need the attention of the council, and not those that can easily be resolved

by the residents on their own. This was the **Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues** theme, which was observed three times.

Regarding the participatory outcomes as outlined by Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009), majority of the barangay decision-makers' insights were analyzed to have not necessarily aligned with any one of them, being classified instead as **N/A** (which recurred 28 times). This, the study concludes, is steadily consistent with the two most frequently-observed themes as discussed in the previous paragraphs, both of which imply the FGD participants' traditionally hierarchical perspective on community problem identification and decision-making. But that being said, the second most frequently-observed participatory outcome in the barangay decision-makers' insights, at least insofar as the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device is concerned, was **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** (which recurred 10 times in the analysis).

The insights that were interpreted in the thematic analysis to have been aligned with said participatory outcome are those that took notice of how potentially effective and useful the geospatial direct-address videos can be as alternative participatory governance device on the barangay level, specifically because of their exposure to them, according to the operational definition of the participatory outcome, opened them up to an improved sense of competency or capacity in tackling the community problems/issues. From the themes, that which aligned with **Improvement of Competencies and Capacities** was **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues**.

The next participatory outcome, which recurred 9 times, was **Feelings of Ownership**, followed by **Influence on Institutions** with 5. The recurrence of the former in the analysis of the barangay decision-makers' insights was observed to have had multiple contexts, which is either the FGD participants talking about their heightened commitment to do something about the community problems/issues after having seen the geospatial direct-address videos, or them pertaining to how the residents should collaborate and, in effect, own up to the addressing of, again, the problems/issues.

But in terms of **Influence on Institutions**, the themes that align with it, among others, were **Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances** and **Influence on Grievance Redress Via Chairman's Trust**. This is because the insights shared by the barangay decision-makers that aligned with said themes point to their perceived influence on their community, the residents, even acquaintances who are in a position (like the Barangay Chairman himself and a City Environment & Natural Resources personnel) to tackle the community problems/issues identified in the geospatial direct-address videos.

And then for VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power, the one that recurred most frequently was **Power Over** (48 themes). Overall, this conforms to the predominant narrative, as analyzed from the barangay decision-makers' insights, that they are most adherent to the more hierarchical, top-down way of addressing problems/issues and not so much to the significantly more collaborative approach encouraged by the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device. Consistent also with this is **Power Within** coming in

at second, which furthers the FGD participants' feelings of confidence and dignity in their status as barangay decision-makers and candidly speaking, as authority figures who may exert control over the destiny of their constituents/immediate community (and to be even more specific to the context of the study, the subdivision residents).

But to serve as counterpoint to the findings in the previous paragraphs, **Power With**, even though coming in only at third, also recurred a significant number of times (18 times, specifically). Although the barangay decision-makers are averse of the residents' complete participation in community problem identification and overall decision-making (again, as encouraged in the geospatial direct-address videos), they are still open to a degree of collaboration with them, specifically in terms of the residents letting them know the problems/issues in the community, albeit in a more traditional way (outside of alternative means like the videos, or the digital map into which they are embedded).

Lastly, **Power To** was also observed, though only five times. The insights that fell under this distinction about power are mostly also aligned with the **Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues**, because, as the operational definition of **Power To** states: *If the barangay decision-maker/resident speaks of his/her realization that he/she can grow in the process of taking action by developing new skills, competencies, and capacities in addressing the community problems/issues after having seen, or while participating in, the geospatial direct-address videos.*

Overall, the barangay decision-makers who participated in the FGD were predominantly adherent to the status quo when it comes to community problem identification and decision-making; that is, the traditional, hierarchical way of the barangay decision-makers being informed of the problems/issues through informal verbal reports (or those sent, also just as informally, by way of SMS or through online means) and then acting upon them unidirectionally, with the residents playing a mere passive role instead of a more proactive one that the geospatial direct-address videos encourage. This is contrary to the need for an adaptive and responsive approach rather than prescriptive approach to policy-making and implementation, as postulated in the joint project of the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) and UNICEF (2009).

But that being said, the barangay decision-makers were still very much open to collaborating with the residents, although in a limited capacity only. In their view, predominantly, the residents are not the barangay decision-makers' equal (or the Barangay Council they represent as a whole) on the question of community problem identification and decision-making. Furthermore, they also took issue with the residents who were the geospatial direct-address videos, specifically due to their ill-advised (at least in the barangay decision-maker's view) decision to air their problems/issues by way of the videos when they easily could have just directly corresponded with them.

Also, because some of the barangay decision-makers are familiar/acquaintances with some of the residents in the direct-address videos, they expressed their desire for the residents to just work with each other to resolve the

problems/issues that they have communicated instead of waiting for the Barangay Council to address them, noting that some of them, in their capacity not as barangay decision-makers but as community members/subdivision residents, do the exact same thing (that is, collaborate with fellow residents/neighbors). Some of the barangay decision-makers were also adamant that they are actively performing their duties to resolve the problems/issues, even going as far as saying that some of them, they claim, have already been addressed/resolved countless times, with the problems just merely recurring.

Apart from privacy issues and the perceived dangers of allowing such a tool or device to be openly accessible to the public/the residents, the barangay decision-makers had positive things to say about the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device. Specifically, they highlighted the usefulness of the tool/device in locating community problems/issues more easily and efficiently in the map.

Some of them also acknowledged the geospatial direct-address videos' (and the digital map into which they are embedded) potential if ever it becomes an official mobile/digital application to be used by the Barangay Council for purposes of developing a database for the community problems/issues (even more specifically, to be incorporated in the grievance committee's pre-existing grievance redress/participatory governance system), though they reiterated that it be used only by the barangay decision-makers and be kept away from residents who have an agenda. It was also noted that the community problems/issues should, at the very

least, be the more serious ones, and not those that can easily be resolved by the residents themselves.

It was also highlighted early on in the paper, but merits inclusion here all the same, the numerous features/attributes of the geospatial direct-address videos: that it is accurate, precise, and replicable (with its findings being near-identical with those in a Facebook survey conducted by GMA News in 2018). Also, that it is visceral and convincing, given the unfiltered sharing of insights on community problems/issues by the residents as captured on video, and in a direct-address manner at that. It is also actionable, because one can easily grasp the nature of the problems/issues communicated on video as well as locate just as conveniently the locations from which they emanate (by way of the digital map).

And lastly, efficient, because the walk through which the collection and recording of the geospatial direct-address videos are possible can be done in just an hour or so (depending on scale and scope of the place/area to be transect-walked), plus scalable, with the GMA News survey, again, serving as basis for this, and how the findings, despite its being national in scope, were easily repeated by the geospatial direct-address videos on the barangay/subdivision level.

Recommendations

Given the study's findings, the researcher recommends that a similar query be undertaken on community problem identification and decision-making, but using or testing an altogether different platform/tool/device that can be used on the barangay,

even city, level. The geospatial direct-address videos can also be reproduced, but with a different, either smaller or larger scope.

Another recommendation is for an almost identical study be undertaken, but the residents' insights are the ones to be analyzed thematically (using a slightly modified version of the operational definitions of Tufte and Mefalopulos' (2009) participatory outcomes and VeneKlasen and Miller's (2002) distinctions about power) in a much more comprehensive manner this time around. Future studies can also develop a more quantitative approach to identifying the community problems/issues on the subdivision or barangay level, with all of the residents being surveyed.

Given the study's participatory slant, the researcher, in addition, also recommends that the geospatial direct-address videos be made/developed by the residents themselves, with them undergoing a short workshop first and then eventually being allowed to shoot the videos and create the digital map (into which the videos are to be embedded) themselves. By the same token, a similar undertaking can also be conducted, but with the barangay decision-makers developing the tool on their own (another may be a combination of residents and barangay decision-makers as designers of the map/shooters of the videos). The researcher, either as an insider or outsider, may collaborate with the residents or the barangay decision-makers for the same goal of developing a series of geospatial direct-address videos.

Also, different variations of the videos can be shot, with future studies recommended to only record footage, without anyone expressing verbally (i.e.

without residents talking in front of, or even communicating directly at, the camera), of the community problems/issues; that or static pictures of the issues (similar to Photovoice). The geospatial direct-address videos may also be converted/transformed into a full-fledged mobile application for barangay, city, even provincial, use.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Transcription of the Focus Group Discussion (Barangay Decision-Makers)

1ST QUESTION

Researcher:

So formally po, magpapakilala lang po ako. Ako po si Ivan Khalil Descartin. Ako po ay, ilang taon ba, mga 24 years po akong nakatira sa (name of subdivision). Pamangkin po ako ni former secretary. Sa Garden Villas na po kami nakatira ngayon. Tapos, siyempre po, pamilyar at very malapit sa akin, sa puso ko ang (name of subdivision). Diyan ako lumaki, 'yan ang lugar na ininugan ko buong buhay ko hanggang magbinata ako, matuli, at magtapos ng pag-aaral. Ayun po, so bilang yun nga po ang pinanggagalingan ko, I took it upon myself na gawing focus din po talaga ang (name of subdivision) po. Ayan, so nabuo po natin yung mapa ng (name of subdivision). So ang tanong ko po sa inyo: Ano po yung tingin niyo po doon sa ipinakita ko po sa inyo na, yun nga po, parang mapa po. Kung tawagin ko po siya ay digital na transect map. Pero tawagin na lang po natin siyang mapa. Ano po ang masasabi niyo po doon sa mapa na 'yon na, yun, parang "interactive" po kumbaga, kung tawagin. Yung naci-click po na parang andito yung isang residente na maci-click siya, lalabas yung video, lalabas yung summary. Ano po yung masasabi niyo po doon sa ganoon, yung mapa po na ganoon, napipindot, tapos lalabas yung problema/isyu. Ano po ang masasabi niyo bilang decision-maker po sa barangay. Kasi, ano po, hindi lang po kayo basta residente po, all seven of you po, hindi lang po kayo residente, mga decision-maker po kayo dito sa (name of barangay). So

ayun po, so ano po ang masasabi niyo po doon sa map na ipinakita ko po sa inyo. Bilang decision-maker po sa barangay, how did it make you feel po? Ano po ang masasabi niyo? Ano po yung naparamdam sa inyo nung...

VAWC Participant:

Okay, ang masasabi ko dito, kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina, although iniimplement naman ng barangay 'yan. Lalo na si Kap, kumbaga dapat lang naman magtapon sa tamang tapunan. Wala lang talagang disiplina. Tapos yung talagang...sa aso, 'yan naman talaga'y napagusapan na eh, ibababa na yung ordinansa niyan eh, na bawal na talagang magalpas ng aso. May mga multa-multa na 'yan eh, hindi ko lang alam kailan naiimplement. At doon naman sa mga kabataan na kagaya ng sa hawak ko sa VAWC, mag-iimplement na rin kasi kami ng curfew, inaantay na lang din namin ibaba 'yan eh. Kumbaga isang tarpaulin kasi yung batas na ilalagay sa bawat lugar para maintindihan nila. Yung lahat ng magiging bawal. At diyan din sa parking, halos pinapatanggal na 'yan eh, kaya lang matitibay din ang mukha kung bakit pagkatapos ipatanggal, ibabalik na naman. O 'di ba? Tapos yung sa nagrurugby, wala akong alam doon. Pero dapat, kung may reklamo sila, inform lang nila na sa amin, dadamputin naman, bakit namang hindi? Kasi talagang ayaw na ayaw namin talaga ng rugby kapag regarding diyan. Tapos, ano pa bang problema?

Researcher:

Yung sa mapa po, Ma'am? Ano pong...

VAWC Participant:

Yung sa mapa, yung binuo niyong mapa, parang halos, kada street, ang problema, sinasabi nila, more on basura. Basura at aso. 'Yon, 'yon. Basura at aso, yun lang 'yon. 'Yon siguro, ang tulong lang doon is yung tao na lang, disiplina lang. Kapag tayo naman ay marunong makiramdam, alaga mong aso 'yan eh. Kapag alam mong nakakaperwisyo ka, ikaw na mismo sa sarili mo, 'di ba?

Administration Participant:

Hindi, ang parang pinaka-tanong yata ni sir is about map, kung gaano siya ka-effective. Sa akin effective talaga, mas maganda siya, kasi kahit ako, minsan nag-Google Map ako eh. Parang mas okay siya lalo na kung iimplement sa mga barangay. Parang mas okay siya kung magiging apps natin siya. Oo, parang ayun naman yung pinakatanong. Oo, dapat meron, para mas madali, para mas mabilis. Kita agad eh. Sa akin talagang accessible, mas maganda.

Researcher:

Tapos parang mache-check, mati-tick off niyo po na parang okay, address na 'to, 'tong isang 'to...

Environment Participant:

Alam niyo kaagad.

Administration Participant:

Maaano kakaagad, mareresolusyonan. Mas madali. Kasi mahirap naman talagang ano eh, hindi naman natin mababantayan, iilan lang naman ang tao ng barangay para mabantayan ang isang buong barangay, 'di ba?

VAWC Participant:

Ilan ba ang population natin? 24,000?

Administration Participant:

21,000.

Researcher:

Okay lang naman po kung hindi po lahat ay maghsa-share. Basta yung pwedeng i-second or mag-agree po kayo doon sa...Sino pa po ang gustong mag-share po, tungkol po doon sa mapa. Ano po yung take niyo po doon sa mapa bilang , yun nga po, yung pinresent ko po sa inyo. Hepe, kayo po?

Peace and Security Participant:

Ang sa akin naman, sa peace and order, kapag duduty ako na Tanod, automatic 'yan, inaano sa guwardiya yung listahan kung sino ang napasok. Pagdating ng mga bandang 10:00, roving na 'yan. Taliwas sa sinabi nito na hindi raw nagro-roving. Araw-araw 'yan. Ang order sa amin ni Kapitan, kada-kanto, kada-phase, kinukunan ng litrato 'yan. Yung kinukunan ng litrato, para may ebidensiya kami na nagro-roving. 'Yan namang sa aso, 'yan inaano sa City Vet, yung magpapahuli ng aso. Kumbaga, kayo'y may aso, gusto niyo ipahuli, pupunta ka sa barangay, iaano mo. Para mabigyan ng certification na ipahuhuli mo yung aso. Madadala sa City Vet.

2nd QUESTION

Researcher:

Thank you po, sir. Sino pa po ang gusto mag-share po, yung tungkol po sa mapa, bilang decision-maker po sa barangay. Kasi medyo mabigat din po yung responsibilidad niyo po eh. Nagdedesisyon po kayo sa barangay, like, every day, na without you even being, parang, conscious of it, nagde-decide po kayo para sa kalahatan, para sa marami. Ayan po, meron pa pong gustong mag-share po? So kung wala na po, yung second question ko po is: Ano po yung tingin niyo po...parang more or less nasagot na po nung ilan. Ano po yung tingin niyo po sa mga problema/isyu na na-capture po on video? Ano po yung tingin niyo na they were communicated...or 'di ba napansin niyo po, vinideohan po natin sila na parang nakikipag-usap po sila sa inyo. How did it make you feel po? Ano po yung parang...Ano po yung tingin niyo po doon sa mga problema/isyu nila?

Administration Participant:

Ano po, sir, yung about basura kasi, hindi lang naman (name of subdivision) may problema. Actually, Manila...lahat nga halos, lalo na yung mga urban areas talaga, mga city, yun naman talaga problema. Yung basura po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), actually, ang may pananagutan, hindi naman po Barangay, yung CENRO, 'no? Hindi po ano namin 'yan kasi unang-una sila yung may...nakuha niyan. Sa kanilang responsibility 'yan. Sa CENRO, hindi po sa Barangay. Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya 'yan eh. Tulad sa amin, sa Nepomuceno, hindi naman napasok sa amin ang truck. Maliit ang kalye namin, dead-end pa sa dulo. So nakiusap ang CENRO na hindi talaga nila

kakayang pumasok. Ang ano na lang doon, hindi naman kami rin pupuwede na magtambak doon sa pinaka-kanto, nagrereklamo naman yung nandoon. Hindi naman natin mailalabas 'yon. Siyempre, kumbaga, yung kayo, walang basura diyan sa harapan niyo, yung sa harapan niya, may basura. Ayun, kaya lang, nandoon yung disiplina naman ng mga tao doon na kapag nagbusina ang truck, saka lang sila maglalabas. So nagkaroon kami ng pag-uusap doon. Nagkaroon talaga kami ng pag-uusap. Ngayon, 'pag halimbawa, ano na yung truck, napuno, bago pa dumating sa amin, tinatawag naman namin yun, bumabalik naman. Although kasi, minsan talaga, hindi nila nababalikan within this day, or kaya late na, kinabukasan, makukuha naman. Ang problema lang, masyado nang maselan din yung taong naandoon. Pero, ayun, proud naman ako na sa Nepomuceno, nagagawa naman 'yon, na kapag nagbusina na ang truck, at kung kailan lang kukunin yung basura, saka lang sila naglalabas. Ayun naman ang sa akin. Kasi, yun nga, sabi kong lagi, nung kami'y nag-meeting doon, wala namang ibang mag-aalaga nung aming street kundi kami rin. Kasi kami lang din yung maaapektuhan. So yung mga aso doon, kakilala namin kung sino yung nadumi sa kalsada, so kami-kami na rin ang nag-uusap. Sa street namin. Yun yung sinasabi ko lang, sa Nepomuceno. So yun, yun ang ano namin, since lalo na doon sa aming street, mas marami ang apartment kesa homeowners. Ilan lang kaming homeowners talaga. Parang lima, anim lang yata kami, pero puro apartment, napakarami. Oo, so ang malimit ko namang kinakausap doon 'pag may mga problema is yung nagpapaupa. Siyempre mga tenant nila 'yan eh, sila may responsibilidad diyan. So as of now, kung meron mang kaming problema sa basura, nagagawan naman namin ng solusyon. Yun 'yon, sa amin. Problema hindi naman ng Barangay yun eh, problema ng community at saka ng CENRO. Hindi responsibilidad ng Barangay. Sa akin.

Researcher:

Thank you po. Yung sa iba naman po...thank you po, Ma'am, for that. Yung mga iba pa pong nabanggit po na mga grievances kanina like, for example, yung aso, yung mga kabataan. Ano po yung take niyo po...ano po yung naramdaman niyo po as decision-makers, nung narinig niyo po yung mga 'yon. Kasi kanina po nung parang narinig niyo, ah, aso eh ganito naman 'yan, ganito. So ano po yung parang opisyal na saloobin niyo po nung narinig niyo po yung ibang mga reklamo, yung mga kabataang magulo, mga ganoon. Sino po ang gustong mag-share? Sino po? Kayo po?

VAWC Participant:

Okay. Kabataan, okay. Kasi yung kabataan talaga'y diyan talaga'y sumasakit ang ulo ko diyan kasi kapag nagsama-sama 'yang mga 'yan nagce-create talaga 'yan ng gulo eh. Lalo kapag may na-tripan, sorry ang dumaan, sad to say, 'yon. Babatuhin ng bote, sasaktan nila. Eh hindi na...ang alam ko dito sa (inaudible) wala na, 'di ba? Napatanggal na ni Kap 'yan eh, yung mga kabataan na nandiyan eh. Hindi ko lang alam yung ibang sinasabi na...ano bang street 'yon? Yung nakita na may nagru-rugby?

Researcher:

Ah yung sa may ano po, sa may Achilles po, Achilles.

VAWC Participant:

Yung paglabas eh may mga bote-boteng basag. Hindi ko alam yung anong yun eh, ngayon ko lang narinig na may ganoon. Kasi actually kapag may mga ganoon kasi na case, pinapaalam agad sa amin. Thank you naman at nalaman naming yung ganoong sistema. Kaya lang, ang problema, dapat sana may magreklamo. Kapag walang nagreklamo, wala kaming malalaman. Yun lang 'yon. Yun ang problema. May magreklamo, aaksiyunan agad, bakit hindi? Mas maganda, 'di ba?

Researcher:

Thank you po, thank you. So sa kabataan, oo nga naman po, thank you rin po for saying that, na may mga...masasabi niyo po ba na may mga reklamo po talaga sa paligid na hindi niyo po talaga malalaman unless through mga ganitong means, yung ganoon po.

VAWC Participant:

Yes. Hangga't walang nagrereklamo.

Researcher:

Opo. Kayo po? Yung pakiramdam niyo po doon sa mga reklamo po na...yung sa video po kanina? Bale yun na din...doon lang din po naglalaro po eh, basura, kabataan, kaunting aso, tapos yung mga wire po na nakaano sa puno, parking, mga double-parking, lagi pong ganoon.

VAWC Participant:

Yung sa puno kasi sa Meralco yun eh. Ire-request mo yun through CENRO.

3rd QUESTION

Researcher:

Opo. So question number three ko naman po is: Ano po naman yung tingin niyo po... 'di ba, again, babalik po tayo doon sa naging approach po nung mga video po na napanood natin, parang nakikipag-usap sila sa inyo. Para bang walang camera, parang nakatingin sila sa inyo. Ano po yung pakiramdam niyo po nung pinapanood niyo po yung ganoon, na para pong nakikipag-usap sila direktso sa inyo? Bilang barangay decision-makers, nakakarinig po kayo ng...mga constituents niyo po sila kung tatawagin eh. Ano po yung pakiramdam niyo po nung napanood niyo po? Yung ilan po sa inyo: "Ay, si ano 'yon." Yung mga ganoon. So ano po yung pakiramdam niyo po, like officially, nung napanood niyo po na para bang nangungusap yung iba, parang ganoon. I'm just going to put it that way. Ano po yung naramdaman niyo? Kayo po, go ahead po.

Environment Participant:

Parang nagulat lang po kasi alam naman nilang dito ako nagtatrabaho dapat po yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin. Yung halimbawa nga po may ganoon, kagaya niyan, mga kilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako. Eh samantalang lagi akong bumibili sa kanila ng dog food.

Researcher:

Thank you po. Kayo po? Ma'am, kayo po...sir, kayo. Yung kumbaga, ano po yung...kayo po, Ma'am, yung pakiramdam niyo po nung parang nakikipag-usap po sa inyo directly yung mga tao kanina sa video.

VAWC Participant:

Eh siyempre, na-surprise ako, na may ganoon palang scenario. Wala akong alam. Sasabihin ko ba? Ire-record ko 'yon? O siyempre, na-surprise kasi hindi ko naman alam na may mga ganoong scenario palang problema, hindi naman naia-address sa amin. So kung may mga...any concerns, sana pwede namang pumunta ng Barangay para at least nagagawan ng remedy kung ano yung problema. Yun lang 'yon.

Researcher:

Yung ano po, if I may add po, parang additional question lang po, yung parang...nakaramdaman po ba kayo...medyo leading na po yung tanong ko pero parang nakaramdam po ba kayo na parang nakikipag-collaborate sa inyo yung residente, na parang makita niyo po in that light, na parang hindi po sila kumkontra necessarily kundi parang nakikipag-collaborate sila sa inyo via this means. Kasi siyempre, not everyone has the guts na parang pumunta sa Barangay. Yung iba, naghihintay lang na may mapagsabihan na platform na maging available po sa kanila. Ano po yung silip niyo po na parang hindi po sila kumokontra per se kundi nakikipag-collaborate, nakikipag-cooperate sa inyo. Na parang "eto yung reklamo namin, pwede nating solusyonan" bilang pamayanan.

Administration Participant:

Sa akin, sir, yung ganoon, okay, hinahangaan ko naman siyempre, kasi sinasabi nila 'yon. Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay. Alam mo 'yon? Yung nasaan na yung ating bilang magkakapitbahay na yung basura niya, bakit hindi kayo yung mga mag-usap nang mas maayos, kasi mas masosolusyonan nang kayu-kayo lang. Kasi kung lagi niyong dadalihin sa Barangay, kapitbahay mo ireklamo mo dahil sa basura, nasaan na yung anuhan natin ng pagiging magkakapitbahay, 'di ba? Alam mo 'yon? Simpleng problema na kapag dinala niyo pa 'yan sa Barangay, lalaki, magkakaroon pa kayo ng mga gap, eh magkakapitbahay na kayo since mga bata pa kayo. Pwedeng pag-usapan. Advantage saka disadvantage yung mga ganoon kasi nga, oo nagsasabi kayo, pero within sana sa inyo na lang 'yon para mas okay. Kasi magkakapitbahay eh. Iba na kasi kapag ininvolve niyo na yung Barangay. Parang next ano na 'yon, parang away-away na 'yon eh, 'di ba? Parang hindi masyadong...sila na lang muna. Ganoon. Kung hindi na talaga nila kayang masolusyonan, saka lang dapat ipasok yung Barangay. As kawani, ha? Kasi ganoon din ang problema ko, kami muna ang nag-solusyon. Ayon, ganoon yung sa akin.

Researcher:

Thank you po. So kayo po, sir, if I may ask, ano po yung tingin niyo po sa ganoon, parang ano po yung naging reaction niyo po kanina na eto, potentially kakilala niyo po, or pwedeng hindi, na parang nakikipag-usap sa inyo through the camera na "eto yung mga reklamo ko, if kayang masolusyonan, solusyonan niyo bilang nasa Barangay." Ano po yung reaction niyo po kanina nung pinapapanood ko po...kayo po?

Barangay Health Worker Participant 1:

Kasi po yung lahat ng reklamo po nila, lahat po 'yan, ginagawa po ni Kap. Regarding din sa aso, yung pagtatae, inano din 'yan ni Kap. Tapos yung katulad nung nag-ano ng rugby boy, katabi lang po yung...dapat alam po niya 'yon. Tapos yung isa na driver...dapat nire-report din yun kay (name redacted) kasi magkasama sila lagi. Ano po, aware po si Kap doon sa yung naimbestiga niyo. Lahat po, si Kap hindi po nagkukulang. Mahigpit po si Kap. Tapos regarding din po sa...yun nasabi na naman ni hepe na ang tanod namin, sir, 7:00 pa lang po, nagro-roving na po, hanggang 11:00. Yun lang po, sir.

Researcher:

Thank you po. Sino pa po ang gusto pong mag-share po tungkol po sa ganoon? Meron po bang parang natigatig po, if I can use that term, na parang "o si ano 'to ah, talaga, may ganito pala siyang reklamo?" Meron po bang ganoon ang reaction? Kayo po, Ma'am?

Barangay Health Worker Participant 2:

Halimbawa naman po sa isang lugar, kung halimbawa pong may reklamong ganoon, lahat naman po kami dito, hindi lamang po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), marami po, (name of subdivision), (name of subdivision), lahat po may kawani ng Barangay. Kung may concern ka po sa lugar ninyo, pwede kayong lumapit po doon sa kawani para maipaabot niya po kay Kapitan. Maiparating po. Yun naman po 'yon. Eh kung sasarilinin mo na lang po, tapos may nagtanong sa 'yo, saka mo sasabihin, eh parang nakakasira naman sa amin bilang kapitbahay niyo na kawani ng Barangay.

VAWC Participant:

Sa amin po kasi sa (name of sitio), kapag regarding diyan sa basura at hindi na nahahakot agad, eh di aayusin nila. Kapag hindi pa rin, tumatawag ako...meron kasi akong friend na nagtatrabaho sa CENRO. Siya ang tatawagan ko, magpapadala siya ng truck para hakutin yung basura. Yun na lang po ang ginagawa ko.

Administration Participant:

Ganoon naman din. Kahit naman saan ganoon. Kapag hindi na ano, itinatawag sa CENRO. Ganoon yung nagiging proseso namin sa basura.

4th QUESTION**Researcher:**

Thank you po for all of your...so, ano po, second to the last question na po tayo, opo. So ano po, balik po tayo doon sa inexecute po namin na output, yung mapa na may ano. Ano po ang tingin niyo po doon? Kasi 'di ba meron po tayong tinatawag na "grievance redress"/"community problem identification". Yun nga po, may grievance, may reklamo, may daing/problema/isyu, na pwedeng masolusyonan via whatever means, 'di ba po? So ano po yung tingin niyo po doon sa ipinakita ko po sa inyo kanina na mapa na clickable, "interactive" kung tawagin po natin na kapag cinlick po lalabas yung summary nung complaints/mga problema o isyu tapos may video. Ano po yung masasabi niyo doon bilang, possibly, pwedeng ma-adopt na tool/device po dito sa (name of barangay)? Yun lang po. Ano po yung masasabi niyo

po sa kanya bilang tool na pwedeng ma-adopt? Kasi nga po, given na po, napaka-technologically evolving na po ng panahon natin, hindi po tayo pwedeng mag-settle lang po talaga sa pen and paper, like, buong buhay po natin. So ano po yung tingin niyo po sa kanya bilang parang potential grievance redress tool? Na pwede po siyang magamit na makasolusyon po sa mga issue at problema po, hindi lang sa (name of subdivision) po, siyempre. In the long term, buong (name of barangay) po, o, who knows, buong (name of city) po. Ma-adopt ng iba pong mga barangay as best practice...go ahead po. Ano po yung masasabi niyo po sa kanya bilang grievance redress/participatory governance tool?

Administration Participant:

Ayun po, yung sinasabi ko nga po, yung kanina, yung may advantage at disadvantage, kasi nga magkakapitbahay, baka mamaya, makita ng iba, “o ako lang pala yung inaano mo, magkapitbahay lang tayo, hindi tayo nag-usap.” Ganoon. Parang disadvantage, ‘di ba? Pero ang advantage, sana, siguro yung mga concerns na mas malalim. Oo. “O dito sa anong ‘to, laging may inuman...”

Researcher:

Ano po yung example niyo po, bukod po sa inuman, na tingin niyo po maca-classify as “malalim”?

Administration Participant:

Yung ano, yung sa pushers, sa drugs, ‘no? May violence ditong nangyayari, sa pamilya. Sana parang mas malalim na mga ganoon. Kasi ‘di ba yung...kung magiging accessible sa lahat ng ano...kahit ako siguro hindi ako magsasabi na yung

kapitbahay ko, may ganito. 'Di ba? Ayun yung parang isang disadvantage. Although mas maganda sana...pero sana, baka siguro limited lang ang maga-access, hindi public. Kasi baka pagmulan pa ng away ng mga magkakapitbahay.

Researcher:

Parang okay lang po ba if ever, additional question lang, parang kayo po ang may control dito po sa Barangay, kayo po ang parang may hawak nung map, tapos kayo na po yung maglalagay? Parang may idedeploy...ano lang po, idea lang po na I am throwing around, parang may ide-deploy po kayo for example pong tanod, or representative from VAWC, tapos siya po yung magrerecord, tapos i-store na po, parang magiging database.

Administration Participant:

Oo. Parang ganoon, hindi siya public talaga.

Researcher:

Sige nga po, Ma'am, if I may ano po, ano po yung tingin niyo po sa ganoong idea? Thank you po, Ma'am. Go ahead, Ma'am.

VAWC Participant:

Hindi, sa akin, mas good 'yon, para naaano mo yung, naa-analyze mo yung mga problema. May database ka na. Kagaya dito sa amin, may kaso kami na-ano, may database kami na a year, yung comparison, ganoon din sana, mas maganda. Na may database kung ano yung mga nangyayari. Kaya lang, baka naman kahit Maritess eh sasabihin pa, eh wala namang kuwenta. 'Di ba? Minsan kasi, gossip

lang eh, palalakingin na, hindi naman relevant yung reklamo. 'Di ba? Mga ganoon sana.

Researcher:

Go ahead po.

Barangay Health Worker Participant 2:

Ay, ano lang po siguro, yun eh kung, halimbawa, kapag ganoon naman, pwede naman sigurong magsisilbing surveillance na rin po. Para po, halimbawa, mas mabilis nating makukuha kung ano ang concern nila. At makikita rin po natin.

Researcher:

Kasi po, if I may share po, if ever po na, yung nga po, mag-iiwan po ako sa inyo po ng PDF file po nitong mapa that you can use po na hindi po parang ganito na nagta-transition pero you can comment. 'Di ba po sa PDF, mag-iinsert ka po ng comment lang, tapos pwede niyo pong...nandoon yung link sa video. Tapos kapag cinlick niyo po, "ah, eto, meron palang ganitong nangyari, vinideohan ng isa natin sa VAWC, puntahan natin mamaya." Yun po, yung parang ganoon. So additional question lang po before our very last question: Ano po yung tingin niyo sa pag-employ po ng video sa ganito pong grievance redress? Potential na grievance redress. Yung paggamit po ng video. Ano po yung tingin niyo po doon? Yung para pong ipinakita ko po sa inyo.

Administration Participant:

Ang worry ko diyan, sir, yung ating Privacy Act, na baka ma-violate natin. May Data Privacy Act tayo. Baka masagasaan natin. Yun sa akin.

Researcher:

Go ahead po. Advantages and disadvantages po.

VAWC Participant:

Ano naman 'yon, depende kasi sa magvi-video, sa paggagamitan, kasi minsan, may mga magvi-video, ang intention lang is "i-video natin 'to kasi yung nakaupo is kalaban natin." Kasi minsan may political ano diyan eh. 'Di ba? Sana pwede yung hindi siya involved, nasa gitna lang. Walang bias. O 'di ba? Kapag alam mong kalaban, bakit mo iinterviewhin siya? Natural sasabihin sa 'yo niyan, lahat negative. Mas mabuti pang mag-interview ka doon sa wala siyang pakialam sa politics. Kumbaga yung intention niya is i-video niya dahil nakita niya is mali. Yun 'yon, mas gusto ko 'yon.

Researcher:

Sir, kayo?

VAWC Participant:

Ano, hepe, magsalita ka naman, regarding diyan sa video.

Peace and Security Participant:

Lahat ng hinaing diyan, nagawa na natin 'to eh. 'Di ba?

Barangay Health Worker Participant 1:

Matagal na po 'yan, sir, pero lagi po 'yan...kinikilos po kakaagad 'yan ni Kap.

Researcher:

Thank you po. Thank you po for all of your perspectives po with regard...so umuulit po. Nasolusyonan, babalik.

Environment Participant:

Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po 'yan. Hindi po ano si Kap diyan sa yung sinasabi nila.

VAWC Participant:

Kahit ang lupon, ilan ang kaso niyan regarding diyan sa aso? Tae, ihi, magpupunta, magrereklamo.

Peace and Security Participant:

Katulad niyang parking. Yung parking dito sa ano. Itinaboy na namin 'yan. Itinaboy namin, lumipat lang sa kabila. Ganoon lang naman eh. Paikut-ikot.

5th QUESTION**Researcher:**

So thank you po for your honesty po in answering. So eto po, last question ko na po sa inyo: How does it compare, yung ipinakita ko po sa inyo na map with the video, yung same po, yung tanong ko po lagi...how does it compare...paano po siya

nagco-compare sa existing niyo na po na community problem identification and decision-making tools or mechanisms sa (name of barangay) po? Ano po ba yung mga mechanisms niyo po na in place, or tools in place po sa (name of barangay) na masasabi niyo pong ginagamit, and how do they compare po dito sa “geospatial direct-address videos” po na kung tawagin natin. Ano po yung mga in place po. System po.

Administration Participant:

May grievance po kasi tayo, ‘di ba?

Lupon Participant:

Sa amin po, may grievance committee kami na pinatutupad sa bawat lugar. Ngayon, doon po namin pinaalam kung ano yung mga dapat gawin, ano yung mga problema nila. Yun ang sinosolusyonan doon sa grievance. Ngayon ang ano naman ng mga grievance diyan eh yung mga ano ng Homeowners ng bawat subdivision. ‘Yan sila ang ano para hindi na dumating dito ang problema. Doon pa lang, sosolusyonan na nila ‘yan. Kaya lang, meron kayong mga na-interview na ganyan, na may mga reklamo palang ganyan, na hindi naman nakakarating dito. Kaya ang nangyari, parang surprise. Pero sa tinatanong, sasagutin ko na yung tinatanong mo kanina, yung tungkol sa map na sinasabi niyo, sa akin, okay ‘yan, effective ‘yan. Kasi alam mo, identified mo kakaagad kung ano problema ng kapaligiran mo. ‘Di ba? ‘Yon, maganda para sa akin. Okay siya.

Researcher:

Sa grievance committee po na tinutukoy po natin, pakiramdam niyo po ba, parang doable na magamit niyo po siya sa inyo, sa grievance po?

Lupon Participant:

Oo, magagamit talaga, kasi nga maaano mo yung problema nila eh. Tukoy mo agad. Magagawa mo. Mabibigyan mo agad ng aksiyon, kasi nga, at least, mayroon doong mga tao na yung siyang haharap agad, mga committee. Kaya ang problema, naso-solve na agad. Ayun po.

Researcher:

Thank you po, sir, thank you po for your take. Sa huli nagsalita si sir, parang panapos sa discussion, opo. Any final remarks po that you would like to add? Kasi sometimes sa mga ina-add po sa dulo, diyan po lumalabas yung mga meaningful din po talaga na...may mga huli pa po kayong gustong idagdag po sa ating discussion?

Administration Participant:

Yun po, katulad ng laging sinasabi ni (name redacted), lahat po yung problema naman is sinosolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay. Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo. Siyempre po, nandoon pa rin yung...sabi nga, ang Barangay, kapag may nagreklamo, talagang aaksiyunan. Kahit gaano kaliit at kalaking reklamo 'yan, basta may reklamo, aaksiyunan. Pero yun nga po, kalimitan naman ng sinabi is parang, sa akin, in my own opinion, community problem, not Barangay problem. Parang tulung-tulong lang dapat talaga yung ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Suwerte tayo sa (name of barangay), mas marami

tayong subdivision kesa sa ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Siguro yun ang dapat na pinagtutuunan ng Homeowners kasi, siyempre, sila yung leader ng kanilang subdivisions, dapat siguro, kaya nga sila kinuha na ni Kap, yung HOA, para makatulong sa bawat solusyon. Kasi hindi kaya naman talaga ng Barangay lahat na bantayan, iilan lang ang Tanod, gaanong kalaki naman ang ating populasyon. So 'yon, yung problema is parang community problem, not Barangay. Pero yung ganitong pong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda. Huwag lang maging public. Ayun, ganoon lang po yung sa akin. Basta lahat po yun, naa-address naman ng...

Researcher:

So ang tingin niyo po, Ma'am, sorry, additional question, tingin niyo po, magagamit po siya, pero parang sa level niyo po as decision-makers? Dito po lang...nandito yung mapa, hindi po pwedeng mapakialaman ng...

Administration Participant:

Yes, para sa akin, ganoon, oo. Parang baka, yun nga, yung privacy nila, masyadong maaano, magiging talk of the town pa sila ng kanilang mga kapitbahay. Parang baka mag-away. So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang humahawak.

Researcher:

And if ever, Barangay po?

Administration Participant:

Barangay.

Researcher:

Thank you. Sino pa po ang gustong...meron pa po? Ah, go ahead po.

Environment Participant:

Saka kami naman po, sir, dito po sa mga kawani, may malasakit naman po sa bawat ano. Kaya nga po kami nilagay ni Kap bawat isang ano para po may ma-tap doon. Sa amin po, wala pong nagrereklamo, pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.

Researcher:

Thank you po. Anyone else po?

Lupon Participant:

Ang sa akin naman, parang suggestion ko lang, siguro para mabigyan ng tamang solusyon itong mga problemang 'to, tulad ng basurang 'yan, aso, mga rugby boys na 'yan, siguro magkaroon ng public forum.

VAWC Participant:

Nagawa na 'yan ni Kap eh.

Lupon Participant:

Oo nga, magkaroon ng public forum, masabi lahat sa tao kung ano yung mga dapat na solusyonan na ano. Katulad niyan, eto'y kung tutuusin, problema ng bawat

ano 'to eh, tao lang sa kapaligiran natin eh, yung mga rugby boys. Kanino bang anak 'yan? O, 'di ba dapat yung magulang ang mag-ano diyan, mag-suheto sa mga...tapos 'yang mga basura, 'yan naman eh, kung ikaw eh may ano sa sarili mo, may disiplina ka, kaya mo namang linisin 'yan eh, hindi para ikalat mo 'yan sa bang-bang eh. 'Di ba? Kaya siguro, maaaring ulitin uli ang public forum para mabigyan ng...malaman uli nila na mali yung ginagawa nilang 'yan.

Researcher:

Tingin niyo po ba pwedeng gamitin 'yan sa public forum if ever? Tanong lang po, 'yang mapang 'yan, pwedeng i-present po, at least one segment of the public forum? Or baka po...

Lupon Participant:

Baka hindi. Ngayon, siya lang ang mag-ano nito, magsagawa ng schedule.

Researcher:

Tapos magfa-flash pa po yung mga video.

Administration Participant:

Maraming makakakita.

VAWC Participant:

Yung mga kalaban, siyempre, negative lahat ng sasabihin.

Lupon Participant:

Maaari. Ganoon nga.

Environment Participant:

Sa amin, dito po, pwede po 'yan, sir.

Researcher:

Saan?

Environment Participant:

Sa Barangay po.

Researcher:

Okay po. Sa level niyo po yung makakakita. Anything else po? Ayun po, sakto po, more or less, pasok po tayo sa 30 minutes, 36 minutes po yung inabot ng discussion natin. So yun lang po.

APPENDIX B

Letter of Request Addressed to, and Signed by, the President of the Homeowners Association

February 06, 2024

Francisca A. Concepcion

President, Olympia Homeowners Association

A blessed day!

My name is **Ivan Khalil Lijauco Descartin**, a Master of Development Communication student at University of the Philippines – Open University (with student number 2014-93327), and I am writing this letter to humbly request that I be allowed to conduct a series of transect walks around the subdivision. Currently, I am writing my master's thesis, entitled *Digital Transect Map with Direct-Address Videos of Residents as Potential Grievance Redress Tool at Olympia Subdivision, Brgy. Labas, Santa Rosa, Laguna*.

I will be accompanied by Maria Rita Rewady Lijauco, an Olympia Subdivision resident for 50 years who also, at several points, served, as Barangay Labas Secretary. The "walks" will be done three times, first around Zeus Drive, Olympus Circle, and Athena Drive, the second one covering Sparta Drive, Achilles Drive, and Hera Drive, and the last one from Nepomuceno Drive, Poseidon Drive, to Prosepina Drive. The purpose of the "walks" is to create a digital transect map of the subdivision, as well as capture, on video, select Olympia residents expressing some of their complaints/grievances that can then, in turn, be forwarded/presented to select members of the Barangay Council. The videos will then be inputted into the digital transect map.

Hoping for your favorable response. Thank you so much!

Warmly,

Ivan Khalil Lijauco Descartin

UPDU Student (MDC), 2014-93327

Francisca A. Concepcion

President, Olympia Homeowners Association

APPENDIX C

Letter of Request Addressed to, and Signed by, the Barangay Chairman

LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF BATAVIA, LAGUNA
Office of the Barangay Secretary to
Brgy. PUNANG BATAVIA

RECEIVED

By: Rlan
Date: 2/22/24
Time: 2:48 PM

February 22, 2024

Dear Hon. Ronald Ian De Guzman:

Good day! My name is Ivan Khalil Lijauco Descartin, a graduate student taking up the Master of Development Communication (MDC) program at the **University of the Philippines - Open University (UPOU)**. Currently, I am working on my thesis on a *digital transect map with direct-address videos of residents as potential grievance redress tool at Olympia Subdivision, Brgy. Labas, Santa Rosa, Laguna*. I have already previously conducted a series of Focus Group Discussion (FGDs) with some of the personnel of Brgy. Labas before the pandemic, but since there were adjustments made to the paper and the output to be produced, an FGD is once again needed.

In this connection, I am humbly requesting that your good office be able to grant me permission to conduct said FGD with choice barangay personnel about their perceptions on the abovementioned digital transect map with direct-address videos of residents as *potential grievance redress tool*. Specifically, my thesis will be needing the following participants in said discussion (7 total):

- 1 Administration Official *SALLY WATSON*
- 1 Member of the Lupon *Juan D. Poman*
- 1 Barangay Health Worker (BHW) *Janet A. Palagan*
- 1 Barangay Peace and Security Officer (BPSO) *Mery Dicala*
- 1 from Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC) *Juan D. Poman*
- 1 from Culture, Arts, and Tourism *Juan D. Poman*
- 1 from Environment *Juan D. Poman*

I am hoping that your good office will be able to secure a schedule for the discussion, preferably this last week of February or first week of March. Rest assured that the discussion will only last for 25-30 minutes. The choice of personnel to participate, provided we satisfy the minimum number of one (1) representative per department, is respectfully entirely up to you. Looking forward to your reply, as this thesis may be able to, in its own way, assist in *barangay-level policy-making in the long run*.

Thank you very much!

Ivan Khalil Lijauco Descartin
Ivan Khalil Lijauco Descartin

09956679368 | ivan6655321@gmail.com

APPENDIX D

Thematic Analysis of the FGD (Coding Sheets)

Question:			
Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker):			
Participatory Outcomes Tuftte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

QUESTION 1 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Collaboration with Residents (in Grievance Redress)	<i>“Tapos yung sa nagrurugby, wala akong alam doon. Pero dapat, kung may reklamo sila, inform lang nila na sa amin, dadamputin naman, bakit naman hindi? Kasi talagang ayaw na ayaw namin talaga ng rugby kapag regarding diyan.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Residents’ Perceived Lack of Discipline Adherence to Hierarchy (in Grievance Redress)	<i>“Okay, ang masasabi ko dito, kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina, although iniimplement naman ng barangay ‘yan.”</i> <i>“Tapos yung talagang...sa aso,</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

		<p><i>'yan naman talaga'y napag-usapan na eh, ibababa na yung ordinansa niyan eh, na bawal na talagang mag-alpas ng aso. May mga multa-multa na 'yan eh, hindi ko lang alam kailan naiimplement"</i></p> <p><i>"At doon naman sa mga kabataan na kagaya ng sa hawak ko sa VAWC, mag-iimplement na rin kasi kami ng curfew, inaantay na lang din namin ibaba 'yan eh. Kumbaga isang tarpaulin kasi yung batas na ilalagay sa bawat lugar para maintindihan nila."</i></p> <p><i>"At diyan din sa parking, halos pinapatanggal na 'yan eh, kaya lang matitibay din ang mukha kung bakit pagkatapos ipatanggal, ibabalik na naman. O 'di ba?"</i></p>	
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Okay, ang masasabi ko dito, kapag regarding sa basura, talaga namang ang mga tao, walang disiplina, although iniimplement naman ng barangay 'yan. Lalo na si Kap, kumbaga dapat lang naman magtapon sa tamang tapunan. Wala lang talagang disiplina. Tapos yung talagang...sa aso, 'yan naman talaga'y napag-usapan na eh, ibababa na yung ordinansa niyan eh, na bawal na talagang mag-alpas ng aso. May mga multa-multa na 'yan eh, hindi ko lang alam kailan naiimplement. At doon naman sa mga kabataan na kagaya ng sa hawak ko sa VAWC, mag-iimplement na rin kasi kami ng curfew, inaantay na

lang din namin ibaba 'yan eh. Kumbaga isang tarpaulin kasi yung batas na ilalagay sa bawat lugar para maintindihan nila. Yung lahat ng magiging bawal. At diyan din sa parking, halos pinapatanggal na 'yan eh, kaya lang matitibay din ang mukha kung bakit pagkatapos ipatanggal, ibabalik na naman. O 'di ba? Tapos yung sa nagrurugby, wala akong alam doon. Pero dapat, kung may reklamo sila, inform lang nila na sa amin, dadamputin naman, bakit naman hindi? Kasi talagang ayaw na ayaw namin talaga ng rugby kapag regarding diyan. Tapos, ano pa bang problema?

QUESTION 1 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tuftes and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Residents' Perceived Lack of Discipline	<i>“Yon siguro, ang tulong lang doon is yung tao na lang, disiplina lang.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within –

Yung sa mapa, yung binuo niyong mapa, parang halos, kada street, ang problema, sinasabi nila, more on basura. Basura at aso. ‘Yon, ‘yon. Basura at aso, yun lang ‘yon. ‘Yon siguro, ang tulong lang doon is yung tao na lang, disiplina lang. Kapag tayo naman ay marunong makiramdam, alaga mong aso ‘yan eh. Kapag alam mong nakakaperwisyo ka, ikaw na mismo sa sarili mo, ‘di ba?

QUESTION 1 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<p><i>“Sa akin effective talaga, mas maganda siya, kasi kahit ako, minsan nag-Google Map ako eh.”</i></p> <p><i>“Parang mas okay siya lalo na kung iiimplement sa mga barangay.”</i></p> <p><i>“Parang mas okay siya kung magiging apps natin siya”.</i></p> <p><i>“Oo, dapat meron, para mas madali, para mas mabilis. Kita agad eh. Sa akin talagang accessible, mas maganda.”</i></p>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

<p style="text-align: center;">NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S</p>			<p>Power Over -</p> <p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within –</p>
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Hindi, ang parang pinaka-tanong yata ni sir is about map, kung gaano siya ka-effective. Sa akin effective talaga, mas maganda siya, kasi kahit ako, minsan nag-Google Map ako eh. Parang mas okay siya lalo na kung iimplement sa mga barangay. Parang mas okay siya kung magiging apps natin siya. Oo, parang ayun naman yung pinakatanong. Oo, dapat meron, para mas madali, para mas mabilis. Kita agad eh. Sa akin talagang accessible, mas maganda.

QUESTION 1 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Environment

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Alam niyo kaagad.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Alam niyo kaagad.

QUESTION 1 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Maaano kakaagad, mareresolusyonan.”</i> <i>“Mas madali.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

Maaano kakaagad, mareresolusyonan. Mas madali. Kasi mahirap naman talagang ano eh, hindi naman natin mababantayan, iilan lang naman ang tao ng barangay para mabantayan ang isang buong barangay, ‘di ba?

QUESTION 1 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos? How did it make you feel as a barangay-decision maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Peace and Security

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	“Pagdating nang mga bandang 10:00, roving na ‘yan. Taliwas sa sinabi nito na hindi raw nagro-roving. Araw-araw ‘yan.” “Ang order sa amin ni Kapitan, kada-kanto, kada-phase, kinukunan ng litrato ‘yan. Yung kinukunan ng litrato, para may ebidensiya kami na nagro-roving.” “Kumbaga, kayo’y	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within -

		<p><i>may aso, gusto niyo ipahuli, pupunta ka sa barangay, iaano mo. Para mabigyan ng certification na ipahuhuli mo yung aso. Madadala sa City Vet.”</i></p>	
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*Ang sa akin naman, sa peace and order, kapag duduty ako na Tanod, automatic ‘yan, inaano sa guwardiya yung listahan kung sino ang napasok. **Pagdating ng mga bandang 10:00, roving na ‘yan. Taliwas sa sinabi nito na hindi raw nagro-roving. Araw-araw ‘yan. Ang order sa amin ni Kapitan, kada-kanto, kada-phase, kinukunan ng litrato ‘yan. Yung kinukunan ng litrato, para may ebidensiya kami na nagro-roving. ‘Yan namang sa aso, ‘yan inaano sa City Vet, yung magpapahuli ng aso. Kumbaga, kayo’y may aso, gusto niyo ipahuli, pupunta ka sa barangay, iaano mo. Para mabigyan ng certification na ipahuhuli mo yung aso. Madadala sa City Vet.***

QUESTION 2 (Insight): What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

<p>Participatory Outcomes Tuftte and Mefalopulos (2009)</p>	<p>Themes</p>	<p>Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)</p>	<p>Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)</p>
<p>Feelings of Ownership – psychosocial outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it</p>	<p>Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)</p>	<p><i>“Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya ‘yan eh.”</i> (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</p> <p><i>“Ayun naman ang sa akin. Kasi, yun nga, sabi kong lagi, nung kami’y nag-meeting doon, wala namang ibang mag-aalaga nung aming street kundi kami rin. Kasi kami lang din yung maaapektuhan.”</i> (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</p> <p><i>“So yung mga aso doon, kakilala namin kung sino yung nadumi sa kalsada, so kami-kami na rin ang nag-uusap. Sa street namin.”</i> (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</p> <p><i>“So yun, yun ang ano namin, since</i></p>	<p>Power Over - X</p> <p>Power With - X</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within - X</p>

		<p><i>lalo na doon sa aming street, mas marami ang apartment kesa homeowners. Ilan lang kaming homeowners talaga. Parang lima, anim lang yata kami, pero puro apartment, napakarami. Oo, so ang malimit ko namang kinakausap doon 'pag may mga problema is yung nagpapaupa. Siyempre mga tenant nila 'yan eh, sila may responsibilidad diyan.” (POWER OVER AND POWER WITH)</i></p> <p><i>“So as of now, kung meron mang kaming problema sa basura, nagagawan naman namin ng solusyon. Yun 'yon, sa amin.” (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</i></p>	
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community	<i>“Problema hindi naman ng Barangay yun eh, problema ng community at saka</i>	Power Over - X Power With -

ANSWER/S	Problems/Issues)	<p><i>ng CENRO. Hindi responsibilidad ng Barangay. Sa akin.”</i></p> <p><i>“Yung basura po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), actually, ang may pananagutan, hindi naman po Barangay, yung CENRO, ‘no? Hindi po ano namin ‘yan kasi unang-una sila yung may...nakuha niyan. Sa kanilang responsibility ‘yan. Sa CENRO, hindi po sa Barangay.”</i></p>	<p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within –</p>
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*Ano po, sir, yung about basura kasi, hindi lang naman (name of subdivision) may problema. Actually, Manila...lahat nga halos, lalo na yung mga urban areas talaga, mga city, yun naman talaga problema. **Yung basura po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), actually, ang may pananagutan, hindi naman po Barangay, yung CENRO, ‘no? Hindi po ano namin ‘yan kasi unang-una sila yung may...nakuha niyan. Sa kanilang responsibility ‘yan. Sa CENRO, hindi po sa Barangay. Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya ‘yan eh. Tulad sa amin, sa Nepomuceno, hindi naman napasok sa amin ang truck. Maliit ang kalye namin, dead-end pa sa dulo. So nakiusap ang CENRO na hindi talaga nila kakayaning pumasok. Ang ano na lang doon, hindi naman kami rin pupuwede na magtambak doon sa pinaka-kanto, nagrereklamo naman yung nandoon. Hindi naman natin mailalabas ‘yon. Siyempre, kumbaga, yung kayo, walang basura diyan sa harapan niyo, yung sa harapan niya, may***

basura. Ayun, kaya lang, nandoon yung disiplina naman ng mga tao doon na kapag nagbusina ang truck, saka lang sila maglalabas. So nagkaroon kami ng pag-uusap doon. Nagkaroon talaga kami ng pag-uusap. Ngayon, 'pag halimbawa, ano na yung truck, napuno, bago pa dumating sa amin, tinatawag naman namin yun, bumabalik naman. Although kasi, minsan talaga, hindi nila nababalikan within this day, or kaya late na, kinabukasan, makukuha naman. Ang problema lang, masyado nang maselan din yung taong naandoon. **Although, para sa akin, ang may ano kasi talaga diyan, yung komunidad na, hindi na Barangay, or Kapitan, or kawani, or ano pa. Kasi community niya 'yan eh. Ayun naman ang sa akin. Kasi, yun nga, sabi kong lagi, nung kami'y nag-meeting doon, wala namang ibang mag-aalaga nung aming street kundi kami rin. Kasi kami lang din yung maaapektuhan. So yung mga aso doon, kakilala namin kung sino yung nadumi sa kalsada, so kami-kami na rin ang nag-uusap. Sa street namin. Yun yung sinasabi ko lang, sa Nepomuceno. So yun, yun ang ano namin, since lalo na doon sa aming street, mas marami ang apartment kesa homeowners. Ilan lang kaming homeowners talaga. Parang lima, anim lang yata kami, pero puro apartment, napakarami. Oo, so ang malimit ko namang kinakausap doon 'pag may mga problema is yung nagpapaupa. Siyempre mga tenant nila 'yan eh, sila may responsibilidad diyan. So as of now, kung meron mang kaming problema sa basura, nagagawan naman namin ng solusyon. Yun 'yon, sa amin. Problema hindi naman ng Barangay yun eh, problema ng community at saka ng CENRO. Hindi responsibilidad ng Barangay. Sa akin.**

QUESTION 2 (Insight 1): What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Eh hindi na...ang alam ko dito sa (inaudible) wala na, ‘di ba? Napatanggal na ni Kap ‘yan eh, yung mga kabataan na nandiyan eh.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Okay. Kabataan, okay. Kasi yung kabataan talaga’y diyan talaga’y sumasakit ang ulo ko diyan kasi kapag nagsama-sama ‘yang mga ‘yan nagce-create talaga ‘yan ng gulo eh. Lalo kapag may na-tripan, sorry ang dumaan, sad to say, ‘yon.

Babatuhin ng bote, sasaktan nila. Eh hindi na...ang alam ko dito sa (inaudible) wala na, 'di ba? Napatanggal na ni Kap 'yan eh, yung mga kabataan na nandiyan eh. Hindi ko lang alam yung ibang sinasabi na...ano bang street 'yon? Yung nakita na may nagru-rugby?

QUESTION 2 (Insight 2): What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Kaya lang, ang problema, dapat sana may magreklamo. Kapag walang nagreklamo, wala kaming malalaman. Yun lang ‘yon. Yun ang problema. May magreklamo, aaksiyunan agad, bakit hindi? Mas maganda, ‘di ba?”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Hindi ko alam yung anong yun eh, ngayon ko lang narinig na may ganoon. Kasi actually kapag may mga ganoon kasi na case, pinapaalam agad sa amin. Thank you naman at nalaman naming yung ganoong sistema.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
			Power Over -

<p style="text-align: center;">NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S</p>			<p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within –</p>
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*Yung paglabas eh may mga bote-boteng basag. **Hindi ko alam yung anong yun eh, ngayon ko lang narinig na may ganoon. Kasi actually kapag may mga ganoon kasi na case, pinapaalam agad sa amin. Thank you naman at nalaman naming yung ganoong sistema. Kaya lang, ang problema, dapat sana may magreklamo. Kapag walang nagreklamo, wala kaming malalaman. Yun lang ‘yon. Yun ang problema. May magreklamo, aaksiyunan agad, bakit hindi? Mas maganda, ‘di ba?***

QUESTION 2 (Insight 3): What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Yes. Hangga’t walang nagrereklamo.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Yes. Hangga’t walang nagrereklamo.

QUESTION 2 (Insight 4): What do you think of the community problems/issues captured/communicated in the geospatial direct-address videos of select residents of the subdivision?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>Yung sa puno kasi sa Meralco yun eh. Ire-request mo yun through CENRO.</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Yung sa puno kasi sa Meralco yun eh. Ire-request mo yun through CENRO.

QUESTION 3 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Environment

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community	Residents’ Perceived Lack of Initiative to Report Community Problems/Issues Directly to the Barangay Decision-Makers	<p><i>“Parang nagulat lang po kasi alam naman nilang dito ako nagtatrabaho dapat po yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin.”</i></p> <p><i>“Yung halimbawa nga po may ganoon, kagaya niyan, mga kilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako.”</i></p>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –

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Parang nagulat lang po kasi alam naman nilang dito ako nagtatrabaho dapat po yung mga concern nila, dapat sabihin po nila sa akin. Yung halimbawa nga po may ganoon, kagaya niyan, mga kilala ko po, nakikita naman po nila ako. Eh samantalang lagi akong bumibili sa kanila ng dog food.

QUESTION 3 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“So kung may mga...any concerns, sana pwede namang pumunta ng Barangay para at least nagagawan ng remedy kung ano yung problema. Yun lang ‘yon.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Barangay Decision-Makers Being Made Aware of Community Problems/Issues Previously Unknown to Them	<i>“Eh siyempre, na-surprise ako, na may ganoon palang scenario. Wala akong alam.”</i> (POWER WITH AND POWER TO) <i>“O siyempre, na-surprise kasi hindi ko naman alam na may mga ganoong scenario palang problema, hindi naman naia-address sa amin.”</i> (POWER WITH AND POWER TO)	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

<p style="text-align: center;">NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S</p>			<p>Power Over -</p> <p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within –</p>
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Eh siyempre, na-surprise ako, na may ganoon palang scenario. Wala akong alam. Sasabihin ko ba? Ire-record ko 'yon? O siyempre, na-surprise kasi hindi ko naman alam na may mga ganoong scenario palang problema, hindi naman naia-address sa amin. So kung may mga...any concerns, sana pwede namang pumunta ng Barangay para at least nagagawan ng remedy kung ano yung problema. Yun lang 'yon.

QUESTION 3 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

<p>Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)</p>	<p>Themes</p>	<p>Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)</p>	<p>Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)</p>
<p>Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it</p>	<p>Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)</p>	<p><i>“Kung hindi na talaga nila kayang masolusyonan, saka lang dapat ipasok yung Barangay.”</i></p> <p><i>“Kasi ganoon din ang problema ko, kami muna ang nag-solusyon.”</i></p> <p><i>“Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay. Alam mo ‘yon? Yung nasaan na yung ating bilang magkakapitbahay na yung basura niya, bakit hindi kayo yung mga mag-usap nang mas maayos, kasi mas masosolusyonan nang kayu-kayo lang.”</i></p> <p><i>“Kasi kung lagi niyong dadalihin sa Barangay, kapitbahay mo irereklamo mo dahil sa basura, nasaan na yung anuhan natin ng pagiging magkakapitbahay, ‘di ba? Alam mo ‘yon? Simpleng problema na kapag</i></p>	<p>Power Over -</p> <p>Power With - X</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within – X</p>

		<p><i>dinala niyo pa ‘yan sa Barangay, lalaki, magkakaroon pa kayo ng mga gap, eh magkakapitbahay na kayo since mga bata pa kayo. Pwedeng pag-usapan.”</i></p> <p><i>Advantage saka disadvantage yung mga ganoon kasi nga, oo nagsasabi kayo, pero within sana sa inyo na lang ‘yon para mas okay. Kasi magkakapitbahay eh. Iba na kasi kapag ininvolve niyo na yung Barangay.”</i></p>	
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Appreciation of Residents’ Initiative to Participate in the Study	<p><i>“Sa akin, sir, yung ganoon, okay, hinahangaan ko naman siyempre, kasi sinasabi nila ‘yon.”</i></p>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within –

Sa akin, sir, yung ganoon, okay, hinahangaan ko naman siyempre, kasi sinasabi nila ‘yon. Pero nandoon yung ano ko na kasi kayo yung

magkakapitbahay, so bakit kailangan niyong dalahin pa sa Barangay. Alam mo 'yon? Yung nasaan na yung ating bilang magkakapitbahay na yung basura niya, bakit hindi kayo yung mga mag-usap nang mas maayos, kasi mas masosolusyonan nang kayu-kayo lang. Kasi kung lagi niyong dadalihin sa Barangay, kapitbahay mo irereklamo mo dahil sa basura, nasaan na yung anuhan natin ng pagiging magkakapitbahay, 'di ba? Alam mo 'yon? Simpleng problema na kapag dinala niyo pa 'yan sa Barangay, lalaki, magkakaroon pa kayo ng mga gap, eh magkakapitbahay na kayo since mga bata pa kayo. Pwedeng pag-usapan. Advantage saka disadvantage yung mga ganoon kasi nga, oo nagsasabi kayo, pero within sana sa inyo na lang 'yon para mas okay. Kasi magkakapitbahay eh. Iba na kasi kapag ininvolve niyo na yung Barangay. Parang next ano na 'yon, parang away-away na 'yon eh, 'di ba? Parang hindi masyadong...sila na lang muna. Ganoon. Kung hindi na talaga nila kayang masolusyonan, saka lang dapat ipasok yung Barangay. As kawani, ha? Kasi ganoon din ang problema ko, kami muna ang nag-solusyon. Ayon, ganoon yung sa akin.

QUESTION 3 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Barangay Health Worker 1

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	<p><i>“Tapos yung katulad nung nag-ano ng rugby boy, katabi lang po yung...dapat alam po niya ‘yon.”</i></p> <p><i>“Tapos yung isa na driver...dapat nire-report din yun kay (name redacted) kasi magkasama sila lagi.”</i></p>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within – X
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation	<p><i>“Kasi po yung lahat ng reklamo po nila, lahat po ‘yan, ginagawa po ni Kap. Regarding din sa aso, yung pagtatae, inano din ‘yan ni Kap.”</i> (POWER OVER</p>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within – X

		<p>AND POWER WITHIN)</p> <p><i>“Ano po, aware po si Kap doon sa yung naimbestiga niyo. Lahat po, si Kap hindi po nagkukulang. Mahigpit po si Kap.”</i></p> <p>(POWER OVER AND POWER WITHIN)</p> <p><i>“Tapos regarding din po sa...yun nasabi na naman ni hepe na ang tanod namin, sir, 7:00 pa lang po, nagro-roving na po, hanggang 11:00.”</i></p> <p>(POWER OVER AND POWER WITHIN)</p>	
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Kasi po yung lahat ng reklamo po nila, lahat po ‘yan, ginagawa po ni Kap. Regarding din sa aso, yung pagtatae, inano din ‘yan ni Kap. Tapos yung katulad nung nag-ano ng rugby boy, katabi lang po yung...dapat alam po niya ‘yon. Tapos yung isa na driver...dapat nire-report din yun kay (name redacted) kasi magkasama sila lagi. Ano po, aware po si Kap doon sa yung naimbestiga niyo. Lahat po, si Kap hindi po nagkukulang. Mahigpit po si Kap. Tapos regarding din po sa...yun nasabi na naman ni hepe na ang tanod namin, sir, 7:00 pa lang po, nagro-roving na po, hanggang 11:00. Yun lang po, sir.

QUESTION 3 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Barangay Health Worker 2

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Halimbawa naman po sa isang lugar, kung halimbawa pong may reklamong ganoon, lahat naman po kami dito, hindi lamang po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), marami po, name of</i>	Power Over - X Power With - X Power To - Power Within - X

		<p>subdivision), (name of subdivision), lahat po may kawani ng Barangay. Kung may concern ka po sa lugar ninyo, pwede kayong lumapit po doon sa kawani para maipaabot niya po kay Kapitan. Maiparating po.”</p> <p>(POWER OVER AND POWER WITH)</p> <p>“Eh kung sasarilinin mo na lang po, tapos may nagtanong sa ‘yo, saka mo sasabihin, eh parang nakakasira naman sa amin bilang kapitbahay niyo na kawani ng Barangay.”</p> <p>(POWER OVER AND POWER WITHIN)</p>	
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Halimbawa naman po sa isang lugar, kung halimbawa pong may reklamong ganoon, lahat naman po kami dito, hindi lamang po sa (name of subdivision), sa (name of barangay), marami po, (name of subdivision), (name of subdivision), lahat po may kawani ng Barangay. Kung may concern ka po sa lugar ninyo, pwede kayong lumapit po doon sa kawani para maipaabot niya po kay Kapitan. Maiparating po. Yun naman po ‘yon. Eh kung sasarilinin mo na lang po, tapos may nagtanong sa ‘yo, saka mo sasabihin, eh parang nakakasira naman sa amin bilang kapitbahay niyo na kawani ng Barangay.

QUESTION 3 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	<i>“Sa amin po kasi sa (name of sitio), kapag regarding diyang sa basura at hindi na nahahakot agad, eh di aayusin nila.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within - X
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community	Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Acquaintances	<i>“Kapag hindi pa rin, tumatawag ako...meron kasi akong friend na nagtatrabaho sa CENRO. Siya ang tatawagan ko, magpapadala siya ng truck para hakutin yung basura. Yun na lang po ang ginagawa ko.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To -

			Power Within -
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Sa amin po kasi sa (name of sitio), kapag regarding diyan sa basura at hindi na nahahakot agad, eh di aayusin nila. Kapag hindi pa rin, tumatawag ako...meron kasi akong friend na nagtatrabaho sa CENRO. Siya ang tatawagan ko, magpapadala siya ng truck para hakutin yung basura. Yun na lang po ang ginagawa ko.

QUESTION 3 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial as well as direct-address approach of the videos (i.e. the residents speaking directly to the camera/you)? How did they make you feel as a barangay decision-maker?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Ganoon naman din. Kahit naman saan ganoon. Kapag hindi na ano, itinatawag sa CENRO. Ganoon yung nagiging proseso namin sa basura.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within -

***Ganoon naman din. Kahit naman saan ganoon. Kapag hindi na ano,
itinatawag sa CENRO. Ganoon yung nagiging proseso namin sa basura.***

QUESTION 4 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Community-Level Collaboration (Outside of Barangay Council)	<i>“Ayun po, yung sinasabi ko nga po, yung kanina, yung may advantage at disadvantage, kasi nga magkakatipbahay, baka mamaya, makita ng iba, “o ako lang pala yung inaano mo, magkakatipbahay lang tayo, hindi tayo nag-usap.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Pero ang advantage, sana, siguro yung mga concerns na mas malalim.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Ayun po, yung sinasabi ko nga po, yung kanina, yung may advantage at disadvantage, kasi nga magkakapitbahay, baka mamaya, makita ng iba, “o ako lang pala yung inaano mo, magkapitbahay lang tayo, hindi tayo nag-usap.” Ganoon. Parang disadvantage, ‘di ba? Pero ang advantage, sana, siguro yung mga concerns na mas malalim. Oo. “O dito sa anong ‘to, laging may inuman...”

QUESTION 4 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers) Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling	<i>“Yung ano, yung sa pushers, sa drugs, ‘no? May violence ditong nangyayari, sa pamilya. Sana parang mas malalim na mga ganoon. Kasi ‘di ba yung...kung magiging accessible sa lahat ng ano...kahit ako siguro hindi ako magsasabi na yung kapitbahay ko, may ganito. ‘Di ba?”</i> <i>“Although mas maganda sana...pero</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

	Community Problems/Issues)	<i>sana, baka siguro limited lang ang maga-access, hindi public. Kasi baka pagmulan pa ng away ng mga magkakapitbahay.”</i>	
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Yung ano, yung sa pushers, sa drugs, ‘no? May violence ditong nangyayari, sa pamilya. Sana parang mas malalim na mga ganoon. Kasi ‘di ba yung...kung magiging accessible sa lahat ng ano...kahit ako siguro hindi ako magsasabi na yung kapitbahay ko, may ganito. ‘Di ba? Ayun yung parang isang disadvantage. Although mas maganda sana...pero sana, baka siguro limited lang ang maga-access, hindi public. Kasi baka pagmulan pa ng away ng mga magkakapitbahay.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 3): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Oo. Parang ganoon, hindi siya public talaga.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Oo. Parang ganoon, hindi siya public talaga.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Hindi, sa akin, mas good ‘yon, para naaano mo yung, naa-analyze mo yung mga problema. May database ka na. Kagaya dito sa amin, may kaso kami na-ano, may database kami na a year, yung comparison, ganoon din sana, mas maganda. Na may database kung ano yung mga nangyayari.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Recommendation on the Types of Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Kaya lang, baka naman kahit Maritess eh sasabihin pa, eh wala namang kuwenta. ‘Di ba? Minsan kasi, gossip lang eh, palalakin na, hindi naman</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within -

		<i>relevant yung reklamo. 'Di ba? Mga ganoon sana."</i>	
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Hindi, sa akin, mas good 'yon, para naaano mo yung, naa-analyze mo yung mga problema. May database ka na. Kagaya dito sa amin, may kaso kami na-ano, may database kami na a year, yung comparison, ganoon din sana, mas maganda. Na may database kung ano yung mga nangyayari. Kaya lang, baka naman kahit Maritess eh sasabihin pa, eh wala namang kuwenta. 'Di ba? Minsan kasi, gossip lang eh, palalakingin na, hindi naman relevant yung reklamo. 'Di ba? Mga ganoon sana.

QUESTION 4 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Barangay Health Worker 2

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Ay, ano lang po siguro, yun eh kung, halimbawa, kapag ganoon naman, pwede naman sigurong magsisilbing surveillance na rin po. Para po, halimbawa, mas mabilis nating makukuha kung ano ang concern nila. At makikita rin po natin.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Ay, ano lang po siguro, yun eh kung, halimbawa, kapag ganoon naman, pwede naman sigurong magsisilbing surveillance na rin po. Para po, halimbawa, mas mabilis nating makukuha kung ano ang concern nila. At makikita rin po natin.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 4): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Ang worry ko diyan, sir, yung ating Privacy Act, na baka ma-violate natin. May Data Privacy Act tayo. Baka masagasaan natin. Yun sa akin.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Ang worry ko diyan, sir, yung ating Privacy Act, na baka ma-violate natin. May Data Privacy Act tayo. Baka masagasaan natin. Yun sa akin.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Recommendation on the Types of Citizens Who Are Allowed to Communicate Community Problems/Issues	<p><i>“Ano naman ‘yon, depende kasi sa magvi-video, sa paggamitan, kasi minsan, may mga magvi-video, ang intention lang is ‘i-video natin ‘to kasi yung nakaupo is kalaban natin.” Kasi minsan may political ano diyan eh. ‘Di ba?”</i></p> <p><i>“Sana pwede yung hindi siya involved, nasa gitna lang.</i></p>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

		<p>Walang bias. O 'di ba? Kapag alam mong kalaban, bakit mo iinterviewhin siya? Natural sasabihin sa 'yo niyan, lahat negative. Mas mabuti pang mag-interview ka doon sa wala siyang pakialam sa politics. Kumbaga yung intention niya is i-video niya dahil nakita niya is mali. Yun 'yon, mas gusto ko 'yon."</p>	
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Ano naman 'yon, depende kasi sa magvi-video, sa paggagamitan, kasi minsan, may mga magvi-video, ang intention lang is "i-video natin 'to kasi yung nakaupo is kalaban natin." Kasi minsan may political ano diyan eh. 'Di ba? Sana pwede yung hindi siya involved, nasa gitna lang. Walang bias. O 'di ba? Kapag alam mong kalaban, bakit mo iinterviewhin siya? Natural sasabihin sa 'yo niyan, lahat negative. Mas mabuti pang mag-interview ka doon sa wala siyang pakialam sa politics. Kumbaga yung intention niya is i-video niya dahil nakita niya is mali. Yun 'yon, mas gusto ko 'yon.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 1): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Peace and Security

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Lahat ng hinaing diyari, nagawa na natin ‘to eh. ‘Di ba?”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X

Lahat ng hinaing diyan, nagawa na natin 'to eh. 'Di ba?

QUESTION 4 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Barangay Health Worker 1

Participatory Outcomes Tuftte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Matagal na po ‘yan, sir, pero lagi po ‘yan...kinikilos po kakaagad ‘yan ni Kap.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X

Matagal na po 'yan, sir, pero lagi po 'yan...kinikilos po kakaagad 'yan ni

Kap.

QUESTION 4 (Insight): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Environment

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po ‘yan. Hindi po ano si Kap diyang sa yung sinasabi nila.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X

Pero ginagawaan po talaga ng paraan po 'yan. Hindi po ano si Kap diyan sa yung sinasabi nila.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 3): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Kahit ang lupon, ilan ang kaso niyan regarding diyan sa aso? Tae, ihi, magpupunta, magrereklamo.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X

Kahit ang lupon, ilan ang kaso niyan regarding diyan sa aso? Tae, ihi, magpupunta, magrereklamo.

QUESTION 4 (Insight 2): What do you think of the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device for community problem identification and decision-making?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Peace and Security

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Katulad niyang parking. Yung parking dito sa ano. Itinaboy na namin ‘yan. Itinaboy namin, lumipat lang sa kabila. Ganoon lang naman eh. Paikut-ikot.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X

Katulad niyang parking. Yung parking dito sa ano. Itinaboy na namin 'yan. Itinaboy namin, lumipat lang sa kabila. Ganoon lang naman eh. Paikut-ikot.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 1): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Lupon

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<p><i>“Kaya lang, meron kayong mga na-interview na ganyan, na may mga reklamo palang ganyan, na hindi naman nakakarating dito. Kaya ang nangyari, parang surprise.”</i> (POWER WITH)</p> <p><i>“Pero sa tinatanong, sasagutin ko na yung tinatanong mo kanina, yung tungkol sa map na sinasabi niyo, sa akin, okay ‘yan, effective ‘yan. Kasi alam mo, identified mo kakaagad kung ano problema ng kapaligiran mo. ‘Di ba? ‘Yon, maganda para sa akin. Okay siya.”</i> (POWER TO)</p>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To -

			Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<p><i>“Sa amin po, may grievance committee kami na pinatutupad sa bawat lugar. Ngayon, doon po namin pinaalam kung ano yung mga dapat gawin, ano yung mga problema nila. Yun ang sinosolusyonan doon sa grievance.”</i></p> <p><i>“Ngayon ang ano naman ng mga grievance diyan eh yung mga ano ng Homeowners ng bawat subdivision. ‘Yan sila ang ano para hindi na dumating dito ang problema. Doon pa lang, sosolusyonan na nila ‘yan.”</i></p>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Sa amin po, may grievance committee kami na pinatutupad sa bawat lugar. Ngayon, doon po namin pinaalam kung ano yung mga dapat gawin, ano yung mga problema nila. Yun ang sinosolusyonan doon sa grievance. Ngayon ang ano naman ng mga grievance diyan eh yung mga ano ng Homeowners ng bawat subdivision. ‘Yan sila ang ano para hindi na dumating dito ang problema. Doon pa lang, sosolusyonan na nila ‘yan. Kaya lang, meron kayong mga na-interview na ganyan, na may mga reklamo palang ganyan, na hindi naman nakakarating dito. Kaya ang nangyari, parang surprise. Pero sa tinatanong, sasagutin ko na yung tinatanong mo kanina, yung tungkol sa map na sinasabi niyo, sa akin, okay ‘yan, effective ‘yan. Kasi alam mo, identified mo kakaagad kung ano problema ng kapaligiran mo. ‘Di ba? ‘Yon, maganda para sa akin. Okay siya.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 2): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Lupon

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem	Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Oo, magagamit talaga, kasi nga maaano mo yung problema nila eh. Tukoy mo agad. Magagawa mo. Mabibigyan mo agad ng aksiyon, kasi nga, at least, mayroon doong mga tao na yung siyang haharap agad, mga committee. Kaya ang problema, naso-solve na agad. Ayun po.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - Power To - X Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To -

			Power Within –
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Oo, magagamit talaga, kasi nga maaano mo yung problema nila eh. Tukoy mo agad. Magagawa mo. Mabibigyan mo agad ng aksiyon, kasi nga, at least, mayroon doong mga tao na yung siyang haharap agad, mga committee. Kaya ang problema, naso-solve na agad. Ayun po.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 1): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

<p>Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)</p>	<p>Themes</p>	<p>Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)</p>	<p>Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)</p>
<p>Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it</p>	<p>Collaboration with Residents (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)</p>	<p><i>“Siyempre po, nandoon pa rin yung...sabi nga, ang Barangay, kapag may nagreklamo, talagang aaksiyunan. Kahit gaano kaliit at kalaking reklamo ‘yan, basta may reklamo, aaksiyunan.” (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</i></p> <p><i>“Pero yun nga po, kalimitan naman ng sinabi is parang, sa akin, in my own opinion, community problem, not Barangay problem. Parang tulong-tulong lang dapat talaga yung ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners”. (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</i></p> <p><i>“Kasi hindi kaya naman talaga ng Barangay lahat na bantayan, iilan lang ang Tanod, gaanong kalaki naman ang ating populasyon. So ‘yon, yung problema is parang community problem, not Barangay.” (POWER WITH AND POWER WITHIN)</i></p>	<p>Power Over -</p> <p>Power With - X</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within - X</p>

<p>Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem</p>	<p>Perceived Benefits of the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos in Tackling Community Problems/Issues</p> <p>Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers)</p> <p>Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)</p>	<p><i>“Pero yung ganitong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda. (POWER TO) Huwag lang maging public. (POWER OVER)”</i></p>	<p>Power Over - X</p> <p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To - X</p> <p>Power Within -</p>
<p>Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community</p>			<p>Power Over -</p> <p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within -</p>
<p>NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S</p>	<p>Assertion of Barangay Implementation</p> <p>Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)</p>	<p><i>“Yun po, katulad ng laging sinasabi ni (name redacted), lahat po yung problema naman is sinosolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay. Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo.” (POWER OVER AND POWER WITHIN)</i></p> <p><i>“Suwerte tayo sa (name of barangay), mas marami tayong subdivision kesa sa ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Siguro yun ang dapat na</i></p>	<p>Power Over - X</p> <p>Power With -</p> <p>Power To -</p> <p>Power Within - X</p>

		<p><i>pinagtutuunan ng Homeowners kasi, siyempre, sila yung leader ng kanilang subdivisions, dapat siguro, kaya nga sila kinuha na ni Kap, yung HOA, para makatulong sa bawat solusyon.” (POWER OVER)</i></p>	
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Yun po, katulad ng laging sinasabi ni (name redacted), lahat po yung problema naman is sinosolusyonan na naman ng ating Kapitan at ng sanggunian po ng Barangay. Kaya lang po, paulit-ulit naman. Paulit-ulit po yung problema. Iyon at iyon pa rin ang kanilang mga inirereklamo. Siyempre po, nandoon pa rin yung...sabi nga, ang Barangay, kapag may nagreklamo, talagang aaksiyunan. Kahit gaano kaliit at kalaking reklamo ‘yan, basta may reklamo, aaksiyunan. Pero yun nga po, kalimitan naman ng sinabi is parang, sa akin, in my own opinion, community problem, not Barangay problem. Parang tulung-tulong lang dapat talaga yung ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Suwerte tayo sa (name of barangay), mas marami tayong subdivision kesa sa ano. Kaya nga may Homeowners. Siguro yun ang dapat na pinagtutuunan ng Homeowners kasi, siyempre, sila yung leader ng kanilang subdivisions, dapat siguro, kaya nga sila kinuha na ni Kap, yung HOA, para makatulong sa bawat solusyon. Kasi hindi kaya naman talaga ng Barangay lahat na bantayan, iilan lang ang Tanod, gaanong kalaki naman ang ating populasyon. So ‘yon, yung problema is parang community problem, not Barangay. Pero yung ganito pong topic, yung ganitong parang apps, is maganda. Sa akin, maganda. Huwag lang maging public. Ayun, ganoon lang po yung sa akin. Basta lahat po yun, naa-address naman ng...

QUESTION 5 (Insight 2): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers) Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling	“Yes, para sa akin, ganoon, oo. Parang baka, yun nga, yung privacy nila, masyadong maaano, magiging talk of the town pa sila ng kanilang mga kapitbahay. Parang baka mag-away.” “So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

	Community Problems/Issues)	<i>humahawak...Barang ay."</i>	
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Yes, para sa akin, ganoon, oo. Parang baka, yun nga, yung privacy nila, masyadong maaano, magiging talk of the town pa sila ng kanilang mga kapitbahay. Parang baka mag-away. So pinakamaganda na lang talaga, meron lang humahawak.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 1): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Environment

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Influence on Tackling Community Problems/Issues Via Chairman’s Trust Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Saka kami naman po, sir, dito po sa mga kawani, may malasakit naman po sa bawat ano. Kaya nga po kami nilagay ni Kap bawat isang ano para po may ma-tap doon. Sa amin po, wala pong nagrereklamo, pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within - X
			Power Over -

<p>NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S</p>			<p>Power With - Power To - Power Within –</p>
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Saka kami naman po, sir, dito po sa mga kawani, may malasakit naman po sa bawat ano. Kaya nga po kami nilagay ni Kap bawat isang ano para po may ma-tap doon. Sa amin po, wala pong nagrereklamo, pinaparating lang po sa akin tapos pini-pm ko na lang po si Kap. Kaya nalalaman din po niya.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 3): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Lupon

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it	Recommendation on Tackling Community Problems/Issues	<i>“Ang sa akin naman, parang suggestion ko lang, siguro para mabigyan ng tamang solusyon itong mga problemang ‘to, tulad ng basurang ‘yan, aso, mga rugby boys na ‘yan, siguro magkaroon ng public forum.”</i>	Power Over - Power With - X Power To - Power Within - X
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -

Ang sa akin naman, parang suggestion ko lang, siguro para mabigyan ng tamang solusyon itong mga problemang 'to, tulad ng basurang 'yan, aso, mga rugby boys na 'yan, siguro magkaroon ng public forum.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 1): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Assertion of Barangay Implementation Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Nagawa na ‘yan ni Kap eh.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Nagawa na 'yan ni Kap eh.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 4): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Lupon

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues) Residents’ Perceived Lack of Discipline	<i>“Oo nga, magkaroon ng public forum, masabi lahat sa tao kung ano yung mga dapat na solusyonan na ano.”</i> <i>“Katulad niyan, eto’y kung tutuusin, problema ng bawat ano ‘to eh, tao lang sa kapaligiran natin eh,</i>	Power Over - X Power With - X Power To - Power Within –

		<p>yung mga rugby boys. Kanino bang anak 'yan? O, 'di ba dapat yung magulang ang mag-ano diyan, mag-suheto sa mga...tapos 'yang mga basura, 'yan naman eh, kung ikaw eh may ano sa sarili mo, may disiplina ka, kaya mo namang linisin 'yan eh, hindi para ikalat mo 'yan sa bang-bang eh. 'Di ba?"</p> <p>"Kaya siguro, maaaring ulitin uli ang public forum para mabigyan ng...malaman uli nila na mali yung ginagawa nilang 'yan."</p>	
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Oo nga, magkaroon ng public forum, masabi lahat sa tao kung ano yung mga dapat na solusyonan na ano. Katulad niyan, eto'y kung tutuusin, problema ng bawat ano 'to eh, tao lang sa kapaligiran natin eh, yung mga rugby boys. Kanino bang anak 'yan? O, 'di ba dapat yung magulang ang mag-ano diyan, mag-suheto sa mga...tapos 'yang mga basura, 'yan naman eh, kung ikaw eh may ano sa sarili mo, may disiplina ka, kaya mo namang linisin 'yan eh, hindi para ikalat mo 'yan sa bang-bang eh. 'Di ba? Kaya siguro, maaaring ulitin uli ang public forum para mabigyan ng...malaman uli nila na mali yung ginagawa nilang 'yan.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 5): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Lupon

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Limited Only to Barangay Decision-Makers) Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling	<i>“Baka hindi. Ngayon, siya lang ang mag-ano nito, magsagawa ng schedule.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

	Community Problems/Issues)		
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Baka hindi. Ngayon, siya lang ang mag-ano nito, magsagawa ng schedule.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 3): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Administration

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Only Limited to Barangay Decision-Makers) Adherence to Hierarchy (in	<i>“Maraming makakakita.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

	Tackling Community Problems/Issues)		
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Maraming makakakita.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 2): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): VAWC

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Adherence to Hierarchy (in Tackling Community Problems/Issues)	<i>“Yung mga kalaban, siyempre, negative lahat ng sasabihin.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

Yung mga kalaban, siyempre, negative lahat ng sasabihin.

QUESTION 5 (Insight 2): How do the geospatial direct-address videos as alternative participatory governance device compare to your already existing problem identification and decision-making mechanisms (if any) in the barangay?

Representative of Department (Barangay Decision-Maker): Environment

Participatory Outcomes Tufte and Mefalopulos (2009)	Themes	Examples from Text (Interview Transcript)	Distinctions About Power VeneKlasen and Miller (2002)
Feelings of Ownership – psycho-social outcomes of increased feelings of ownership of a problem and a commitment to do something about it			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
Improvement of Competencies and Capacities – as required to engage with the defined development problem			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within -
Influence on Institutions – actual influence on institutions that can affect an individual or community			Power Over - Power With - Power To - Power Within –
NONE OBSERVED IN THE ANSWER/S	Limited Access to the Geospatial Direct-Address Videos (Only Limited to Barangay Decision-Makers) Adherence to Hierarchy (in	<i>“Sa amin, dito po, pwede po ‘yan, sir. Sa Barangay po.”</i>	Power Over - X Power With - Power To - Power Within –

	Tackling Community Problems/Issues)		
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Sa amin, dito po, pwede po 'yan, sir. Sa Barangay po.